

DONOR-ACCEPTOR SYSTEMS BASED ON PORPHYRINS AND CORROLES

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By

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*Dedicated to my
beloved
parents*

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Certificate

This is to certify that the thesis entitled "*Donor-acceptor based systems on porphyrins and corroles*" being submitted by *Mr. B. Shivaprasadachary*, to Osmania University, Hyderabad for the award of the degree of Doctor of Philosophy is a record of bonafied research work carried out by him.

Mr. B. Shivaprasadachary, has worked under my guidance and has fulfilled the requirements for the submission of thesis. The results in this thesis have not been submitted for any degree or diploma of this or any other university.

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DECLARATION

I hereby declared that the scientific contents of this thesis are based on my original work carried out under the guidance of **Dr. Lingamallu Giribabu**, Principal Scientist, CSIR-Indian Institute of Chemical technology, Hyderabad-500007. To the best of my knowledge this work has not been submitted to this or any other University for the award of the Ph.D. degree.

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Abbreviations

D-A	Donor-acceptor
DSSC	Dye sensitized solar cell
ATP	Adenosine tri phosphate
NADP	Nicotinamide adenine dinucleotide phosphate
NADPH	Nicotinamide adenine dinucleotide phosphate hydrogen
RC	Reaction centre
PRC	Photosynthetic Reaction centre
PS-I	Photo system-I
PS-II	Photo system-II
EET	Exited energy transfer
PET	Photo induced electron transfer
CS	Charge separation
TiO ₂	Titanium dioxide
MLCT	Metal to ligand charge transfer
CST	Charge separated state
VR	Vibrational relaxation
IC	Internal conversion
ISC	Inter system crossing
Fl	Florescence
Ph	Phosphorescence
D*	Excited state Donor

A*	Excited state Acceptor
FRET	Forster resonance energy transfer
k_{ET}	Energy transfer rate
ΔG_0	Gibbs free energy change
TS	Transition state
DPM	Dipyrromethane
PAH	Poly aromatic hydrocarbons
BDP	Boron dipyrromethane
MHz	Mega hertz
Fc	Ferrocene
WE	Working electrode
SCE	Stranded calomel electrode
RE	Reference electrode
CCDC	Cambridge crystal data centre
HOMO	High occupied molecular orbitals
LUMO	Low occupied molecular orbitals
MEPD	Molecular electron potential diagram
SE	Stimulated emission
ESA	Exited state absorption
SADS	Species associated difference spectra
GSB	Ground state bleaching
eV	Electron volt
ΔG_{PET}	Gibbs free energy change for Photo induced electron transfer

ΔG_{EN}	Gibbs free energy change for energy transfer
LED	Light emitted diode
CT	Charge transfer
OD	Optical density
UV-vis	Ultra violet and visible
CV	Cyclic voltammetry
DPV	Differential pulse voltammetry
TBAP	Tetra butyl ammonium perchlorate
OX(P)	Oxidation potential
R(P)	Reduction potential
E_{0-0}	Excitation Transition Energies
E_{HOMO}	HOMO energy level
E_{LUMO}	LUMO energy level
SCE	Standard Calomel Electrode
DFT	Density Functional Theory
TD-DFT	Time dependent density functional theory
mmol	mill mole
RT	Room Temperature
hrs	Hours
NMR	Nuclear magnetic resonance
MALDI	Matrix assisted laser desorption/ ionisation
m/z	Mass to charge ratio
ppm	Parts per million

NOESY	Nuclear Overhauser effect spectroscopy
AFM	Atomic force microscopy
TEM	Transmission electron microscopy
ϵ	Molar extinction coefficient
ns	Nano second
ps	Pico second
fs	Femto second

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This thesis entitled “**Donor-acceptor systems based on porphyrins and corroles**” deals with design, synthesis, theoretical aspects, spectroscopy, electrochemical, photo physical characterisation and excited state dynamics of porphyrin and corrole macrocycles, that have been covalently bonded either at axial or peripheral position/s and supramolecular π - π interaction with electron acceptor units. The major attention has been laid on the design of molecular structures in order to study the long lived charge transfer state and formation of near-IR charge transfer complex of porphyrin and corrole based donor acceptor systems to mimic the natural photosynthetic reaction centre.

Construction of donor-acceptor (D-A) systems using tetrapyrrolic compounds, plays an important role to explain the photo driven processes such as electron, energy and charge-transfer reactions, the most important in nature photosynthetic process. These charge separated species not only useful to understand the various biological process but also have several optoelectronic applications.¹ In the end such studies, either theoretical or experimental, provide fundamental knowledge for applied research on how to design controllable molecular systems in which one can tune the flow of electrons or energy.

Porphyrins and corroles are belongs to tetrapyrrolic family, their metallo/metalloid derivatives possess tunable electrochemical and photophysical applications in various research areas such as molecular electronics, molecular catalysis, photodynamic therapy *etc.*²⁻⁶ Porphyrins structurally close relation with chlorophyll pigment and corroles are one carbon atom less and are present in Vitamin B12. A great variety of D-A systems based on porphyrins and corroles have been reported in the literature.⁷⁻¹⁰ Among them Porphyrins and corroles with metallocenes based D-A systems have not reported for generation of long lived charge separated species by using its peripheral (either *meso* or β -pyrrole) positions. In contrast, construction of D-A systems by using axial position/s of resident metal/metalloid ion of corroles are relatively less known in literature due to the stability and synthetic protocols of corrole macrocycle compared to the porphyrins. Extension of π -conjugation in porphyrins by fusing macrocycle with hydrocarbons such as anthracene, pyrene *etc.*, will shift the absorption towards red region and these fused porphyrins with good acceptor such as perlynediimide to form charge transfer complex. In this thesis, the theme of energy/electron transfer between donor-acceptors and formation of charge-transfer complex in the systems designed to investigate the phenomenon are examined.

The work elucidated in this thesis has been divided into seven chapters. A brief, chapter-wise account of the results is presented below.

Chapter 1. Introduction

In this chapter we have discussed about the brief introduction of natural photosynthesis and importance of artificial photosynthesis, theories involved in energy and electron transfer, particularly in D-A systems. Literature survey on artificial donor-acceptor systems development and formation of their long lived charge transfer state of various ‘peripherally’- and ‘axially’ substituted porphyrins, and corroles have been discussed.

Chapter 2. Materials and methods

This chapter consists list of chemicals used and their purification methods and also summarize spectroscopic, electrochemical, magnetic resonance and photo physical techniques involved to study and characterize the materials during the research work.

Chapter 3. Synthesis, Structure and Photophysical Properties of Ferrocenyl or mixed Sandwich Cobaltocenyl Ester Linked meso-Tetratolylporphyrin Dyads

In this chapter, we designed and synthesized porphyrin-metallocene dyads consisting of a metallocene [either ferrocene or mixed sandwich η^5 -[C₅H₄(COOH)]Co(η^4 -C₄Ph₄)] connected *via* an ester linkage at *meso* phenyl position of either free-base [**H₂TTPFe** or **H₂TTPCo**] or zinc porphyrin [**Zn-TTPFe** or **Zn-TTPCo**] (Figure 1). All these dyad systems were characterized by various spectroscopic and electrochemical methods. X-ray crystal structure of **Zn-TTPCo** suggests that the complex exists in dimeric form. The absorption spectra of all four dyads measured in dichloromethane solvent and indicated the absence of electronic interactions between porphyrin macrocycle and metallocene in the ground state. Electrochemical properties suggest that redox values of dyads are not much different from monomeric units. However, interestingly, in all four dyads, fluorescence emission of the porphyrin was quenched (19-55%) as compared to their monomeric units. The quenching was more pronounced in ferrocene derivatives rather than cobaltocenyl derivatives. The emission quenching can be attributed to the excited state intramolecular photoinduced electron transfer from metallocene to singlet excited state of porphyrin and the electron transfer rates (k_{ET}) were established in the range 1.51×10^8 to 1.11×10^9 s⁻¹ (Table 1).

Figure 1. Molecular structures of porphyrin-metalloenes.

Table 1. Fluorescence data and Fluorescence decay parameters.

Dyads	$\lambda_{em}, nm^*(\Phi_F, \% Q)^\dagger \lambda_{ex} = 420 nm$			$\tau, ns (A\%), \lambda_{ex} = 405 nm^\ddagger$		
	Toluene	CH ₂ Cl ₂	CH ₃ CN	Toluene	CH ₂ Cl ₂	CH ₃ CN
H₂TTP	653, 719 (0.11)	653, 719 (0.13)	653, 719 (0.14)	9.6	9.2	9.2
H₂TTPCo	654, 721 (0.073, 33%)	653, 719 (0.09, 31%),	654, 718 (0.09, 36%)	6.4 1.56x10⁸	6.6 1.51x10⁸	6.6 1.51x10⁸
H₂TTPFe	653, 720 (0.056, 49%)	653, 720 (0.065, 50%)	653, 720 (0.063, 55%)	3.4 (66) 5.8 (34) 2.94x10⁸	3.6 (67) 6.1 (33) 2.77x10⁸	3.6 (67) 6.1 (33) 2.77x10⁸
ZnTTP	599, 642 (0.037)	603, 649 0.036	606, 659 0.042	2.07(95) 1.11(5)	1.76(95) 1.17(5)	1.72(89) 2.86(11)
Zn-TTPCo	605, 656 (0.030, 19%)	598, 648 (0.024, 33%)	606, 658 (0.026, 38%)	0.9 (63) 1.6 (37) 1.11x10⁹	1.1 (77) 2.1 (23) 9.09x10⁸	1.1 (88) 2.4 (12) 9.01x10⁸
Zn-TTPFe	606, 656 (0.027, 27%)	598, 649 (0.023, 36%)	598, 648 (0.021, 50%)	1.0 (90) 3.4 (10) 9.99x10⁸	1.0 (83) 2.7 (17) 9.99x10⁸	1.1 (83) 2.7 (17) 9.09x10⁸

*Error limits: $\lambda_{ex}, \pm 2 nm, \Phi \pm 10\%$. $\dagger Q$ is defined in Eq. 2 (see text). \ddagger All lifetimes are in nanoseconds (ns), Error limits of $\tau \sim 10\%$. Bold value denotes rate constant in s^{-1} .

(*Photochem. Photobiol.*, **2015**, *91*, 33-41.)

Chapter 4. Synthesis, characterization and photophysical properties of ferrocene and mixed sandwich cobaltocenyl ester linked meso- triaryl corrole dyads

Figure 2. Molecular structures of Corrole-metalloenes as **Dyad 1** and **Dyad 2**.

In order to further understand about the long lived charge separated states, herein, we extended similar design concept to other member of tetrapyrrolic family such as corroles. In this chapter, we designed and synthesised corrole-metalloene dyads consisting of metallocene [either ferrocene (**Dyad 1**) or mixed sandwich η^5 -[C₅H₄(COOH)]Co(η^4 -C₄Ph₄) (**Dyad 2**) connected *via* an ester linkage at *meso* phenyl position (Figure 2). Both the dyads were characterized by ¹H NMR, MALDI-TOF, UV-visible, fluorescence spectroscopies (steady-state, picosecond time-resolved), femtosecond transient absorption spectroscopy (*fs*-TA) and electrochemical methods. The absorption spectra of these dyads showed slight broadening and splitting of Soret band that indicates a weak ground state interaction between the corrole macrocycle and metallocene part of these D-A systems. The electrochemical properties suggest that redox properties are not altered. The ground-state properties suggest that there exist ground state interactions between metallocene and corrole macrocycle. DFT studies suggest that both HOMO and LUMO resides on corrole macrocycle. However, in both the dyad systems, fluorescence emission of the corrole was quenched in polar solvents as compared to its parent compound 10-(4-hydroxyphenyl)-5,15-bis-(pentafluorophenyl) corrole (**Ph-Corr**). The quenching was more pronounced in ferrocene derivatives rather than cobaltocenyl derivatives may be due to more electron releasing nature of ferrocene (Table 2). Transient absorption studies confirm the absence of photoinduced electron transfer from metallocene to corrole for these dyad systems and the quenching of singlet state of corrole is found to enhance intersystem crossing due to heavy atom effect.

Table 2. Fluorescence decay parameters[†] and electron transfer rate constants (k_{ET} , S⁻¹).[‡]

Compound	(τ, ns (A%), k_{ET} , s ⁻¹)			
	Toluene	ODCB	CH ₂ Cl ₂	CH ₃ CN
Ph-Corr	4.16	4.13	3.98	3.88
Dyad 1	3.42(99)	3.26(95)	3.20(97)	2.66(97)
	3.35(1)	10.4(5)	2.33(2)	10.7(3)
	2.9x10⁸	3.1x10⁸	3.1x10⁸	3.8x10⁸
Dyad 2	3.76(98)	3.74(93)	3.61(100)	2.96 (94)
	10.7(2)	10.2(7)	2.8x10⁸	6.13 (6)
	2.7x10⁸	2.7x10⁸		3.4x10⁸

[‡] Error limits of τ and k_{ET} ~ 10%. Values in parenthesis are relative amplitude of corresponding decay component.

(*J. Porphyrins Phthalocyanines.*, **2017**, 21, 646–657.)

Chapter 5. Axially substituted phosphorous(V) corrole with polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons: Synthesis, X-ray structure, and photoinduced energy and electron transfer studies

Figure 3. Molecular structures of axially linked Corroles triads.

In the previous chapter, we have utilized *meso* phenyl positions of corrole macrocycle in the construction of D-A systems. One of the methods, that one can minimize the

aggregation of corroles is utilization of axial position/s. The concept of ‘Axial bonding’ is not much explored in corrole chemistry. Here, we have utilized axial positions of a Phosphorous(V) corrole in the construction of D-A systems. This approach is facile, modular, by conducting hydroxyl condensation at axial positions of a metalloid corrole to avoid tedious synthetic protocols. This has been encouraged in the study of axially linking 5,10,15- tris(pentafluorophenyl)corroleP(V), **P(tpfc)(OH)₂** with polyaromatic hydrocarbons (PAH) either naphthalene (**Triad 1**) or pyrene (**Triad 2**) as shown in Figure 3. Both the triads were characterized by various spectroscopic techniques and electrochemical methods. The X-ray structure of **Triad 1** revealed the presence of two naphthalene entities bound to the phosphorous centre without causing steric crowding (Figure 4).

Figure 4. Molecular Structure of **Triad 1**. H atoms have been omitted for clarity.

The electrochemical and computational studies of both the triads, excited state events, monitored by both time-resolved emission and transient absorption studies, revealed several interesting results. In the case of **Triad 1**, efficient energy transfer takes place from singlet excited naphthalene to corrole (Table 3), however, no photo events from excited phosphorous corrole were evident. Interestingly, in the case of **Triad 2**, although energy transfer process from singlet excited pyrene to corrole was weak, evidence of photoinduced charge separation leading to the formation of pyrene⁺-PC⁻ was witnessed from femtosecond transient absorption studies when either pyrene or corrole was selectively excited. The importance of

axial bound donor entities on phosphorous(V) corrole in promoting photoinduced energy and electron transfer events is borne out from the present study.

Table 3. Energy transfer data of **Triad 1**^a

	Solvent	%Q	%T	k_{obs} (10^9 s^{-1})	$k_{\text{EN}}^{(\text{obs})}$ (10^9 s^{-1}) ^e	J^d ($\text{cm}^6 \text{ mmol}^{-1}$) ^c	k_{Forster} (10^{13} s^{-1}) ^d
Triad 1	Toluene ($n = 1.496$, $\varepsilon = 2.24$) ^b	89	80	0.58	0.29	0.26×10^{-13}	0.15
	DCM ($n = 1.452$, $\varepsilon = 8.93$) ^b	85	80	0.81	0.57	2.52×10^{-13}	3.32
	DMSO ($n = 1.477$, $\varepsilon = 46.7$) ^b	75	71	0.06	0.05	0.02×10^{-13}	0.49

^aError limits: %Q, $k_{\text{obs}} \pm 8\%$, %T, $k_{\text{EN}}^{(\text{obs})}$: $\pm 15\%$. ^b n and ε refer to refractive index and dielectric constant of the solvents, respectively. ^cSpectral overlap term calculated by using PhotochemCAD software.²⁷ ^d $\kappa^2 = 0.66$ in all the cases and $R_{\text{c-c}} = 5.65 \text{ \AA}$ (**Triad 1**). ^e $k_{\text{EN}}^{(\text{obs})}$ calculated by using equation. $\frac{T_{\text{obs}}/(1-T_{\text{obs}})}{\tau(\text{PAH})} T_{\text{obs}}$, energy transfer efficiency, was calculate from the overlap of the excitation and absorption spectra. 1.496; 2.240.

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Chapter 6. Unprecedented Charge-Transfer Complex of Fused Diporphyrin as Near-Infrared Absorption Induced High Aspect Ratio Nanorods

In the previous three chapters, we have used covalent bond in construction of D-A systems. In natural photosynthesis matrix aids in various supramolecular interactions between donor-acceptor systems *via* π - π stacking, Van der waal interaction, and hydrogen bonding to form charge transfer complex. Structural similarities between donor and acceptor are rather important to achieve this phenomenon. Herein, we are designed, synthesized and characterized near IR-charge transfer complex by electron donors such as non-fused diporphyrin-anthracene (**DP**), zinc diporphyrin-anthracene (**ZnDP**) and fused zinc diporphyrin-anthracene (**FZnDP**) in which **FZnDP** absorbs in NIR region, and perylenediimide (**PDI**) as an electron acceptor to form near-IR charge transfer complex (CT) by supramoleculor π - π interaction.

Synthetic scheme of **FZnDP** is shown in Figure 5. UV-vis-NIR absorption, ^1H nuclear magnetic resonance, Nosey spectroscopy and powder X-ray diffraction analysis demonstrated that the CT complex formation occurs by π - π stacking between perylene in **FZnDP** and **PDI** upon mixing together at 1:1 molar concentration in CHCl_3 , unlike non-fused **ZnDP** and **DP** (Figure 6 & 7). Transmission electron microscopic and atomic force microscopic images revealed that CT complex initially forms nanospheres leading to nanorods by diffusion of CH_3OH vapours into the CHCl_3 solution of **FZnDP/PDI** (1:1 M) (Figure 6).

Figure 5. Synthetic scheme of **DP**, **ZnDP** and **FZnDP**.

Figure 6. (a) Chemical structures of diporphyrin-anthracene (**DP**) and zinc diporphyrin-anthracene (**ZnDP**). (b) Structure of fused zinc diporphyrin-anthracene (**FZnDP**) and corresponding pictorial representation. (c) Schematic representation of mixture of **FZnDP** and **PDI** leads CT complex in CHCl_3 , which results nanospheres and coalesced to form nanorods by diffusion of CH_3OH vapours.

Figure 7. UV-vis-NIR optical absorption spectra of a) **DP**, **ZnDP** and **FZnDP** before and after mixing of **PDI** in CHCl_3 at 2×10^{-5} M at 25°C . at 1:1 molar ratio. b) Absorption spectra of stoichiometric ratio (0-1 equivalents) of **PDI** to the **FZnDP** (1 equivalent, 2×10^{-5} M) added successively and recorded at 25°C .

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Chapter 7. Conclusions & Future work

This chapter presents general conclusions based on the investigations carried out in this work and discussed in further extending plans for future work.

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Chapter-1

Introduction

1.1. General introduction

Solar energy is the most abundant renewable source. Plants efficiently convert the solar energy into chemical energy by photosynthesis utilizing highly organized photo systems. These systems are based on light-harvesting antennas comprised of large number of self-organized chlorophylls, which absorb light energy and transfer it to the photosynthetic reaction center (site of electron-hole separation). Green plants and bacteria consist of complex collection of chromophores non-covalently bound to a protein scaffold, which fix the cofactors in a definite distance and facilitates efficient electron transfer. The proteins also plays vital role to modulate the functioning of the cofactors and directs the electron-transfer pathways. In this way, natural photosynthesis depends significantly on light absorption, excitation energy transfer and charge separation processes for efficient solar energy conversion.

Furthermore, developing environmentally sustainable solutions to meet the increasing energy demands of the world is one of the most important goals of research. Thereby, lot of efforts has been devoted into the development of molecular systems which mimic the function of the photosynthetic systems. The collection of light over a wide spectral range and the population in long-lived charge-separated state constitute the major factors in building artificial systems. Thus, these processes prove to be the fundamental basic for photovoltaic technologies. Lack of understanding of the fundamentals in photophysics and photochemistry of artificial systems, noticed, since most of the work mainly focused on development of materials and device fabrication. For this reason, our goal was to investigate the processes following photo excitation, a better understanding of which is necessary for an optimal design of efficient architectures for photovoltaic devices.

In the artificial systems, macrocyclic complexes were designed to imitate the structural features of intermolecular interactions and thermodynamic parameters in bacterial photosynthetic system explaining well the mechanism of self-assembly process. Several covalently and non-covalently linked donor-acceptor moieties with definite distance and orientation were designed and studied. Covalent and non-covalent interactions and charge transfer self-assembly processes, such as the formation of π stacks, hydrogen bonds and van der Waals contacts, well utilized to connect the donor-acceptor entities to achieve efficient energy transfer and intramolecular electron-transfer processes. In majority of these studies,

porphyrins,¹ corroles,² phthalocyanines³ have been used as electron donors and fullerenes,⁴ anthraquinones,⁵ perylene imides⁶ as acceptors to understand the significance of excitation energy transfer (EET) and photoinduced electron transfer (PET) reactions. For a better understanding, a variety of multichromophoric donor acceptor systems were synthesized by our group,⁷ and studied employing various spectroscopic methods.

In the next section of the chapter, we briefly review the fundamentals of photophysical and photochemical processes that are predominant in the explored systems after absorption of light. Time resolved spectroscopy applied as a main tool to monitor the dynamics of these processes as energy and electron migration are among the fastest events in chemistry and take place on time scale range from tens of femtoseconds to few nanoseconds. The principles and the experimental details of the techniques used during the thesis work will be described (Chapter 2). In the following chapters, the main projects carried out during my thesis will be presented. In Chapter 3, an intramolecular photoinduced electron transfer in porphyrin dyads with metallocenes were examined. Next two chapters explain the excited-state dynamics of corrole-metallocene dyads (Chapter 4) and corrole triads with polyaromatic hydrocarbons (Chapter 5). Besides that, fused porphyrins as efficient near IR charge transfer complexes were also discussed (Chapter 6). The aim of the work was to develop efficient charge transfer systems and Donor-Acceptor systems to study the energy and electron transfer processes. The entire thesis is served to improve our understanding on molecular donor-acceptor interactions to mimic artificial photosynthesis from theoretical to practical applications.

1.2. Photosynthesis

The process of photosynthesis has been studied for long time; many scientists contributed their discoveries towards this process

- The first discovery by Jan van Helmont in the 17th century (1643), who discovered that the mass of a growing plant came from water and carbon dioxide not from soil.
- In the next century, Joseph Priestly (1771) performed the classic ‘bell jar’ experiments. He was the first person to show that plants produce oxygen gas.
- Jan Ingenhousz (1779) finds that aquatic plants produce oxygen bubbles in the presence of sunlight but not in the dark.

- Julius Robert Mayer (1845) in 19th century proposed that plants can convert light energy into chemical energy.
- T.W. Engelmann (1881) concluded that plants absorb the light they need (red and blue) and reflect the rest (green).
- Samuel Ruben & Martin Kamen (1941) used isotopes to determine that the oxygen liberated in photosynthesis comes from water.
- Melvin Calvin 19480 and coworkers 20th century were first to trace the complete path that carbon travels through a plant during photosynthesis, starting from its absorption as atmospheric carbon dioxide to its conversion into carbohydrates and other organic compounds and proposed Calvin cycle. He was the sole recipient of the 1961 Nobel Prize for chemistry
- Rudolph Marcus (1992) described the electron transport chain due to fact that electron transfer is common, as well as essential reaction within the nature. He won the Nobel Prize, 1992 in Chemistry for describing the process by which electrons are transferred from one molecule to another in the electron transport chain. Marcus's theory has become vital within the field of chemistry.

1.2.1 Natural Photosynthetic Process

Naturally photosynthesis occurs in many kinds of bacteria and algae, plants, some protists, leaves and sometimes the stems of green plants which involve the conversion of light energy into chemical energy. The cells of plant leaves contain organelles called chloroplasts that actually carry out the photosynthetic process. No other structure in a plant cell is able to carry out photosynthesis. The photosynthetic process depends on a set of complex protein molecules that are located in and around a highly organized membrane in chloroplast, through a series of energy transducing reactions. Photosynthesis can be defined as the physicochemical process by which photosynthetic organisms use light energy to drive the synthesis of stable form that is carbohydrates and liberates oxygen.

Photosynthesis takes place in three stages:

- (a) Capturing energy from sunlight;
- (b) Using the energy to make ATP and reducing power in the form of a compound called NADPH.

(c) Using the ATP and NADPH to power the synthesis of organic molecules from CO₂ in the air (carbon fixation).

The first two stages take place in the presence of light and are commonly called the **light reactions**. The third stage, the formation of organic molecules from atmospheric CO₂, is called the **Calvin cycle**. As long as ATP and NADPH are available, the Calvin cycle may occur in the absence of light, called as **dark reaction**. These all reactions of photosynthesis take place within thylakoid membranes within chloroplasts in leaf cells (Figure. 1.1)

The final result of photosynthesis in nature can be summarized by the well-known equation.

Figure 1.1. Structure of Chloroplast.

In whole photosynthetic process two different kind of reactions will takes place, one is in presence of light and the other in absence of light accounted below.

1.2.1.1 Light dependent reactions: (In Thylakoid)

Light-dependent series of reactions which occur in the **grana**, and require the direct energy of light to make energy-carrier molecules that are used in the second process:

- Light energy is trapped by chlorophyll to make ATP (photophosphorylation)
- Water is split into oxygen, hydrogen ions and free electrons:
$$2\text{H}_2\text{O} \longrightarrow 4\text{H}^+ + \text{O}_2 + 4\text{e}^- \text{ (photolysis) } \dots\dots\dots (1.2)$$
- Electrons then react with a carrier molecule nicotinamide adenine dinucleotide phosphate (NADP), changing it from its oxidized state (NADP⁺) to its reduced state (NADPH).
$$\text{NADP}^+ + 2\text{e}^- + 2\text{H}^+ \longrightarrow \text{NADPH} + \text{H}^+ \dots\dots\dots (1.3)$$

1.2.1.2 Light independent reactions: (Calvin Cycle-Stroma)

Light-independent series of reactions which occur in the stroma of the chloroplasts, when the products of the light reaction, ATP and NADPH, are used to make carbohydrates from carbon dioxide (reduction), initially glyceraldehyde 3-phosphate is formed.

The internal membranes of chloroplasts are organized into sacs called *thylakoids*, and often numerous thylakoids are stacked on one another in columns called *grana*. The thylakoid membranes house the photosynthetic pigments for capturing light energy and the machinery to make ATP. Surrounding the thylakoid membrane system is a semi liquid substance called stroma. The stroma houses the enzymes needed to assemble carbon molecules. In the membranes of thylakoids, photosynthetic pigments are clustered together to form a photosystem.

Each pigment molecule within the photosystem is capable of capturing *photons*, which are packets of energy. A lattice of proteins holds the pigments in close contact with one another. When light of a proper wavelength strikes a pigment molecule in the photosystem, the resulting excitation passes from one chlorophyll molecule to another. The excited electron is not transferred physically it is the *energy* that passes from one molecule to another. A crude analogy to this form of energy transfer is the initial “break” in a game of pool. If the cue ball squarely hits the point of the triangular array of pool balls, the two balls at the far corners of the triangle fly off, but none of the central balls move. The energy passes through the central balls to the most distant ones. Eventually the energy arrives at a key chlorophyll molecule that is touching a membrane-bound protein. The energy is transferred

as an excited electron to that protein, which passes it on to a series of other membrane proteins that put the energy to work making ATP and NADPH and building organic molecules. The photosystem thus acts as a large antenna, gathering the light harvested by many individual pigment molecules.

1.2.1.3 Pigments and absorption

Molecules that which are good absorbers of light in the visible range are called pigments. Organisms have evolved a variety of different pigments. All photosynthetic organisms have chlorophyll-*a*. Accessory pigments absorb energy that chlorophyll-*a* does not absorb. Accessory pigments include chlorophyll-*b* (also *c*, *d*, and *e* in algae and protistans), xanthophylls, and carotenoids (such as beta-carotene). Two main general pigments involved in green plant photosynthesis are chlorophylls and carotenoids. Chlorophyll-*a* absorbs its energy from the violet-blue and reddish orange-red wavelengths, and a little from the intermediate (green-yellow-orange) with wavelengths between 500 and 600 nm, and light of these wavelengths is, therefore, reflected by plants. When these photons are subsequently absorbed by the pigment in our eyes, we perceive them as green (Figure 1.2).

Figure 1.2. a) Structure of Chlorophyll-*a* and b) absorption spectra of various natural pigments.

The conversion of usable sunlight energy into chemical energy is mainly associated with the action of the green pigment Chlorophyll-*a* and is the only pigment that can act directly to convert light energy to chemical energy. However, chlorophyll *b*, acting as an accessory or secondary light-absorbing pigment, complements and adds to the light absorption of chlorophyll-*a*. Chlorophyll-*b* has an absorption spectrum shifted toward the

green wavelengths. Therefore, chlorophyll-*b* can absorb photons chlorophyll-*a* can't. Chlorophyll-*b* therefore greatly increases the proportion of the photons in sunlight that plants can harvest. An important group of accessory pigments, the carotenoids, assist in photosynthesis by capturing energy from light of wavelengths that are not efficiently absorbed by either chlorophyll.

All chlorophylls have:

- A lipid-soluble hydrocarbon tail (C₂₀H₃₉ -)
- A flat hydrophilic head with a magnesium ion at its centre; different chlorophylls have different side-groups on the head

The tail and head are linked by an ester bond.

The electron transfer occurs in reaction center of chlorophyll. Donates a light induced electron to the primary electron acceptor and reducing it. The oxidized chlorophyll then fills its electron hole by oxidizing a donor molecule. (Figure 1.3). Photosynthesis electron donor and acceptor entities are arranged *via* non-covalent incorporation of well-defined protein complex.⁸ light induced electron transfer and energy transfer events occur between these well-organized pigments. The electron transfer (charge separation or formation of radical ion pair) occurs with remarkable high efficiency of almost 1, while eliminating the energy wasting by back electron transfer. The small overall reorganization energy ($\lambda \sim 0.2$ eV), exhibited by the photosynthetic reaction centers and the well-balanced electronic coupling between the electron donor and acceptor entities have been attributed to the high efficiency of charge separation

Figure 1.3. The reaction center chlorophyll donates a light-energized electron to the primary electron acceptor, reducing it. The oxidized chlorophyll then fills its electron “hole” by oxidizing a donor molecule.

1.2.1.4 Factors affecting the rate of photosynthesis

The main factors are light intensity, carbon dioxide concentration and temperature, known as limiting factors.

- As light intensity increases the rate of the light-dependent reaction, and therefore photosynthesis generally increases proportionately. As light intensity is increased however, the rate of photosynthesis is eventually limited by some other factor. Chlorophyll *a* is used in both photosystems-I and II. The wavelength of light is also important. PSI absorbs energy most efficiently at 700 nm and PSII at 680 nm. Light with a high proportion of energy concentrated in these wavelengths will produce a high rate of photosynthesis.
- An increase in the carbon dioxide concentration increases the rate at which carbon is incorporated into carbohydrate in the light-independent reaction and so the rate of photosynthesis generally increases until limited by another factor.
- Photosynthesis is dependent on temperature. It is a reaction catalysed by enzymes. As the enzymes approach their optimum temperatures the overall rate increases. Above the optimum temperature the rate begins to decrease until it stops.

1.2.2 Artificial photosynthesis

Artificial photosynthesis has the potential to solve both the environmental and energy challenges. The idea behind artificial photosynthesis is to create a biomimetic system which can utilize the energy of the Sun in a similar fashion to photosynthetic organisms. In addition to converting light into more accessible forms of energy, a secondary goal is the storage of this captured energy for use at a later time. One of the advantages of synthesizing photosynthetic antennae is the range of components we can incorporate, which are not limited to what is producible by a bio cell's mechanics.⁹ Also, unlike natural photosynthetic centers, artificial reaction centers can use covalent bonds rather than protein scaffolds to maintain the physical arrangement and electronic coupling of components,¹⁰ which again simplifies the antenna and reaction centre, and reduces production time, cost, and resources needed for construction.

However, artificial photosynthetic systems don't need any bio membranes so they are not limit by biology in that respect. Some examples of such systems are;

- Kay and Grätzel¹¹ used natural porphyrins on colloidal TiO₂ electrodes to generate photo-induced charge separation, the efficiencies of which were comparable to natural photosynthesis. They found that conjugation between the chromophore and anchoring carboxyl group is not required for efficient electron transfer.
- Imahori *et al.*¹² produced three different mixed self-assembled monolayers for energy and electron transfer to a gold surface in a study mimicking photosynthesis. A quantum yield of 50±8% and an incident photon-to-current efficiency of 1.6% were achieved.
- Imahori *et al.*¹³ produced self-assembling mono layers of ferrocene-porphyrin-C₆₀ triads on gold electrodes which, when irradiated, gave high quantum efficiencies of 20-25%.
- Ferrer *et al.*¹⁴ designed and characterized a ruthenium containing supra-molecular system capable of mimicking the function of a macroscopic electrical extension cable, with a light powered electron source.

1.2.2.1 Light harvesting systems

Photosynthetic organisms universally exploit antennae systems to absorb light and funnel the excitation energy to the Reaction Centers (RC) where the charge separation occurs. This process converts light energy to chemical energy. The use of antennae allows a multitude of pigment molecules to direct light excitation energy to each RC. This architecture increases the number of photons and the range of photon energies that can be directed to a RC to perform charge separation. By increasing the probability that a given RC will produce a charge separation per unit time, antennae enable the rate of Reaction Centers turnover under ambient sunlight to be matched to the rate of downstream biochemical processes for more efficient biosynthetic function.

Figure 1.4. a) Excitation energy transfer path (blue arrow), bacterial light harvesting system, b) Electron transfer path after a charge separation in the bacterial reaction center (purple arrows).

Artificial light-harvesting antenna systems are capable of collecting light and transferring energy in an efficient and direct way. The excitation of a light-absorbing antenna array followed by the energy-transfer sensitization of a RC. When a RC is coupled to an antenna array, a large number of antenna chromophores surrounding the RC absorb incident photons. The resulting excited states then transfer electronic energy to the RC before undergoing radiative or nonradiative deactivation. Highly branched, tree-like dendrimers have been widely employed as antenna systems. The convergent and/or divergent synthesis of dendrimers allows the assembly of a large number of chromophores in close proximity. (Figure 1.4).

To mimic natural photosynthesis, various artificial photosynthesis systems have been developed. Generally, artificial light harvesting systems consist of donors and acceptors; the light harvesting systems are connected to reaction centers via bridges, which are used to generate a charge separation and ideally transfer the charge before recombination occurs.¹⁵ Chlorophylls are involved in both light collection and charge separation in the reaction centre¹⁶ of natural photosynthesis systems. Among the light-harvesting chromophores, porphyrins and phthalocyanines are closely related to chlorophyll derivatives. Metal coordination compounds, which exhibit metal to ligand charge transfer (MLCT) at relatively low energy, have been widely employed as photosensitizers.¹⁷ Early work in designing molecular model systems focused on light absorption and excited state electron transfer

involving the π - π^* transition of porphyrins.¹⁸ Hence porphyrins have been studied extensively in artificial photosynthesis.

Porphyrin-based¹⁹ arrays, bodipy-based²⁰ dendrimers and polymers have been reported to be efficient light harvesting systems with fast energy transfer rates. For example, the incorporation of porphyrin dimers within a dye-sensitized solar cell, a 70% of absorbed photon-to-current conversion efficiency has been shown.¹⁹ Dye-loaded zeolites have been used to direct the energy transfer along a pre-designed route.²¹ The energy captured by the collectors was transferred to the reaction centre to drive the electron transfer leading to formation of a charge-separated state. The main problem here is the competing process, i.e., charge recombination, which decreases the conversion efficiency. To overcome this problem, triads, tetrads, etc have been synthesized based on the discovery that electron transfer rates decrease with the increasing separation between the donors and acceptors.²² These designs do help to decrease the charge recombination rate to some extent, but this is not the ultimate solution and the coupling of the collector and reaction centre is another issue

Some examples of charge separation generated in artificial photosynthesis systems:

- Bhosale, *et al.*, have generated a proton gradient across a lipid bilayer using p-octiphenyl rods and naphthalene diimides arranged in the membrane as helical tetrameric π -stacks.²³
- Steinberg-Y frach, *et al.* report the use of a molecular triad (composed of a porphyrin, carotenoid and naphthaquinone), spanning the width of the membrane it is in, producing a photo-induced proton gradient by trans-membrane proton transfer.²⁴
- Kuciauskas *et al.* synthesized and characterized a (PZP)₃-PZCPC₆₀ hexad, which mimics the basic function of antenna systems and reaction centre complexes in photosynthesis.²⁵
- Palacios, *et al.* have reported the use of a triad containing a carotenoid, a dimesitylporphyrin and a bis(heptafluoropropyl)- porphyrin in trans-membrane electron transfer and charge separation.²⁶
- Imahori and Fukazumi generated artificial photosynthesis systems, composed of porphyrins and fullerenes, using self-assembly processes. However only low PCEs were achieved (~1%).²⁷

Artificial systems can be designed with enhanced light-harvesting capacity and efficiency compared with natural systems. For example, Würthner and co-workers prepared a bichromophoric assembly consisting of blue naphthalene bisimide (NBI) dyes at the periphery of aggregated zinc chlorines **ZnchlNBI-1**. As model compounds for bacteriochlorophyll-*c*,²⁸ Zinc chlorins are very efficient in harvesting blue and red light, but not the significant green region (Figure 1.5). The artificial bichromophoric assembly absorbs green light and demonstrates efficient energy transfer from the NBI dyes to the zinc chlorines,²⁹

Figure 1.5. Structure of **ZnchlNBI-1** As model compounds for bacteriochlorophyll-*c*

1.2.2.2 Advantage of Artificial photosynthesis

When using the total solar irradiation, natural photosynthesis has an overall efficiency of 3-6%.³⁰ It takes eight to >10 photons to give one molecule of carbon dioxide. Other limitations to higher efficiencies are the reflection off of photosynthetic surfaces, respiration energy requirements, the window of wavelengths that can be utilized, and photons not hitting the photoactive pigments. This is an opportunity to improve upon nature and make artificial photosynthetic systems of higher efficiencies than natural photosynthesis

1.3 Excitation Energy Transfer (EET) and Photo induced Electron Transfer (PET)

An understanding of basic principles of photoinduced electron and energy transfer is very important to the design of elegant artificial photosynthetic model systems that mimic the

analogous natural system and harvest solar energy with maximum efficiency. The basic components needed to design and build efficient artificial photosynthetic model systems include;

- (i) Antenna chromophore that absorbs light and forms an excited state species.
- (ii) The excited state species must transfer electrons to acceptor chromophore.
- (iii) The electron transfer must be directional, and
- (iv) The lifetimes of excited states must be long enough for the electron transfer and, thereby, provide long lived charge-separated cation and anion radical ion pairs.

A molecule in the excited state can relax to the ground state by fluorescence, internal conversion, intersystem crossing, non radiative decay, or by two main physical mechanisms: electron transfer or energy transfer to another molecule. Basically, energy and electron transfer are classified as quenching pathways. Quenching is defined as the deactivation of an excited sensitizer by an external component. The external component, quencher usually is a ground-state molecule. During the quenching process, the sensitized chromophore induces permanent or temporary chemical changes in surrounding ground-state molecules. Quenching process may take place between a sensitizer and quencher completely separated or attached to one another via a flexible or rigid spacer molecule. Quenching generates reactive intermediates that rapidly undergo transformation to stable products.

1.3.1 Excited–state deactivations and Jablonski diagram

A common way to present photophysical deactivation pathways of electronically excited states is using a schematic energy level diagram as Jablonski diagram (Figure 1.6). In the ground state, most molecules are singlets accordingly denoted S_0 where all electron spins are paired. The electronic excited states populated by photo–excitation are also singlets (*vide supra*) denoted S_1, S_2, \dots . The more closely spaced levels associated to each electronic state are the vibrational levels. Depending on the energy of the absorbed photon, the initially populated excited state is either the n -vibrational level of S_1, S_2, \dots . The molecule first dissipates its excess of energy *via* fast vibrational relaxation mechanisms (VR) and populates lower vibrational levels of the excited state according to a Boltzmann distribution.

The energy is lost as heat through collisions with the surrounding molecules or the solvent. In solution, VR is quite fast, *i.e.* from tens of femtoseconds to tens of picoseconds.

This means that, in general, all other deactivation processes occur from the equilibrated excited states. The excess of energy is then released *via* different competing deactivation pathways classified into non-radiative and radiative processes.

Figure 1.6. Jablonski diagram showing non-radiative and radiative deactivation pathways for an excited state.

Internal conversion (IC) and intersystem crossing (ISC) are both non-radiative decay processes and do not imply absorption or emission of photon. They occur between isoenergetic vibrational levels of different electronic states, hence no energy is lost. The resulting state is a vibrationally excited state that further relaxes *via* vibrational relaxation. Thus, IC and ISC are represented as horizontal arrow lines (\rightarrow) in the Jablonski diagram. Difference between IC and ISC lies in the spin state of the levels involved. Internal conversion moves the molecule between isoenergetic vibrational levels of electronic states of the same multiplicity: for example, $S_1 \rightarrow S_0$ in (Figure 1.6). In contrast to IC, intersystem crossing involves electronic states of different multiplicity. For example, from the S_1 state, the molecule can spin flip its electron and move to the triplet excited state T_1 . The probability of IC and ISC processes (i.e. the rates) is dependent on the Franck-Condon factor and the spin overlap (*vide supra*). Since the change of spin in transitions is formally forbidden, intersystem crossing (i.e. $S_1 \rightarrow T_1$) is much slower than internal conversion (i.e. $S_1 \rightarrow S_0$).

Competing with the non-radiative IC and ISC are radiative processes that lead to emission of photons. Radiative processes involve vertical transitions (\rightsquigarrow) between

electronic excited states and the ground state. The excess energy is released in the form of photons with energy matching the energy difference between the two electronic states. Once more, one distinguishes photon emission from transitions between states of same spin multiplicity and different spin multiplicity. Singlet emission such as e.g. $S_1 \rightarrow S_0$ is called fluorescence (Fl) and takes place on the nanosecond time scale. Photon emission occurring from a triplet state, such as $T_1 \rightarrow S_0$ is called phosphorescence (Ph). Similar to intersystem crossing (*vide supra*), triplet emission is a spin-forbidden transition, hence less probable and much slower (i.e. typically microseconds to milliseconds or even seconds for organic molecules). In (Figure 1.6), note that photon emission is voluntarily represented as potential deactivation pathway only from S_1 and T_1 . Indeed, due to usually fast internal conversion processes within each high excited state (S_n , T_n , $n > 1$) and fast vibrational relaxation, *the emitting level of a given multiplicity is the lowest excited level of that multiplicity* (Kasha's rule³¹). While most molecules obey this rule, exceptions exist, e.g. azulene,³² some porphyrins³³ and some phthalocyanines³⁴ for which emission from the S_2 state is observed.

In the special case of a donor-acceptor couple, the donor excited state may be quenched via energy and/or electron transfer to the acceptor. In that sense, the excess energy stored in the excited state may be used to perform reactions which thermodynamically will not be possible from the ground state. For example, in the natural photosynthesis, the energy stored in the excited states triggers a cascade of electron transfer steps that ultimately results in a charge-separated state with sufficient energy for water splitting and carbon dioxide reduction (*vide supra*).

1.3.2 Excitation Energy transfer (EET)

Energy transfer is very important process in nature and technology, as it allows to obtain an excited state not only due to a direct absorption of light, but also through transferring electronic energy from other excited species that has absorbed the light in the first place. It permits excitation of molecules that do not absorb the incident light. The common examples can be found in the photosynthesis, where the energy is absorbed by the light harvesting antennas and transferred to the photosynthetic reaction center.³⁵

The energy transfer between donor-acceptor referred to as excitation energy transfer (EET) can be described by the following equation,

$$D - A + hc/\lambda \rightarrow D^* - A \xrightarrow{k_{EET}} D - A^* \dots\dots\dots (1.5)$$

The excitation energy transfer rates, k_{EET} , can thus be predicted by the appropriate Fermi Golden Rule and can be described by the following equation,

$$k_{EET} = (2\pi/h) \left| \int \Psi_{D-A^*} \hat{H}' \Psi_{D^*-A} d\tau \right|^2 FWCD \dots\dots\dots (1.6)$$

Where Ψ_{D-A^*} and Ψ_{D^*-A} are the wave functions of the initial D^*-A and $D-A^*$ final states, respectively. \hat{H}' denotes the electronic coupling operator between the two excited states D^* and A^* . The FWCD-term consists of the sum of the vibrational overlap integrals at thermal equilibrium. Since electronic coupling may occur through space (i.e. coulombic) or through bond (i.e. electron exchange), \hat{H}' can be divided into two parts, coulombic \hat{H}'_c and electron exchange \hat{H}'_e .

Depending on the donor-acceptor system (e.g. donor-acceptor distance, relative orientation of the donor and acceptor or spin of the involved states), through-space or through-bond electronic coupling may dominate. This leads to two alternative mechanisms by which EET may occur: a coulombic mechanism commonly known as FRET (Förster Resonance Energy Transfer) and an electron exchange mechanism called Dexter energy transfer (Figure 1.7).

Figure 1.7. Schematic comparisons of (A) FRET and (B) Dexter energy transfer mechanisms. Adapted from reference.³⁶

1.3.2.1 Forster Resonance Energy Transfer (FRET)

In FRET, the coulombic interaction arises from the fact that a chromophore in the excited state generates an electric field. Likewise light, this electric field can perturb the charge distribution of neighboring chromophores. Thus, the interaction between the donor and acceptor in FRET is regarded as the interaction between two transition dipoles, i.e. one on the donor and one on the acceptor. Hence, it follows the same selection rules as the transition dipole moments associated to the transitions $D^* \rightarrow D$ and $A \rightarrow A^*$, e.g. resonance condition, no change in spin (*vide supra*). Since the same selection rules as for absorption and emission transitions apply, it also means that faster FRET rates will be obtained in donor–acceptor couples that have strong radiative transitions (i.e. large transition dipole moments). This is clearly seen in the expression of the FRET energy transfer rate k_{EET}^F predicted by Förster theory that includes the fluorescence quantum yield Φ_D , the lifetime τ_D of the donor and an overlap integral F between the emission spectrum of the donor $I_D(\bar{\nu})$ and the molar absorptivity spectrum of the acceptor $\epsilon_A(\bar{\nu})$,^{37,38}

$$k_{EET}^F = 8.8 \times 10^{-25} \frac{k^2 \Phi_D}{n^4 R_{DA}^6 \tau_D} J_F \dots\dots\dots (1.7)$$

Where,

$$J_F = \frac{\int \left(\frac{I_D(\bar{\nu}) \epsilon_A(\bar{\nu})}{r^4} \right) d(\bar{\nu})}{\int I_D(\bar{\nu}) d(\bar{\nu})} \dots\dots\dots (1.8)$$

Note that in F , normalization is done on the emission spectrum of the donor. This means that F is independent of the oscillator strength of the donor. Equation 1.8 also shows how directional energy transfer may be achieved in a multichromophoric system. Energy transfer will be directed towards the acceptor chromophore whose absorption spectrum overlaps the most with the donor emission spectrum.³⁹ Hence, faster EET will be obtained in systems where the chromophores are spatially arranged according to their transition energy gaps, i.e. in a downhill energy gradient.

In equation 1.7, another important parameter is k^2 which reflects the directional nature of the dipole–dipole interaction. Its value varies between zero for perpendicular transition dipole moments and four for collinear transition dipole moments. n is the solvent refractive index and finally R_{DA} is the donor–acceptor distance.

1.3.2.2 Dexter energy transfer

As mentioned above, Dexter energy transfer is a through-bond energy transfer mechanism, which can be described as a double-electron transfer process (Figure 1.7). In contrast to FRET, it requires overlap between the donor and acceptor orbitals.

The rate for Dexter energy transfer, k_{EET}^D , can be expressed according to the Fermi Golden rule by,

$$k_{EET}^D = (2\pi/\hbar) \left| \int \psi_{D-A^*} \hat{H}' \psi_{D^*-A} d\tau \right|^2 J_D \dots\dots\dots (1.9)$$

Where,

$$\left| \int \psi_{D-A^*} \hat{H}' \psi_{D^*-A} d\tau \right|^2 J_D = V_{DA}^{EET}(0) \exp\left(-\frac{\beta^{EET}}{2}(R_{DA} - r_0)\right) \dots\dots (1.10)$$

and J_D is the Dexter overlap integral between the emission spectrum of the donor and the molar absorption spectrum of the acceptor.

$$J_D = \frac{\int I_D(\bar{\nu}) \epsilon_A(\bar{\nu}) d\bar{\nu}}{\int I_D(\bar{\nu}) d\bar{\nu} \int \epsilon_A(\bar{\nu}) d\bar{\nu}} \dots\dots\dots (1.11)$$

In equation 1.10, V_{DA}^{EET} denotes the donor-acceptor electronic coupling for exchange energy transfer, $V_{DA}^{EET}(0)$ is the donor-acceptor electronic coupling taken at the contact distance r_0 and β_{EET} is the attenuation factor for exchange energy transfer. Likewise the electronic coupling for electron transfer, V_{DA}^{EET} decays exponentially with the donor-acceptor distance R_{DA} and so does the energy transfer rate k_{EET}^D . Hence, Dexter energy transfer dominates mostly at short distances, provided that the donor and acceptor molecular orbitals overlap. In contrast, FRET whose rate decays with the sixth power of R_{DA} (equation 1.7) can occur with an appreciable rate for much longer donor-acceptor separation distances.

Another important difference between Dexter energy transfer and FRET is highlighted by equation 1.11. In the expression of J_D , the normalization is not only made on the emission spectrum of the donor but also on the absorption spectrum of the acceptor. This implies that the Dexter energy transfer rate is in contrast to FRET, independent of the oscillator strengths

of the donor and acceptor. This means that triplet–triplet energy transfer via Dexter mechanism is not forbidden as it is in FRET.

1.3.3 Photo induced electron transfer (PET)

The electron transfer reactions described in this thesis are intramolecular electron transfer reactions, this reaction consists of the transfer of an electron between the electron donating (D) and accepting (A) parts of the molecular system. In this work, Electron transfer reactions are triggered using light excitation by selectively exciting either the donor or the acceptor. These reactions are called photoinduced electron transfer (PET) reactions and can be described by the following reaction,

Here, the donor is initially excited and the ET reaction is of an electron transfer from the donor excited state D^* to the ground state acceptor A. The product of the ET reaction is the charge–separated state, $D^{+\bullet} - A^{-\bullet}$

1.3.3.1 Factors affecting photo induced electron transfer:

The various factors affecting PET includes:

- Orbital symmetry
- D-A distance
- Bridge in between the D and A
- Feasible energies (Gibbs free energy)

The effect of these factors is clearly substantiated using different experimental studies and complementary theoretical descriptions.⁴⁰ Amongst which, a significant theoretical explanation for predicting the rate of electron transfer is provided by the Nobel prize winner of 1992, Prof. R.A.Marcus.⁴¹

1.3.3.2 Marcus theory

Electron transfer reactions can be described by motion of atoms along potential energy surfaces. Here, the potential energy surfaces are the one of the photoexcited reactant $D^* - A$ and the ET product $D^{+\bullet} - A^{-\bullet}$ (reaction 1.12) as function of the reaction coordinate (Figure 1.8). The reaction coordinates include the vibrational (nuclear) coordinates of the

reacting molecules and the position and orientation of the solvent molecules. Since electron transfer is a dark reaction, it will only occur at the configuration of the reacting system (reaction coordinate/potential energy) that satisfies both energy conservation and Franck–Condon conditions. These conditions are fulfilled at the crossing point between the two surfaces, these called transition state TS, both the reactant and the product have classically the same energy. Moreover, the transfer occurs at fixed positions of the atoms, and hence the Franck–Condon principle is also satisfied. At the transition state, the electronic coupling between the donor and the acceptor, V_{DA} causes a splitting of the two surfaces (Figure 1.8). The extent of this splitting, i.e. the electronic coupling will in part determine the probability of D^*-A to cross over the “mountain pass” and form $D^{*+}-A^-$. Other factors intervene in an electron transfer “journey”. At the beginning of the ET journey, the reacting D^*-A is in a valley (the lower left region of Figure 1.8). Hence to reach TS, D^*-A needs to first distort along the reaction coordinate from its equilibrium position to the transition state, i.e. changes in bond lengths. This requires energy called activation energy, ΔG^\ddagger . Formation of $D^{*+}-A^-$ is also characterized by a change in dipole moment with respect D^*-A . As pointed out first by Libby,⁴² this charge-separated state is formed initially in a “unsuitable” solvent environment, i.e. the surrounding solvent molecules do not have time to rearrange on the short time scale of ET to accommodate the changes in polarization. Reorganization of the solvent molecules to bring $D^{*+}-A^-$ to its equilibrium state again requires energy that is involved in the reorganizational energy denoted λ . In (Figure 1.8), λ corresponds to the energy to bring the reactant to the nuclear and solvent configuration of the final (i.e. equilibrated) product. Finally, the rate of electron transfer will depend on the driving force or standard free energy of the reaction, ΔG^0 .

The Marcus equation for determining the rate of electron transfer, k_{ET} is written as,

$$K_{ET} = \sqrt{\frac{\pi}{h^2 \lambda k_B T}} V_{DA}^2 \exp\left(-\frac{(\Delta G^0 + \lambda)^2}{4 \lambda k_B T}\right) \dots \dots \dots (1.13)$$

With the activation energy ΔG^\ddagger is equal to $(\Delta G^0 + \lambda)^2 / 4\lambda$.

The equation (1.13) represents the relationship between the rate of electron transfer

constant (k_{ET}) and the Gibbs free energy change (ΔG^0), h is the Planck's constant, λ is the reorganization energy, k_B is the Boltzmann constant, T is the absolute temperature and V is the electronic coupling constant, which depends on the distance of separation and nature of the intervening spacer between the donor (D) and the acceptor (A).

Figure 1.8. Schematic (left) of the potential energy surfaces of the initial state and the charge-separated state in Marcus parabola: the driving force ΔG^0 , the activation energy ΔG^\ddagger , the reorganizational energy λ and the electronic coupling V_{DA} : (Right) the potential energy surfaces of the excited states D^*-A and $D^{*+}-A^-$ and the charge-separated states $D^{*+}-A^-$ for different ET regimes with (I) $\Delta G^0 > -\lambda$, (II) $\Delta G^0 = -\lambda$ and (III) $\Delta G^0 < -\lambda$.

Another prediction of Marcus theory is the inverted region which is derived from the quadratic dependence of the activation energy on sum of the driving force and reorganization energy.⁴³ Looking at the variation of ΔG^\ddagger with ΔG^0 , when ΔG^0 is decreased from zero to a negative value, the activation energy decreases, until it fully vanishes for $\Delta G^0 = -\lambda$. However, when the driving force becomes even more negative, i.e. $\Delta G^0 < -\lambda$, the activation energy starts to increase again. The decrease of ΔG^\ddagger with increasingly negative ΔG^0 is expected trend in chemical reactions and is often referred to as the normal region in ET.

1.3.3.3 The reorganization energy

Both the reactant and solvent nuclear modes contribute to the reorganization energy, λ , which can then be expressed as the sum of two independent parts, i.e. λ_{in} and λ_{out} .

$$\lambda = \lambda_{\text{in}} + \lambda_{\text{out}} = \lambda_{\text{in}} + \frac{e^2}{4\pi\epsilon_0} \left(\frac{1}{2R_D} + \frac{1}{2R_A} - \frac{1}{2R_{DA}} \right) \left(\frac{1}{n^2} - \frac{1}{\epsilon_S} \right) \dots \quad (1.14)$$

λ_{in} represents the reorganization of the inner (reactant) nuclear modes, i.e. changes in bond lengths and bond angles that D^*-A undergoes when moving from the reactant to the product nuclear configuration. λ_{out} involves the reorganization of the outer (solvent) nuclear modes which accompany ET and accommodate changes in polarization around the donor/acceptor couple. In most cases, in polar solvents, λ_{out} is the dominant term in the expression of λ for electron transfer reactions. By approximating the donor and acceptor to spheres, λ_{out} can be estimated from the refractive index and the dielectric constant of the solvent ϵ_S .⁴⁴ This expression for λ_{out} implies that λ_{out} will be particularly large in polar solvents and when RDA is large.

Electron transfer depends on the redox properties of the donor acceptor and couple together with the excitation energy. In polar solvents, the Gibbs free energy change for charge separation (ΔG_{cs}), is given by following equation.

$$\Delta G_{\text{cs}} = e(E_0(D^+/D) - E_0(A/A^-) - \Delta E_{0-0}X(P)) \dots \quad (1.15)$$

Where, “P” is the “polar driving force”. In other words, the incident excitation energy ($\Delta E_{0,0}$) should be more than the energy required to oxidize the donor and to reduce the acceptor. The fascinating aspects of the mode and factors affecting the ET have been a persistent spotlight of investigation by the competent chemists. And research in this area has always received much interest till date.

1.4. Donor-Acceptor systems

Over the last two decades, considerable efforts have been devoted to the synthesis of electron donor-acceptor (D-A) mimics the more complicated natural photosynthetic system.⁴⁵⁻⁴⁸ Most of these D-A systems have been primarily investigated with the aim of creating charge separated states that live long enough to drive secondary redox reactions.⁴⁹⁻⁵² From a fundamental point of view, simple donor-acceptor model systems are also ideal systems to get more insights into excitation energy (EET) and electron (ET) transfer processes, i.e. to sort out the molecular parameters (e.g. geometry, electronic structure) that

govern their kinetics and efficiencies. In the literature, a vast variety of D–A supramolecular systems has been reported employing e.g. porphyrins,^{1,53} phthalocyanines,^{3,54} corroles,^{2,55} phenothiazines,⁵⁶⁻⁵⁹ coordination compounds,⁶⁰⁻⁶² as electron donor and e.g. fullerenes,⁶³⁻⁶⁵ graphene,⁶⁶ quinones,^{5,67} perylene imides⁶⁸⁻⁶⁹ as electron acceptor.

Donor–acceptor systems provide guideline knowledge how charge or energy moves, in that not only applies to the design of efficient molecular systems for artificial photosynthesis, but also the design of efficient molecular scale electronics. Regardless of the targeted applications like DSSC, either for artificial photosynthesis or molecular electronics,⁷⁰ most important is to understand how the donor and acceptor components in supramolecular systems interact. It means identifying the molecular properties that control the signal transmission between the donor and the acceptor, i.e. how fast electrons or excitation energy move between the donor and acceptor. Ultimately such studies, either theoretical or experimental, provide essential knowledge for applied research on how to design controllable molecular systems in which one can tune the flow of electrons or energy.

1.4.1 General strategies for artificial donor-acceptor systems

The arrangement of the donor–acceptor hybrids in the photosynthetic reaction centre (PRC) is accomplished *via* non-covalent incorporation into a well-defined protein matrix. To mimic primary events of natural photosynthesis, the study necessitates simple donor-acceptor model systems. The ultimate goal is to design and synthesis different conjugates which can efficiently convert solar energy into useful chemical energy. A main feature in photosynthetic reaction centre modelling is incorporation of a photo excitable chromophore with a donor or an acceptor using a covalent or non covalent linkage.

Several covalently and non-covalently linked light harvesting model systems, involving different donors such as porphyrins,^{1,53} corroles,^{2,55} phthalocyanines,^{3,54} naphthalocyanines,⁷¹ and metallocenes,⁷² (ferrocene, cobaltocene) and acceptors such as quinines,^{5,67} fullerenes,⁶³⁻⁶⁵ perylenecarboxiimides,⁶⁸⁻⁶⁹ and bodipys,^{20,73} have been synthesized and investigated to discover basic aspects of light induced electron/energy transfer and to obtain long lived charge separated states.⁷⁴ The covalently-linked model systems are substantially different from natural systems, especially with regard to the composition of the medium intervening between donor and acceptor. Therefore, discovery of

non-covalently linked donor-acceptor models to mimic natural systems appears to be more promising in the field of artificial photosynthesis.

Careful design of such molecules must take into account the following factors arising from the energy/electron transfer theory described in the previous section.

1. Proper redox potentials of the donor and acceptor to enable electron transfer;
2. Suitable size and symmetry of the donor and acceptor to optimize and thus k_{ET} and k_{BET} .
3. Light harvesting ability of at least one of the chromophores, *i.e.* high molar absorption coefficient at a wavelength where excitation can be carried out;
4. Suitable excited state energy of the light harvesting chromophore. *i.e.* negative free energy of ET from the excited state.
5. Mutual orientation and distance of the chromophores, *i.e.* control of λ and thus k_{ET} and k_{BET} .

These strategies have been incorporated to increase the rates of the forward ET and to slow down the BET (Backward electron transfer) such as modification of energies of donor-acceptor dyads, tuning electronic coupling between donor and acceptor moieties, and incorporation of secondary donor or acceptor into multicomponent array. These factors systematically altered to overcome the difficulties encountered in donor-acceptor systems. In PET process of artificial photosynthetic model systems, charged species, the radical cation of donor ($D^{\bullet+}$) and the radical anion of the acceptor ($A^{\bullet-}$) are utilized as electrons and holes to drive electrical current or promote chemical reactions before back electron transfer leading to the initial state of reactants.

1.5 Porphyrins

Porphyrin is an 18π aromatic macrocyclic compound that consists of four pyrrole units and four bridging carbon atoms in a planar conformation. One can find the structure of porphyrin in nature, such as in various types of chlorophylls and haeme. Chlorophylls play pivotal roles in photosynthesis as both light harvesting antennae and charge separation reaction systems. Haemes are one of the key components for biocatalysts and oxygen carriers in the blood. Without porphyrins, no life can exist on earth.

Figure 1.9. Porphyrin macrocycle and its IUPAC numbering. Identification of the pyrrole rings in corroles using the A–D system.⁷⁵

Particularly in chemistry, porphyrins and metalated porphyrins have attracted organic and inorganic chemists simply because of their beautiful molecular shapes. The highly symmetrical D_{4h} planar structure of metalloporphyrin has inspired a number of chemists and brought out their molecular creativity. Moreover, porphyrin is one of the archetypal functional molecules, playing an important role in diverse areas of scientific research owing to its unique electronic and optical properties. Porphyrin research has a long history, covering a wide variety of disciplines of natural sciences, including photosynthesis, P450-related biocatalysis,⁷⁶ organic photovoltaic cells,⁷⁷⁻⁷⁸ photodynamic therapeutic agents,⁷⁹ bioimaging probes,⁸⁰ chemosensors,⁸¹ conductive organic materials,⁸²⁻⁸³ light emitting materials,⁸⁴ near-infrared dyes,⁸⁵ nonlinear optical materials,⁸⁶ information storage,⁸⁷ molecular wires,⁸⁸⁻⁸⁹ metal ligands and supramolecules.⁹⁰⁻⁹¹

1.5.1 Covalently bonded porphyrin based donor-acceptor systems

A large number of covalently linked donor-acceptor systems have been elegantly designed, synthesized and studied to understand photoinduced energy and electron transfer reactions to mimic antenna functionality in natural photosynthesis.⁸²⁻⁸⁵ The design of synthetic light-harvesting model systems by incorporating covalently linked porphyrins (metallo and free base) has been developed to mimic natural photosynthetic pigments. Scientists have reported a variety of such array systems with donors including ferrocene,^{72,96} tetrathiafulvalene,⁹⁷⁻⁹⁸ poly aromatic hydrocarbons⁹⁹⁻¹⁰⁰ etc., and acceptors such as quinines,

¹⁰¹ fullerenes, ¹⁰² and perylenecarboxiimides. ¹⁰³ Such molecular designs have greatly assisted in exploring the primary aspects of light induced electron/energy transfer and to obtain long lived charge separated states. ¹⁰⁴⁻¹⁰⁵

Among the vast family of covalent donor-acceptor systems reported, those based on porphyrins are note worthy. This is due to their exact similarities with the chlorophyll core of the natural Photosynthesis Reaction Centre (PRC) and desirable properties like wide range of absorption in the visible and near-IR region with strong absorption bands around 400 nm ($\epsilon > 200,000$), the Soret band or B-band arising from S_0 to S_2 transition, followed by several weaker absorptions (Q bands) arising from S_0 to S_1 transition at higher wavelengths (from 450 to 750 nm), flexibility in core structure, extensive π -conjugated macrocycle which improves its electron donating ability and thermal, electrochemical and photostability which is also an essentially desirable requirement for the synthesis of sensitizers used in photovoltaic applications. ¹⁰⁶⁻¹⁰⁸ Moreover, the fluorescence quantum yield and the lifetime of 1S and 1T states are long enough to facilitate their interaction with the neighboring donor/acceptor molecules, which render them as attractive molecules in the artificial photosynthesis research.

1.5.1.1 Dimeric porphyrins

Lindsey and co-workers ¹⁰⁹ constructed dimeric porphyrin array system, **ZnFbP**, the dimers consist of Zn porphyrin and a free base porphyrin which is *meso-meso* linked by the diarylethyne spacer (Figure: 1.10.) The methyl groups attached on the spacer aryl group adjacent to the porphyrin chromophore revealed torsional constrain which provides a semi rigid architecture that limits direct chromophore interactions. This structural behavior is promoting modest bending and allowing rotation of the porphyrin planes about the ethylene in fluid solution which attributes to activation of efficient energy transfer. The lifetime of ZnFbP dimer gave a slight increase time scale (~2.3 - 2.4 ns) compared with ZnTPP (2.04 ns). The fluorescence yield, fluorescence excitation, fluorescence life time and transient absorption studies reveal that the yield of energy transfer is well over 90%. studies revealed excitation energy transfer with time constants in the order of 24-88 ps. Fast energy transfer rates (~720 ps) of all the dimers are consistent with a through bond mechanism, rather than through space (Förster) energy transfer. Moreover, torsional constraints due to methyl

substituents in the diarylethyne linker would not be expected to strongly influence a through space energy transfer process.

Figure 1.10. Molecular structures of ZnFp, 1FB-PZn, 2FB-PZn and 3FB-PZn.

Flamigni *et al*, reported¹¹⁰ energy transfer in a series of hetero-dyads of zinc porphyrin and free-base porphyrin connected at the β -position by π -conjugated bridges, **1FB-PZn**, **2FB-PZn** and **3FB-PZn** (Fig. 1.10). Determination of energy transfer in a series of free-base porphyrin/zinc porphyrin dyads connected by π -delocalized bridges has been accurately performed with respect to models, the corresponding free-base porphyrin and zinc porphyrin homo-dyads, which perfectly represent the units in the same molecular environment of the dyads. The mechanism cannot be accounted for entirely by a dipole–dipole (Förster) scheme, and the inclusion of a contribution by electron exchange (Dexter) in the π -phenylenevinylene containing dyads has led to derive a very weak distance-dependence of the rate of the exchange energy transfer. This is assigned to the nature of the bridge and to the highly coplanar arrangements of the bridge with respect to the donor, which enhances the coupling. The overall result is a very high (>98%) energy transfer efficiency.

1.5.1.2 Porphyrin anthraquinones

B. G. Maiya and co-workers¹¹¹ have been synthesized a porphyrin–anthraquinone conjugate D-A dyads as free-base $\text{H}_2(\text{L}_2)$ and Zinc (ZnL_2) derivatives with an azomethine bridge, (Figure 1.11) and characterized by various spectroscopic techniques. In these dyads porphyrin acts as donor, anthraquinone acts as acceptor. Both free-base and zinc porphyrin fluorescence was quenched (88–97%), when compared to their corresponding monomeric analogues (H_2L_2 and ZnL_2). The electron-transfer rate constants are calculated, indicating k_{ET} values in the range of 1.1×10^9 to $9.9 \times 10^{10} \text{ s}^{-1}$ that are solvent-dependent.

Figure 1.11. Molecular structures of PAQ, PEQ, $\text{H}_2(\text{L})_2$, $\text{Zn}(\text{L})_2$ dyads and $\text{AQ}(\text{H}_2)_2$, $\text{AQ}(\text{Zn})_2$ triads.

Recently, our group have constructed¹¹² bis-porphyrin-anthraquinone triad system $\text{AQ}(\text{H}_2)_2$ and $\text{AQ}(\text{Zn})_2$ (Figure 1.11) using azomethine bridge in which there is a negligible electronic communication in the ground state between the donor porphyrin and acceptor anthraquinone of these triads. In excited state both the triads exhibit significant fluorescence emission quenching (51–92%) of the porphyrin emission compared to their monomeric units. The emission quenching is attributed to the excited state intramolecular photoinduced electron transfer from porphyrins to anthraquinone. The electron transfer rates (k_{ET}) of these triads are found in the range 1.0×10^8 to $7.7 \times 10^9 \text{ s}^{-1}$ and are found to be solvent dependent.

Connolly and co-workers¹¹³ have attached an anthraquinone acceptor directly at the *meso* position of a tritolyl porphyrin (**H₂PAQ**, **PEAQ** and **ZnPEAQ**) (Figure 1.11). They have studied a comparative investigation of the solvent dependent photophysical properties H₂PAQ with that of the corresponding PEAQ moieties which possess flexible electron-rich ester linkage. No appreciable change in the ground state properties between the two porphyrin-quinone dyads was observed. But a noticeable change was observed in the emission quenching and lifetime of the rigid H₂PAQ system

1.5.1.3 Porphyrin-BODIPY'S

Figure 1.12. Molecular structures of BODIPY-Porphyrin donor-acceptor arrays.

Dinolfo and co-workers¹¹⁴ synthesized three donor-acceptor energy transfer arrays that contain one (**Dyad**), three (**Tetrad**), and four (**Pentad**) in which donor BODIPY connected to a Zn-tetra phenylporphyrin acceptor with the 1,2,3-triazole linkage (Figure 1.12). Photophysical characterization and DFT electronic structure modeling of the three arrays are consistent with efficient Förster resonance energy transfer from the BODIPY donors to the Zn-tetraphenylporphyrin acceptor.

BODIPY emission is significantly quenched in all three arrays, consistent with energy transfer to the porphyrin core, with efficiencies of 95.8, 97.5, and 97.2% for the Dyad,

Tetrad, and Pentad, respectively. In all three systems applying Förster theory to the spectroscopic data of the chromophores gives energy transfer efficiency estimates that are in close agreement with experimental values. Comparison of the theoretical and measured energy transfer efficiencies suggests the through-space mechanism plays a dominant role in the three arrays.

1.5.1.4 Porphyrin- Fullerene with secondary donors

The combination of more than two entities in the donor-acceptor architectures show multi-step electron transfer which promotes to yield a long-lived charge separated state with a high quantum yield. One of the representative examples is carotenoid polyenendiarylporphyrin-fullerene triad,¹¹⁵ which is shown in (Figure: 1.13). In this system, porphyrin (P) act as primary electron donor, fullerene (C₆₀) as an acceptor while carotene (C) act as a secondary electron donor. In 2-methyltetrahydrofuran solution, the triad reveals photoinduced electron transfer to yield C-P^{•+}-C₆₀^{•-}. This charge separated state evolves by electron donation from the carotenoid to give the final charge separated state C^{•+}-P-C₆₀^{•-} with an overall quantum yield of 0.14 and creating lifetime of 170 ns. Even in a glass at 77 K, the lifetime of the charge separated state, C^{•+}-P-C₆₀^{•-} is 1.5 μs with the quantum yield of ~0.10. This charge separated state further decays mainly by charge recombination to give the carotenoid triplet ³*C-P-C₆₀ rather than ground state.

Instead of carotenoid in triad system, Imahori and coworkers¹¹⁶ have reported ferrocene as a secondary electron donor in triads, **Fc-H₂P-C₆₀** and **Fc-ZnP-C₆₀** (Figure 1.13). In benzonitrile at room temperature, photoinduced charge separation *via* electron transfer pathway occurs from all of the excited states, i.e., porphyrin singlet excited state ¹ZnP* and porphyrin triplet excited state ³ZnP* to the C₆₀ moiety, and from the porphyrin moiety to the C₆₀ singlet excited state ¹C₆₀* and the C₆₀ triplet excited state ³C₆₀*, to initially produce Fc-ZnP^{•+}-C₆₀^{•-} with high quantum yield. The resulting transient state of Fc-ZnP^{•+}-C₆₀^{•-} undergoes to form a long lived charge separated state of Fc^{•+}-ZnP-C₆₀^{•-} (16 μs in DMF) *via* secondary electron transfer from ferrocene moiety to ZnP^{•+} with quantum yields close to unity. This can be rationalized by the small reorganization energy of C₆₀ in multistep electron transfer processes, where forward electron transfer is accelerated and back electron transfer is decelerated. The charge shift rate constant in benzonitrile was determined as 2.8 x 10⁹ s⁻¹.

The $\text{Fc}^{\bullet+}\text{-ZnP-C}_{60}^{\bullet-}$ decays mainly by charge recombination to ground state, rather than to the secondary donor triplet state excited state. The electron transfer rate constants for the charge recombination in $\text{Fc}^{\bullet+}\text{-ZnP-C}_{60}^{\bullet-}$ were determined in solvents of increasing polarity by analyzing the decay kinetics of the $\text{C}_{60}^{\bullet-}$ fingerprint at 1000 nm in transient absorption spectra. These charge recombination rates decrease with increasing solvent polarity.

Figure 1.13. Molecular structures of covalently linked ferrocene-porphyrin-fullerene C_{60} triad, Carotenoid polyene-diarylporphyrin-fullerene(C_{60}) and Porphyrin-BODIPY- C_{60} triads.

Recently, Harvey and coworkers¹¹⁷ reported the synthesis of two new covalently bonded triad systems, Zn(II)porphyrin based (**ZnP**)-**BODIPY**- C_{60} and freebase of porphyrin based (**H₂P**)**BODIPY**- C_{60} (Figure 1.13). Where the porphyrin is covalently attached to the *meso* carbon of dipyrromethane core while the C_{60} is attached to the boron center. Excitation of the BODIPY triggers an energy transfer $^1[\text{BODIPY}]^*$ to $[\text{H}_2\text{P}]^1$ or $[\text{ZnP}]^1$, respectively. This has been confirmed for both the dyads from steady state and time resolved

measurements. Further evidence for the entitled energy transfer process came from femtosecond transient absorption measurements, the rate for energy or electron transfer and charge separation, in the different investigated solvents. Moreover estimated lifetime associated with the kinetic decays, i.e. charge recombination, found to be 276 ps in benzonitrile, 536 ps in 2-methyl THF and 1.247 ns in toluene. In this manner one can estimate the rate for electron transfer k_{et} as $6.4 \times 10^{11} \text{ s}^{-1}$ toluene $9.6 \times 10^{11} \text{ s}^{-1}$ 2-methyl THF and $21.7 \times 10^{11} \text{ s}^{-1}$ benzonitrile.

1.5.2 Axially linked Porphyrin based Donor-Acceptor systems

The efficiencies of light harvesting and charge separation by covalently synthesized donor-acceptor array systems are much less than that of the natural systems. Therefore, it is meaningful to exploit non covalent donor-acceptor molecular architectures for mimicking reaction center functionality.

In order to increase energy and electron transfer efficiency, scientists have been inserted different antenna chromophores such as boron dipyrromethane (BDP) and fullerene etc. non-covalently linked to the porphyrin through axial position. D'Souza and coworkers¹¹⁸ reported a supramolecular triad which is assembled by axially coordinating imidazole-appended fulleropyrrolidine to the zinc center of a covalently linked zinc porphyrin-boron dipyrin dyad (Figure 1.14).

Figure 1.14. Molecular structures of Borondipyrin-porphyrin-fullerene(C₆₀) triad.

In this non-covalent system boron dipyrromethane (BDP) acts as an energy absorbing and transferring antenna, and zinc porphyrin (ZnP) acts as an energy acceptor from the antenna and promotes electron transfer to the fullerene moiety by using the excitation energy, with the fullerene (C_{60} -Im) being the electron acceptor. Selective excitation of the BDP moiety resulted in efficient intramolecular energy transfer ($k_{ENT} = 9.2 \times 10^9 \text{ s}^{-1}$) creating singlet excited ZnP with quantum yield of ~ 0.83 . Electron transfer from the excited zinc porphyrin to fullerene subsequently follows, resulting in the formation of the charge-separated state with a lifetime of 5 ns ($\Phi_{CS} \text{ singlet} = 0.9$). The important feature of this model system is its relative simplicity because of the utilized supramolecular approach to mimic rather complex combined antenna-reaction center events of photosynthesis.

Figure 1.15. Molecular structures of Terathiofulvalene-porphyrin-fullerene(C_{60}) triad.

D'Souza *et.al.*¹¹⁹ explained the distance dependence of sequential electron transfer in vertical, linear supramolecular triads, **TTF-Ph_n-py** \rightarrow **AlPor-Ph_m-C₆₀**, ($n = 0, 1$ and $m = 1, 2, 3$), constructed using tetrathiafulvalene (TTF), aluminum(III) porphyrin (AlPor) and fullerene (C_{60}) entities (Figure1.15). The C_{60} and TTF units are bound to the Al center on opposite faces of the porphyrin, the C_{60} through a covalent axial bond using a benzoate

spacer, and the TTF through a coordination bond *via* an appended pyridine. Time-resolved optical and EPR spectroscopic methods and computational studies are used to demonstrate that excitation of the porphyrin leads to step-wise, sequential electron transfer (ET) between TTF and C₆₀, and to study the electron transfer rates and exchange coupling between the components of the triads as a function of the bridge lengths.

Femtosecond transient absorption studies show that the rates of charge separation, k_{CS} are in the range of 10^9 – 10^{11} s⁻¹, depending on the length of the bridges. The lifetimes of the charge separated state TTF^{•+}–C₆₀^{•-} obtained from transient absorbance experiments and the singlet lifetimes of the radical pairs obtained by time-resolved EPR are in good agreement with each other and range from 60–130 ns in the triads. The singlet charge recombination lifetime shows a much weaker dependence on the distance between the donor and acceptor, suggesting that a simple super exchange model is not sufficient to describe the back reaction.

Figure 1.16. Molecular structures of the axial supramolecular triads, BDP-COO-AITPP-C60-PPV-pyr, BDP-COO-AITPP·C60-pyr, BDP-O-AITPP·C60- PPV-pyr, and BDP-O-AITPP·C60-pyr triads.

Recently D'Souza and co-workers¹²⁰ reported sequential photoinduced energy transfer followed by electron transfer leading to the formation of charge separated states in a newly assembled series of supramolecular triads comprised of boron dipyrromethenes

(BODIPY or BDP), aluminum porphyrin (Al-TPP) and C₆₀ (Figure 1.16). In this system the energy donor (BDP) and electron acceptor (C₆₀) were axially positioned to the plane of Al-TPP *via* the central metal. The structural integrity of the newly synthesized compounds and self-assembled systems were fully established using spectral, electrochemical and computational methods. Selective excitation of the BDP moiety, in the dyads and triads resulted in successful formation of BDP*. An electron transfer from BDP* to C₆₀ to yield BDP⁺-AlTPP-C₆₀⁻ could be ruled out due to distance considerations and competing singlet-singlet energy transfer process involving AlTPP. The measured rates of electron transfer were found to be modest and increased distance between the AlTPP and C₆₀ led to decreased rates. Axial positioning of BDP energy donor of appropriate distance and orientation is equally feasible to observe efficient excitation energy transfer. They have calculated the rate of energy transfer for four triads, k_{ENT} values were found to be 9.3×10¹¹ s⁻¹ and 2.1×10⁹ s⁻¹ for BDP-O-AlTPP, and 4.3×10¹¹ s⁻¹ and 0.67×10⁹ s⁻¹ for BDP-COO-AlTPP. Furthermore, the Al-TPP* formed either by energy transfer or by direct excitation, promoted electron transfer to the coordinated C₆₀ unit resulting into the formation of BDP-AlTPP⁺-C₆₀⁻ charge separated states of appreciable lifetimes, the measured rates of electron transfer were found to be modest and increased distance between the AlTPP and C₆₀ led to decreased rates. Finally, the sequential energy transfer followed by electron transfer to mimic photosynthetic “antenna-reaction center” events have been successfully accomplished in the four supramolecular triads.

In general porphyrin act as a donor, but some reports on non-covalent porphyrin systems act as either energy or electron acceptor. Giribabu *et al*,¹²¹ have been synthesized a series of P(V), Ge(IV), and Sn(IV) porphyrin-based, “axial-bonding” type hybrid trimers (Figure 1.17). In these triad systems metal porphyrins are basal scaffolding unit, the free-base, VO(IV), Co(II), Ni(II), Co(II), or Zn(II) porphyrins occupy the two axial sites *via* an aryloxy bridge. Absorption and redox potential data reveals that there exists no interaction between the π-planes of the basal-axial porphyrins in these arrays so the ground state properties are more or less similar with their constituent monomers. Whereas the excited state properties, emission was quenched in all the trimers, which is due to an excited energy transfer (EET) from the central main group element containing porphyrin (M) to the axial free-base/zinc(II) porphyrin (H₂/Zn) and also the photoinduced electron transfer (PET) from

H_2/Zn (ground state) to the singlet state of the central porphyrin (M) and the energy transfer efficiency (% EET) follows the order $(H_2)_2Ge$ ($83\% \pm 10\%$) > $(H_2)_2Sn$ ($68\% \pm 10\%$) > $(H_2)_2P$ (5%). PET also seems to be more probable, when excited at 405 nm from singlet $^1H_2/^1Zn$ to central metal as revealed by the thermodynamic considerations.

Figure 1.17. Molecular structures of “axial-bonding”-type porphyrin hybrid trimers.

B. G. Maiya and co-workers,¹²² have made a comparative study on the orientation dependent excitation energy transfer (EET) by attaching a donor anthracene either at the peripheral or axial position of a *p*-tolyl substituted Sn(IV)porphyrinato dihydroxy compounds (Figure (1.18)). The steady state fluorescence emission and excitation spectra revealed that the energy utilized for excitation is efficiently transferred from the peripheral anthracene moiety to the porphyrin macrocycle but not from the axially substituted anthracene.⁴⁷

Figure 1.18. Molecular structures of Dyad(1), Triad(2), Tertad(3).

There is no EET from anthracene to porphyrin in triad (2) (donor subunits are exclusively at the axial positions), almost 99% in dyad (1) (donor subunit is exclusively at the peripheral position), where as in tetrad (3) only 30% observed this is due to that the peripheral anthracene subunit of tetrad (3) absorbs only one third of the incident light at the excitation wavelength. In this D-A system energy transfer to the porphyrin is strongly favored (~100%) from the peripheral anthracene and is quite inefficient (~0%) from the axial anthracene.

Figure 1.19. Molecular structures of Triad-1, Triad-2, Triad-3.

Hirakawa and co-workers¹²³ have reported porphyrin, pyrene triads (Figure 1.19) and they have studied the competition between EET and PET in a series of axially substituted pyrene-phosphorus (V) porphyrin triad. The quenching experiments were performed by

varying the bridge length between the donor pyrene and the acceptor porphyrin. Fluorescence quantum yields of the porphyrin and the pyrene moieties became remarkably smaller in the triads than in the corresponding reference compounds, this is due to the triads having π - π interaction between the pyrene and the porphyrin moieties. In excited states of the pyrene or the porphyrin moieties, electron transfer occurred from the pyrene moieties to the porphyrin rings in the triads. In the photoexcited states of pyrene in Triad-2 and Triad-3, energy transfer observed in the less polar solvent. These phenomena indicate that the switching between energy transfer and electron transfer is controlled by solvent polarity. The less polar matrix is considered to be useful for the coexistence of energy transfer and electron transfer. The efficiency of the energy transfer of the triads in less polar solvent increased with increasing pyrene-porphyrin distance. These triads provide a method to evaluate the photophysical switching of artificial molecular system.

1.6. Corrole

Tetrapyrroles, in particular porphyrins, are without any doubt the class of compounds used more widely for the construction of artificial arrays for light energy conversion.¹²⁴⁻¹²⁶ This is in part due to biomimetic reasons, since most of the naturally occurring pigments in the photosynthetic structures are of a similar type, but it is also due to the easy preparation and the wide range of electro-optical properties available after simple chemical modifications. More recently, there has been an increasing interest towards less conventional tetrapyrroles that display similar, but still distinguished properties. One of these families, corroles,¹²⁷⁻¹²⁸ are cyclic aromatic tetrapyrroles characterized by a direct pyrrole-pyrrole linkage and are able to coordinate trivalent metals. The high electron density caused by the smaller size of the macrocycle can lead to instability unless substitution with strongly electron-withdrawing groups is applied.

Corroles have been known since 1965 when Johnson and Kay published the first synthesis of a corrole,¹²⁹⁻¹³¹ their method did however require multiple steps of synthesis to acquire the necessary starting materials and as a result the field attracted little interest for over 30 years. Short and high-yielding procedures have only been available since 1999 when the two groups of Paolesse¹³² and Zeev Gross¹³³ were reported two different procedures leading to 5,10,15-triarylcorroles. Since then, the field of corrole synthesis has been

improved, most notably by the Gryko *et al.*, but also by the easy and high yielding procedure for the preparation of dipyrromethanes reported by the group of Dehaen.¹³⁴

Figure 1.20. Corrole macrocycle and its IUPAC numbering. Identification of the pyrrole rings in corroles using the A–D system.⁷⁵

Attracted by these new chromophores, started a systematic photophysical study on free-base corroles, which confirmed their high potential as components for photoactive arrays.¹³⁵ Whereas the HOMO–LUMO gap was similar to that of porphyrins, they displayed higher luminescence yield, easier oxidation, and a wider absorption in the visible range than porphyrins. Their ability to generate singlet oxygen *via* triplet sensitization was efficient, similar to that of porphyrins and, in analogy to the latter, they displayed characteristic radical, singlet and triplet excited-state absorption spectra.¹³⁵ More or less at the same time many groups started detailed photophysical studies on both free-base and metalated corroles.¹³⁶⁻¹³⁸

1.6.1 Corrole based Donor-Acceptor systems

The collection and conversion of light energy into chemical energy is based on the use of molecular structures of various complexities, where the absorbed light energy is first converted into an excited state able to undergo energy or electron transfer processes and finally it is stored in a charge separated state as chemical (electrochemical) potential. A photosynthesis approach has seen tetrapyrroles number among the most common components of these arrays.

Photophysical and photochemical investigations on corroles were rather scarce and have progressed only in the past few years, although some applications were directly related

to the photophysical properties (in particular luminescence), of these compounds, as in pH sensing and in medicinal use. A systematic photophysical study of free-base corroles by Gryko et al. and others allowed to point out some analogies, but also several superior properties with respect to porphyrins.¹³⁹⁻¹⁴⁰ These investigations, together with parallel electrochemical studies,¹⁴¹ put the basis for the use of free-base corroles as photo and electro active building blocks in the construction of photo functional arrays. The structurally similar porphyrins, due to their excellent properties and availability, have constituted for several decades the most used components of arrays for light energy collection and conversion. However, the need to improve the performances and increase the variety of such molecular systems encouraged the use of other porphyrinoids. Among those, corroles had some success, since they possess the right properties, namely intense light absorption throughout the visible spectral range; singlet excited state lifetimes in the nanosecond range, high luminescence yields and high radiative rate constants, strong absorption features of the excited states, good photostability in most solvents and relative ease of oxidation. These interesting features of corrole macrocycle appears to be promising to play the role of components in photoactive arrays for light energy conversion, and variety of corrole D-A systems for light energy capture and charge separation were designed till date. Reports based on corrole coupled to fullerene (C₆₀), aromatic imides, anthraquinones and bodipys as acceptors,¹⁴²⁻¹⁵⁶ and porphyrins, triphenylamine, corbazole, phenathiozins and polycyclic aromatics as donors,¹⁵⁷⁻¹⁶⁰ displayed efficient energy transfer, light collection efficiency and charge separation. The past few years have witnessed several examples of multi-particle arrays based mostly on the best characterized free-base corroles and to a lesser extent also on their metal complexes. Herein, we would like to present, together with the relevant basic properties of corroles, the most significant cases of corrole-based D-A systems able to display the ability to collect and transfer light energy, to convert it *via* photoinduced electron transfer step(s) and to store it as charge separation. These systems are important for light energy conversion applications and for the production of photoresponsive molecular structures.

1.6.1.1 Corrole-Fullerene D-A systems

Figure 1.21. Molecular structures of Corrole-fullerene dyad systems.

D'Souza, Gryko and co-workers¹⁴² reported first example of covalently linked free-base corrole-fullerene **dyads 1** and **2** (Figure 1.21) with long-lived charge-separated states (CS) in non-polar solvents. In the newly synthesized dyads, the free-energy calculations performed by employing the redox and singlet excited state properties in both polar and nonpolar solvents suggested the possibility of electron transfer from the excited singlet state of corrole to the fullerene entity. Accordingly, steady-state and time-resolved emission study revealed efficient fluorescence quenching of the corrole entity in the dyads. Further studies involving femtosecond laser flash photolysis and nanosecond transient absorption studies confirmed electron transfer to be the quenching mechanism, in which the electron-transfer product, the fullerene anion radical, was able to be spectrally characterized. The yield of CS, measured by a direct comparison with a standard, was around 90% or higher. The bridge length does not affect the yield, and the CS lifetimes are in the microsecond range, 4.5 and 1.6 μs for the short and the long dyad, respectively. The rate of charge separation, k_{CS} , was found to be in the order of 10^{10} - 10^{11} s^{-1} suggesting an efficient photoinduced electron transfer

process. Interestingly, the rate of charge recombination, k_{CR} was slower by five orders of magnitude in non-polar solvents, resulting in a radical ion-pair lasting for several microseconds. This remarkable lifetime is explained on the basis of a strongly “Marcus inverted” reaction, the reorganizational energy is in fact lower than the driving force for charge recombination. This novel feature is due to appropriately positioning the energy level of the charge-separated state below the triplet states of either of the donor and acceptor entities in both polar and non-polar solvents.

Graja, Wrobel and co-workers reported¹⁴³ the bichromophoric systems comprising of corrole and fullerene units, **dyad-3** (Figure 1.21) and representing one of the rare cases of elaborate structures based on corrole with the use of photophysical methods. The dyad displays spectroscopic properties which are the superposition of the component spectra, indicating a very weak electronic coupling. Excitation of the corrole unit leads to charge redistribution. The UV-vis absorption and fluorescence and also fluorescence kinetics suggest the presence of charge separation. It was shown that light absorption of the corrole-fullerene dyad-3 is better fitted to the sunlight spectrum than porphyrin. Electron paramagnetic resonance investigations suggest partial spin density redistribution at low temperature between corrole and fullerene in the dyad. Quantum chemical calculations support experimental results.

Tagmatarchis and co-workers reported,¹⁴⁴ **corrole-C₅₉N** dyad (Figure 1.21) their preparation and characterization of dyad were described.^R Evaluation of the optical and photophysical properties of dyad revealed that upon photoexcitation the characteristic fluorescence of corroles is strongly quenched by the presence of azafullerene in the corrole-C₅₉N dyad. Electrochemical measurements shed light on the redox properties of dyad. Femtosecond transient absorption spectroscopy aided in corroborating the formation of the (corrole)⁺(C₅₉N)⁻ charge separated state directly derived from the corrole singlet excited state.

Recently, our group constructed,¹⁴⁵ corrole-fullerene dyad and corrole – fullerene-triphenylamine triad **TPACor-C₆₀**, (Figure 1.21) in which corrole is directly linked to the β -pyrrole position of the corrole macrocycle and are designed to probe light induced energy and electron transfer events, as photosynthetic model compounds. In the molecular triad, **TPACor-C₆₀**, the energy donor triphenylamine (TPA) was connected at the *meso* position

and the electron acceptor fullerene at the β -pyrrole position of corrole macrocycle. Existence of moderate level of intramolecular interactions between the components of the triad and dyads was witnessed. Excitation of **TPA** entity in **TPACor-C₆₀** revealed efficient singlet-singlet energy transfer from $^1\text{TPA}^*$ to corrole that followed electron transfer from $^1\text{corrole}^*$ to fullerene to yield **TPACor^{•+}-C₆₀^{•-}** charge separated state. A charge separated state was also observed in the case of **TPC-C₆₀** dyad by direct excitation of the corrole entity. Owing to the close association, ultrafast charge separation and rapid charge recombination was witnessed whose rates followed the expected solvent polarity trends. Importantly, in nonpolar toluene, the charge recombination process followed populating $^3\text{corrole}^*$ suggesting that the energy of **TPC^{•+}-C₆₀^{•-}** and **TPACor^{•+}-C₆₀^{•-}** radical ionpairs is higher than the triplet corrole, being 1.52 eV. The present study has successfully demonstrated ultrafast formation of high energy radical ion-pairs in non-polar solvent.

1.6.1.2 Corrole-Aromatic imides

Gryko *et.al* reported¹⁴⁶ 1,8-Naphthalimide-Corrole dyads **CorNI-1** and **CorNI-2** in 2007 (Figure 1.22). When the dyad is excited in the naphthalene imide manifold, the ensuing singlet excited state has enough energy to display intramolecular reactivity. Competitive energy and electron transfer have been evidenced, the relative weight of the two processes being determined by the driving force for charge separation. The energy transfer efficiency decreases from 100% in the dyads containing the corrole more difficult to oxidize to 65% and 15% in the dyads containing corrole with progressively lower oxidation potentials whereas electron transfer efficiency follows the reverse pattern.

Energy transfer is discussed in the frame of current theories; a dipole-dipole mechanism could explain the process in dyads containing the imide **NI-2**, though we cannot exclude a contribution by an electron exchange mechanism. A large contribution by an electron exchange mechanism is proposed in dyads containing the non-emitting imide **NI-1**. Excitation in the corrole manifold yields an excited state which does not display any intramolecular reactivity due to its low energy.

Figure 1.22. Molecular structures of donor acceptor based corrole-aromatic imides.

Same authors in 2010 reported¹⁴⁷ a corrole-naphthalene bisimide dyad **C3-NI** (Figure 1.21) based on solvent polarity effect on intramolecular electron transfer. The properties of simple models were also examined in the same solvents and association phenomena were evidenced in **NI** solutions. In the dyad association is not possible due to steric congestion and electronic factors. An efficient charge separation reaction with yields of the order of 90%

occurs in non-polar and moderately polar solvents upon excitation throughout the UV and the visible wavelength range of **C3-NI**. In the UV, the **NI** unit is excited and the resulting **C3-¹NI** state transfer's energy to the lower lying **¹C3-NI** with rates of the order of 10^{11} s^{-1} , irrespective of solvent polarity. Direct excitation of the latter state in the visible wavelength range, as well as its indirect formation by sensitization, is followed by a LUMO-LUMO electron transfer producing **C3⁺-NI⁻** with rates of the order of 10^9 s^{-1} , about twice in DCM than in toluene. Charge recombination to the ground state has a rate of the order of 10^8 s^{-1} in toluene and is an order of magnitude faster in DCM.

Gryko, Flamigni and co-workers reported¹⁴⁸ perylene bisimide corrole based D-A systems. The bichromophoric systems **C2-PI**, **C3-PI**, and **C3-PPI** consisting of 5,15- meso substituted corroles (2,6 dichlorophenyl and pentafluorophenyl) and perylene bisimide units represent one of the rare cases of elaborate structures (Figure 1.21). **C2-PI** and **C3-PI** differ in the nature of the corroles, whereas **C3-PI** differs from **C3-PPI** in the presence of a further phenyl unit in the linker between photoactive units. Spectroscopic properties which are the superposition of the component spectra indicate a very weak electronic coupling. Excitation of the corrole unit leads to charge separation with a rate which decreases from 2.4×10^{10} to 5.0×10^9 and to $40.9 \times 10^7 \text{ s}^{-1}$ for **C2-PI**, **C3-PI**, and **C3-PPI**, respectively. They also reported¹⁴⁹ a corrole-peryene carboximide dyads (**C2-Pia** and **C2-Pix**) (Figure 1.21) for improving the photo induced charge separation parameters by tuning the redox properties and spectroscopic properties of the components.¹⁵¹ The energy level of the charge separated state was tuned by selecting perylene and corrole components with diverse redox and spectroscopic properties. High spectroscopic energy levels of the perylene carboximide derivatives (**PIs**) allow a fast charge separation to be maintained in competition with an energy-transfer process from the **PI** to the corrole unit. Yields and lifetimes of charge separation in toluene are 75% and $2.5 \mu\text{s}$ for **C2-Pia** and 65% and 24 ns for **C2-Pix**. The results and the effect of solvent polarity are discussed in the framework of energy and electron-transfer theories.

Gryko, Flamigni and co-workers¹⁵⁰ reported energy- and electron transfer processes in corrole-peryenebisimide-triphenylamine array (**TPA-C-PI**) (Figure 1.21). The multi-chromophoric system, , possessing corrole as the central unit linked to perylene bisimide and

N-[4-(phenylethynyl)phenyl]-N,N-diphenylamine was synthesized, as were the component dyads **C-PI** and **C-TPA**. Electrochemical and spectroscopic studies confirmed a weak coupling between the component units in the triad which was characterized by an extensive absorption throughout the 300-700 nm regions. Photophysical measurements showed efficient energy transfer to occur from the diphenylacetylene substituted aromatic amine (99%) and perylene bisimide unit (100%) to the corrole and subsequent electron transfer from the corrole to perylene bisimide (97% efficient). The final charge separated state in **TPA-C⁺-PI⁻** was identified as **TPA-C⁺-PI⁻**, with a lifetime of 1.9 ns, similar to that of **C⁺-PI⁻** (2.3 ns). The charge separated state with charges on the extreme components, **TPA⁺-C-PI⁻**, is not formed for thermodynamic reasons.

The same group¹⁵¹ reported a photoinduced electron transfer in an amine-corrole-peryene bisimide assembly (**DPA-C3-PI**) (Figure 1.21). An assembly has been synthesized that consists of four units; a *meso*-substituted corrole (**C3**), perylenebisimide (**PI**), and two electron-rich triphenylamine (**DPA**) units. **PI** is connected through a 1,4-phenylene bridge to **C3**, whereas the two **DPA** units are linked to **C3** through a diphenyl ether linkage, which is used for the first time to connect the various moieties. Various synthetic strategies were elaborated, and the chosen one afforded the final system in six steps in an overall yield of 6%. The resulting assembly, made of three different units, was named a “triad”. Excitation of the corrole (**C3**) or perylene bisimide (**PI**) units led to the charge-separated state **DPA-C3⁺-PI⁻** with a rate $k > 10$ in benzonitrile and dichloromethane or with k of the order of 10^{10} s^{-1} in toluene. The latter charge separated state decayed to the ground state with a rate $k = 1.8 \times 10^9 \text{ s}^{-1}$ in toluene. In the polar solvents benzonitrile and dichloromethane, recombination to the ground state competes with a charge shift to form the distal charge separated state, **DPA⁺-C3-PI⁻**, the formation of which occurs with a yield of 50 %. Recombination to the ground state of **DPA⁺-C3-PI⁻** occurs with a rate $k = 5 \times 10^7 \text{ s}^{-1}$ in dichloromethane and $k = 2 \times 10^7 \text{ s}^{-1}$ in benzonitrile.

1.6.1.3 Corrole –Bodipys

Recently, our group¹⁵² reported **BODIPY-Cor** based donor–acceptor system *via* ester linkage consisting of BODIPY as energy donor and electron acceptor while free-base corrole as energy acceptor and electron donor (Figure 1.23). The dyad was synthesized and

characterized by using various spectroscopic and electrochemical methods. Optical absorption studies and electrochemical studies showed minimum π - π interactions between the chromophores of the dyad and were supported by DFT calculations. Photophysical studies of the dyad showed that, upon selective excitation of BODIPY moiety results in very efficient energy transfer from BODIPY to corrole with k_{EN} in the range of 1.40×10^9 to $2.95 \times 10^9 \text{ S}^{-1}$. On the other hand, excitation of corrole component of the dyad showed that there is an efficient photo induced electron transfer from the singlet state of corrole to the ground state of BODIPY and are found to be solvent dependent.

Figure 1.23. Molecular structures of Corrole-BODIPY arrays.

John Mack and Zhen Shen group¹⁵³ reported a series of new corrole-BODIPY dyads **5**, **6** and **7** (Figure 1.23), bridged by ethynyl linker moieties with high yields. The direction of energy transfer upon electronic excitation has been explored, and was found to be dependent on the number of corrole rings and their connection position on the BODIPY core. Intense bands in the absorption spectrum cover most of the visible region, which is potentially advantageous for capturing solar energy. Studies of excitation spectra and life times suggest that the energy transfer efficiency between the BODIPY and corrole moieties reaches almost 85%, which appears to be efficient in the context of energy transfer within the singlet manifold. The high ET_{eff} values demonstrate that corrole-BODIPY dyads **5-7** provide an effective way to construct energy transfer systems. ET_{eff} values obtained were 69.3% for **5**, 84.5% for **6** and 58.1% for **7**. The rates of energy transfer (K_{ET}) were 0.63×10^8 , 0.93×10^8 , $0.27 \times 10^8 \text{ s}^{-1}$ for dyads **5**, **6** and **7** respectively.

Recently, Harvey and co-workers¹⁵⁴ reported the synthesis of new covalently linked **red** (no styryl), **green** (styryl mono-substituted), and **blue** (styryl-disubstituted)-BODIPY-gallium(III) corrole derivatives bridged by triazole linkers in high yields using click chemistry (Figure 1.23), and evaluated their photophysical properties. An original and efficient control of the direction of the singlet energy transfers is reported, going either from BODIPY to the gallium-corrole units or from gallium-corroles to BODIPY, depending upon the nature of the substitution on BODIPY. In one case (green), both directions are possible. The mechanism for the energy transfers is interpreted by means of through-space Förster resonance energy transfer (FRET). The direction of the singlet energy transfer, gallium-corrole* \rightarrow BODIPY or BODIPY* \rightarrow gallium-corrole, can be modulated depending on whether zero, one, or two styryl groups are attached to the BODIPY moiety. In one case, both directions were found possible based upon the non-nil spectral overlap of the donor emission and acceptor absorption (i.e., J integral of the Förster theory). The qualitative analysis of the k_{ET} data using FRET clearly shows the presence of conformers in solution; the folded conformers are more stable for compounds **red** and **blue** and the unfolded one is more stable for compound **green-BODIPY-Cor**, which uses slightly different flexible chains. The size of the J integral plays a key role on the size of the k_{ET} value.

1.6.1.4 Corrole–anthraquinone

Giribabu *et.al.*¹⁵⁵ have been designed and synthesized corrole–anthraquinone dyad (**Cor–AQ**) having the ‘Olefin Bridge’ at the β -pyrrole position (Figure 1.24) and characterized by elemental analysis, ESI-MS, ^1H NMR, UV-Visible, fluorescence spectroscopy (steady-state, femtosecond time-resolved), femtosecond transient absorption spectroscopy (*fs*-TA) and electrochemical methods. **Cor–AQ** dyad exhibit significant fluorescence emission quenching (93-95%) of corrole emission compared to the free-base corrole monomer. Emission quenching is attributed to the excited-state intramolecular photo induced electron transfer (PET) from corrole to anthraquinone in the Cor–AQ dyad. The electron-transfer rates (k_{ET}) for **Cor–AQ** were found to be $3.33 \times 10^{11} \text{ s}^{-1}$. Despite their very different driving forces, charge separation (CS) and charge recombination (CR) are found to be in identical timescales.

Figure 1.24. Molecular structures of corrole-anthraquinone systems.

Same research group¹⁵⁶ studied a novel molecular triad, based on corrole and anthraquinone **AQ-(Cor)₂** (Figure 1.24) having azomethine-bridge at the pyrrole- β position and synthesized by following a facile one step reaction. The molecular system, (**AQ-(Cor)₂**) is characterized by fluorescence spectroscopy (steady-state and time-resolved) as well as electrochemical methods. The present study supported by density functional theory calculations manifest that there exist a negligible electronic communication in the ground state between the donor tritolylicorrole and acceptor anthraquinone of the triad. However, interestingly, in the triad (**AQ-(Cor)₂**), fluorescence emission of the tritolylicorrole quenched

significantly (17–80%) compared to their monomeric units. The emission quenching is attributed to the excited state intramolecular photoinduced electron transfer from donor tritollycorrole to acceptor anthraquinone and the electron transfer rates (k_{ET}) are found in the range 4.1×10^8 to $2.4 \times 10^9 \text{ s}^{-1}$ and are solvent dependent.

1.6.1.5 Corrole with Organic donors

Giribabu *et al.*,¹⁵⁷ have designed and synthesized D–A corrole conjugates having either donor triphenylamine connected directly to the acceptor corrole macrocycle or an ethynyl phenyl bridge in between them **TPA-Cor** and **TPA-E-Cor** (Figure 1.25). Both dyads have been characterized by various spectroscopic techniques. Ground state properties indicate that there exist minimum π - π interactions between the aromatic π -planes. This has been supported by energy minimization by DFT calculations. Photophysical studies of these dyads showed that upon selective excitation of the corrole component no photo-induced process occurs, however, excitation of the triphenylamine moiety results in very efficient energy transfer process. The photoinduced processes are discussed in the frame of current theories however, considering the fact that contribution of EET in each investigated solvent is 90% for TPA-Cor and 80% for TPA-E-Cor.

Same group¹⁵⁸ reported donor–acceptor conjugates in which donor polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons such as either pyrene, **Cor-pyr** or fluorine, **Cor-flu** linked at the β -pyrrole position of a corrole using vinylene spacer and (Figure 1.25). Both the dyads are characterized by elemental analysis, MALDI-MS, ^1H NMR, UV–vis and fluorescence spectroscopy (steady-state and time-resolved) as well as electrochemical method. Ground state properties indicate that there is a moderate π - π interaction in these dyad systems. However, fluorescence emission of polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons of both the dyads quenched significantly (88–98%) compared to their monomeric units. The quenched emission was attributed in terms of intramolecular excitation energy transfer, which competes with the photoinduced electron transfer reaction in these dyads.

Figure 1.25. Molecular structures of corrole-organic donor arrays.

Yang Liu *et al*, reported novel donor-acceptor dyad corrole- phenothiazine (**TPC-PTZ**), in which phenothiazine (PTZ) connected at β -pyrrolic position of either freebase corrole (TPC) *via* vinylic spacer¹⁵⁹ (Figure1.25), The ground state properties of the dyad indicate weak electronic communication between the two chromophores. However, the fluorescence emission from the PTZ of the dyad was efficiently quenched (96-99%) as compared to pristine PTZ where the dyad was excited at 310 nm, clearly suggesting that this quenching of fluorescence emission of PTZ in the dyad can be due to intramolecular photo induced energy transfer from excited singlet state of PTZ to corrole macrocycle ($^1\text{PTZ}^*-\text{Cor} \rightarrow \text{PTZ}-^1\text{Cor}^*$). Similar results were also observed when the same experiment performed in different solvents (PhMe, MeCN and DMF) with varying polarity. Forster rate of energy transfer (k_{Forster}) values are in the range of $2.3\text{-}12 \times 10^{10} \text{ s}^{-1}$ for TPC-PTZ in all the investigated solvents.

Recently, Iti guptha¹⁶⁰ and co-workers designed carbazole-corrole dyads with ethynyl bridge and their (Cu, Co) metal complexes **CuCbzTPC** and **CoCbzTPC** (Figure 1.25) were synthesized and studied by electrochemical and excited state properties. Fluorescence studies indicated the efficient energy transfer from donor-carbazole moiety to the acceptor unit corrole in dyads. The linkage of electron rich carbazole moiety to the corrole unit affected their electronic properties in the dyads, as judged by the cyclic voltammetry. Dyads (CuCbzTPC) and (CoCbzTPC) showed cathodic shift compared to their corresponding monomers. The presence of bent phenylethylene linker between donor and acceptor units in the dyads and pentafluorophenyl groups at the *meso*-position of corrole unit in the dyads resulted in the slower rates of energy transfer with reduced efficiency. The calculated values of ET_{eff} is 74% for free-base corrole dyad.

1.6.2 Axially bonded corrole based Donor-acceptor systems

Donor-acceptor systems based on corroles mainly reported using the peripheral positions (either *meso* or β -pyrrole) of the corrole macrocycle. Only a few were reported on the axial bonding using the resident metal/metalloid atom to better understand the electron and energy transfer directions to mimic natural photosynthetic system. In recent times, Al(III),¹⁶¹ Ga(III),¹⁶² Sn(IV)¹⁶³ and P(V)¹⁶⁴ corroles have been studied and shown that these complexes are highly fluorescent with high quantum yields. The main motivation behind the study of corrole complexes with main group elements (especially Ga(III) and P(V) corrole complexes) is due to their good photophysical properties.

1.6.2.1 Phosphorous (V)-Corrole

Figure 1.26. a) Molecular structures of P(V) Corrole, b) Absorption spectra and c) Emission spectra of P(V) Corrole.

Like P(V) porphyrins, P(V) corroles are unique in which phosphorus is hexacoordinated having two axial ligands which is facile for construction of D-A systems using axial positions. X-ray crystal structure of P(V)corrole confirmed the hexacoordination environment.¹⁶⁵ The absorption spectra of P(V)-corroles showed high intense solet band ~ 410 nm and also strong Q-band at about ~ 600 nm together with other Q-bands, in contrast to P(V)porphyrins, which showed weak bands in the visible region (Figure 1.26). These P(V)corrole complexes were easier to oxidize and more difficult to reduce compared to P(V) porphyrins. These compounds are highly fluorescent, unlike P(V) porphyrins, and the quantum yields for selected P(V) corroles were as high as Al(III) and Ga(III) corroles,¹⁶⁶⁻¹⁶⁷ which are the best known fluorescent compounds among oligopyrrolic macrocycles. Due to these interesting properties the axial substituted hexa-coordinated P(V) corrole complexes will have potential applications in various fields, including photodynamic therapy and bio-imaging.¹⁶⁸⁻¹⁶⁹

M.Ravikanth¹⁷⁰ and co-workers reported the stabilization of the hexa-coordination environment of P(V) corroles by using alkyl/aryl substituted silyloxy groups as axial ligands. The hexacoordination geometry of **P(V) corrole complexes-a, b and c** (Figure 1.26) can be stabilized by substituting axial hydroxyl groups of a central P(V) atom by various alkyl/aryl substituted silyloxy groups. However, P(V) corroles generally undergo axial ligand dissociation to form a mixture of penta- and hexa-coordinated P(V) corroles in non-coordinating solvents such as toluene, CH₂Cl₂, CHCl₃. The usage of moderately bulkier and electron donating silyloxy groups helps to restrict the axial ligand dissociation of silyloxy substituted hexacoordinated P(V) corroles in non-coordinating solvents, such as benzene, toluene, and CH₂Cl₂, and do not undergo dissociation to penta-coordinated P(V) corrole complexes. The crystal structure confirmed the hexacoordination geometry for the P(V) corroles. The P(V) corroles are highly fluorescent in a hexacoordination environment compared to pentacoordination environment, the silyloxy substituted hexacoordinated P(V) corrole complexes exhibit interesting absorption, electrochemical and fluorescence properties and are highly stable under electrochemical conditions.

Giribabu *et al.*¹⁷¹ designed new vertically-aligned hetero trimeric arrays based on the P(V) corrole scaffold . While a phosphorus (V)corrole forms the basal scaffolding unit, either

two free-base porphyrins $[(H_2)_2-PCor]$ or Zn II porphyrins $[(Zn)_2-PCor]$ occupy the two axial sites *via* an aryloxy bridge (Figure 1.27). In addition, their photophysical properties have also been investigated systematically and the results were interpreted in terms of intramolecular electron and energy transfer mechanisms. The efficiency of the intramolecular EET from the central P(V)corrole to the axial free-base porphyrin is $\sim 85\%$. Similar quenching efficiency calculations of the zinc porphyrins as axial ligands of trimer arrays was not possible because of absorption overlap of the bands due to the donor P(V)corrole and acceptor zinc porphyrin. However, the PET reaction from the singlet-state of central P(V)corrole to the axial free-base porphyrins cannot be ruled out based on thermodynamic considerations, when excited at 405 nm.

Figure 1.27. Molecular structures of axially linked corrole D-A systems.

Same group¹⁷² have constructed hetero dimers by exploiting axial bonding capabilities of Ge(IV) corroles [(H₂)-GeCor] and [Zn-GeCor] (Figure 1.27). The ground state properties indicate that there are minimum π - π interactions between the macrocyclic units of these hetero dimers. ¹H NMR spectra indicate that the disposition of porphyrin unit in these hetero dimers is of 'vertical' type. Quenched emission observed due to an intramolecular EET from Ge(IV) corrole to the axial porphyrin compete with a PET from ground state of axial porphyrin to the excited state of Ge(IV) corrole, when excited at 400 nm in both the hetero dimers. The energy transfer efficiency was found to be 72 and 60% in [(H₂)-GeCor] and [(Zn)-GeCor], respectively. The quenched emission was observed, when excited at 425 nm was due to intramolecular PET from axial excited porphyrin to the ground state of Ge(IV) corrole. However, the PET reaction from ground state of axial H₂/Zn to the excited state of basal metalloid corrole cannot be ruled out on thermodynamic considerations when excited at 400 nm.

1.7 Summary

The basic principles involved in electron- and energy transfer and relevance of these in biological and abiological systems as applicable to the subject matter of this thesis are presented in this chapter.

This thesis has been divided into seven chapters.

1.8 References

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Chapter-2

Materials and Instrumentation

2.1 Introduction

In this chapter presented to specify the range of chemicals, describes the standard procedures used during sample preparation and other materials employed at various stages of the research work. Procedures followed for the purification of solvents and chemicals are given. Further, a brief discussion of the various instrumental methods, in particular the photophysical and electrochemical techniques employed during the course of the investigation of energy and electron transfer.

2.2. Materials Used

Reagents

Pyrrole, p-tolaldehyde, 4-hydroxybenzaldehyde, N,N-dicyclohexadecarbamide (DCC) and DMAP [(4-(dimethylamino)pyridine], Mesitaldehyde, Pentafluorobenzaldehyde, Pentafluoro benzoylchloride, Ethylbromide, 1,5-dibromoanthraquinone, β -Naphthol, Pyrene-1-ol, Indium chloride, Scandium(III)triflate, Pyridine and POCl_3 , are purchased from either sigma Aldrich or TCI and Tetrabutyl ammonium perchlorate (TBAP), used as supporting electrolyte in cyclic voltammetry was purchased from Aldrich (India).

Acids

Hydrochloric acid (HCl), Trifluoro acetic acid (CF_3COOH), Propionic acid, Sulphuric acid (H_2SO_4), Nitric acid (HNO_3) were of AR grade obtained from Ranbaxy (India).

Bases and salts

Zinc(II)acetate (ZnOAc), Triethylamine (TEA), Magnesium (Mg), Sodium nitrite (NaNO_2), Copperbromide, (CuBr), Calcium chloride (CaCl_2), Sodium hydroxide (NaOH), Potassium carbonate (K_2CO_3), Sodium bicarbonate (NaHCO_3), Sodium carbonate (Na_2CO_3), Sodium sulphate (Na_2SO_4), Ammonium acetate ($\text{CH}_3\text{COO}^-\text{NH}_4^+$) were purchased from Finar chemicals.

Solvents

Dichloromethane (DCM), Chloroform (CHCl_3), Acetonitrile (ACN), Tetrahydrofuran (THF), Hexane, Benzonitrile (PhCN), Dimethylsulphoxide (DMSO) Ethanol, Methanol,

Diethyl ether, Toluene, Ethylacetate, Diehylether, Pentane, Millipore Water (H₂O) all these were gained from Finar chemicals (INDIA).

The solvents employed during the research work were purified according to the standard procedures.¹⁻² The LR grade methylene chloride was washed twice with sulphuric acid, and then with water. This was followed by washing twice with sodium bicarbonate solution and then with water. The solvent was dried over calcium chloride and distilled over phosphorus pentoxide. It was stored over basic alumina until use. Chloroform (LR) was washed with water 2 to 3 times, stored over calcium chloride overnight, and distilled over phosphorus pentoxide. It was stored in the dark over basic alumina. Acetone, triethylamine ethanol and acetonitrile were purified according to the procedures reported in the literature.³⁻⁴

The deuterated solvents such as Chloroform-d and methanol-d were obtained from Aldrich Chemicals (U.S.A.) and were used as such.

Chromatography materials

Pre-coated silica gel 60-F254 plates were purchased from Merck for thin layer chromatography, Silica gel (60-120, 100-200, mesh) and Basic Alumina were purchased from Finar chemicals (India).

2.3 Instrumentation Techniques

The structural and photophysical investigations utilized as analytical proofs for characterizing a range of monomers, dimer and trimer D-A systems, which are synthesized and reported in this thesis includes: ¹H-NMR,NOESY spectra, ESI/MALDI Mass, Single crystal X-ray diffraction, TEM, AFM,UV-visible spectroscopy, Fluorescence spectroscopy, Pico second time-resolved fluorescence (TCSPC), Transient absorption and electrochemical methods. These techniques were elaborated briefly as follows.

2.3.1. Structural Characterization

The ¹H NMR spectra were recorded using either a Bruker 400MHz AVANCE or 500MHz INOVA spectrometer running X-Win software with Trimethylsilane(TMS) as the internal standard, NOESY spectra were recorded at 298 K on a 500 MHz INOVA

spectrometer, respectively, and deuterated Chloroform/Methanol solvents with typical sample concentration of 1×10^{-3} M.

ESI-Mass spectra were recorded on Thermo LCQ Fleet Ion Trap mass spectrometer and MALDITOF mass spectra were recorded with an Axima Performance MALDI-TOF/TOF mass spectrometer. Major fragmentations of the molecule were given as percentages relative to the base peak intensity.

X-ray data for the compound were collected at room temperature using a Bruker Smart Apex CCD diffractometer with graphite monochromated Mo-K α radiation ($\lambda = 0.71073$ Å) with ω -scan method.⁵ Integration and scaling of intensity data were accomplished using SAINT program.⁵ The structures were solved by Direct Methods using SHELXS97,⁶ and refinement was carried out by full-matrix least-squares technique using SHELXL-2014/7.⁶

Transmission Electron Microscope (TEM) measurements were carried out using FEI (TECNAI G2 30 S-TWIN) with an accelerating voltage of 100 kV without staining. Atomic Force Microscopy (AFM) images recorded under ambient conditions using a NTEGRA (NT-MDT) operating with a tapping mode regime. Micro-fabricated TiN cantilever tips (NSG10) with a resonance frequency of 299 kHz and a spring constant of 20-80 Nm⁻¹ used for measurement.

2.3.2. Photophysical Characterization

2.3.2.1 UV-vis spectroscopy

The UV-Visible spectra were recorded on a Shimadzu (Model UV-3600) spectrophotometer using 1×10^{-6} M concentrations (for Soret band) and 5×10^{-5} M concentration (for Q bands). The intense color of tetrapyrrolic compounds are due to the highly conjugated macrocyclic ring. Porphyrins exhibit characteristic absorption bands in the UV-Visible region, a sharp intense band at the near-UV region, around 420 nm with molar extinction coefficient (ϵ): 10^5 M⁻¹cm⁻¹ due to excitation to second excited state (S_0 to S_2) and weak bands in the visible region, around 500-750 nm with ϵ : 10^4 M⁻¹cm⁻¹ due to excitation to the singlet excited state (S_0 to S_1). These tetra pyrrolic compounds absorption bands usually depends on the nature and geometrical orientation of the peripheral/axial substitutions with

respect to the macrocycle and thus they are the clear identities of the substituents and the metal centre that affects the relative energies of electronic transitions.

Figure 2.1. A typical UV-Visible absorption spectra of a) free-base porphyrin and b) free-base Corrole.

The effect of changes in conjugation pathway and symmetry of macrocycle on its UV-Visible absorption spectra are well documented in the literature.⁷ Corrole also show similar kind of absorption spectram in the UV-Visible region a sharp, intense. (Figure 2.1)

2.3.2.2 Fluorescence Spectroscopy

Fluorescence spectroscopy is used to measure emission of a compound as a function of wavelength. Upon illumination molecules absorb photons and excite the electrons into higher energy levels. These excited molecules emit the photons with lower energy than the initial absorbed energy while relaxing to the ground state. By calculating the area of the emission spectra we can predict the quantum yield (ϕ) of the compound by using the following formula.

$$\phi_{\text{Sample}} = \frac{A_{\text{Sample}} \times OD_{\text{Standard}}}{A_{\text{Standard}} \times OD_{\text{Sample}}} \times \phi_{\text{Standard}} \dots \dots \dots (2.1)$$

Where, A = area of the emission spectra, OD = optical density of the sample at the excitation maxima. In addition, the band gap between HOMO and LUMO also calculated by overlapping the emission spectra and the absorption spectra, the intersection point is corresponds to band gap wavelength.

$$E_{0-0} = \frac{1240}{\lambda} \dots\dots\dots (2.2)$$

Where, λ is the wavelength at intersection point.

The concentration of the solutions was maintained constantly at OD~0.05 for all the compounds in order to eliminate the possibility of quenching caused by aggregation. Such aggregations are competing quenching pathways and are usually observed at higher sample concentrations. The reported standard Φ values used for reference compounds are: $\phi = 0.13$ for free-base porphyrin (5, 10, 15, 20-tetraphenyl porphyrin),⁸ $\phi = 0.036$ for Zn porphyrin (5,10,15,20- tetraphenyl porphyrinato zinc(II)) $\phi = 0.19$, for free-base corrole (5, 10, 15, triphenylcorrole), $\phi = 0.356$ in CH₂Cl₂ solvent.⁹ Usually, porphyrins and corrole show distinct emission peaks around 550-800 nm. Metallated porphyrins usually show quenched emission due to increased rate of inter system crossing to triplet excited state, thereby reducing the emission intensity.

2.3.2.3 TCSPC measurements

Time correlated single photon counting (TCSPC) method was used for measuring the fluorescence lifetime of the molecules in their excited state using a Fluorolog-3 Triple Illuminator, IBH Horiba JobinYvon setup. This setup includes a picosecond light emitting diode laser (NanoLED) as the excitation source and a photomultiplier tube R928P, Hamamatsu) as the detector. A scatterer (Ludox sample diluted in DD water) was used to record the lamp profile. IBH DAS6 (version 2.3) software was used to analyze the decay curves using the non-linear least squares interaction procedure. The quality of the fit was ascertained from the χ^2 values and the distribution of residuals. Free-base corroles show longer excited state lifetime (~4 ns) compared to the metalated corrole (~0.001 ns). Free-base porphyrins show longer excited state lifetime (~9 ns) compared to the metalated porphyrins (~ 1 to 2 ns). The number of lifetime components depends on the number of individual moieties present in the target molecule as well as on the flexibility of the intervening spacer between the macrocycle and the substituents.

2.3.2.4 Femtosecond Transient absorption spectroscopy

Femtosecond transient absorption spectroscopy experiments were performed using an Ultrafast Femtosecond Laser Source (Libra) by Coherent incorporating

diode-pumped, mode locked Ti:Sapphire laser (Vitesse) and diode-pumped intra cavity doubled Nd:YLF laser (Evolution) to generate a compressed laser output of 1.10 W. For optical detection, a Helios transient absorption spectrometer coupled with femtosecond harmonics generator both provided by Ultrafast Systems LLC was used. The source for the pump and probe pulses were derived from the fundamental output of the Libra (Compressed output 1.15 W, pulse width 100 fs) at a repetition rate of 1 kHz. The source for the pump and probe pulses were derived from the fundamental output of Libra (Compressed output 1.45 W, pulse width 100 fs) at a repetition rate of 1 kHz. About 95% of the fundamental output of the laser was introduced into a TOPAS-Prime-OPA system with 290-2600 nm tuning range from Altos Photonics Inc., (Bozeman, MT), while the rest of the output was used for generation of white light continuum. Kinetic traces at appropriate wavelengths were assembled from the time-resolved spectral data. Data analysis was performed using Surface Xplorer software supplied by Ultrafast Systems. All measurements were conducted in degassed solutions at 298 K.

2.3.3 Electrochemical Characterization

Cyclic voltammetric (CV) and differential pulse voltammetric (DPV) techniques using a PC-controlled electrochemical analyser (CH instrument model CHI620C). The sample concentration used for these analyses was ~1mM in an organic solvent and the scan rate was maintained at 100 mV s⁻¹ for CV and 10 mV s⁻¹ for DPV measurements. The system was internally calibrated with ferrocene/ferrocenium (Fc/Fc⁺). Tetrabutylammonium perchlorate (TBAP) was used as a supporting electrolyte. Glassy carbon was used as the working electrode (WE), Platinum wire as the counter electrode (CE) and saturated calomel electrode as the reference electrode (RE). The sample solution was always flushed and degassed with Nitrogen gas purchased from IOLAR (India) Limited, which was prior purified by passing through alkaline pyrogallol solution and KOH pellets.

The redox potentials of the macrocycle are generally affected by the nature of metalation and peripheral/axial substitutions, and by the planarity of the macrocyclic ring. Porphyrins undergo two reversible one-electron oxidations and two reversible one-electron reductions.¹⁰ Corroles are generally easier to oxidize than analogous porphyrins; Corroles

undergo three reversible one-electron oxidations, one reversible and one quasireversible one-electron reductions. In both the cases first oxidation and reduction corresponds to the formation of porphyrin/corrole π -cation/anion radical. (Figure 2.2)

Figure: 2.2. Typical cyclic voltagram.

Spectroelectrochemical experiments were performed using a CH instruments model CHI 620C electrochemical analyzer utilizing a three-electrode configuration of thin layer quartz spectroelectrochemical cell at 25°C. The working electrode was transparent Pt gauze. Pt wire counter electrode and SCE reference electrode separated from the bulk of the solution by a double bridge were used.

2.3.4 Theoretical Studies

All the calculations have been carried out using a Gaussian 09 package in personal computer.¹¹ The obtained geometries of all the donor-acceptor molecules were stable in their conformation to genuine global minimum energy structures using B3LYP hybrid functional and 6-31G(d,p) basis set were used as the input for further calculations.¹²⁻¹³ Executed ground state properties are energy-minimized structures, frontier molecular orbitals (FMOs) by Density Functional Theory (DFT) in the gas phase. Time Dependent Density Functional Theory (TD-DFT) obtained excited state properties like percentage of molecular contribution, oscillatory strength and singlet transition energy in the dichloromethane (DCM) solvent. The geometries were then used to obtain the frontier molecular orbitals (FMOs) and were also subjected to single-point TDDFT studies (first 10 vertical singlet-singlet

transitions) to obtain the UV-Vis spectra of the molecules. The integral equation formalism polarizable continuum model (PCM) within the self-consistent reaction field (SCRF) theory was used in the TDDFT calculations to describe with M06-2x function and the solvation of the donor-acceptor molecules in dichloromethane.^{14,15} The software GaussSum-2.2.5 was employed to simulate the major portions of the absorption spectra and to interpret the nature of transitions.^{16,17} The contribution percentages of individual units present in the D-A system to the respective molecular orbitals were calculated.

2.4 General considerations

At all times, care was taken to avoid the entry of direct, ambient light into the samples in the spectroscopic and electrochemical experiments. Unless otherwise specified, all experiments were carried out at ambient temperature. All hazardous chemicals were handled with appropriate precaution. Protective gloves, goggles, and safety mask were employed to minimize exposure to obnoxious chemicals, ultraviolet light etc.

The following are the standard error limits involved in various measurements (unless otherwise stated)

λ max (absorption/fluorescence)	± 1 nm
log ϵ	$\pm 10\%$
^1H NMR chemical shifts	± 0.01 ppm
$E_{1/2}$	± 0.03 V
ϕ	$\pm 10\%$

2.5 Summary

This chapter presents a brief account of various solvents and chemicals used in this study. A description of the spectroscopic and other physical methods employed in this study is also given.

2.6 References

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Chapter-3

*Synthesis, Structure and Photophysical
Properties of Ferrocenyl or mixed
Sandwich Cobaltocenyl Ester Linked
meso-Tetratolylporphyrin Dyads*

3.1 Introduction

As we discussed in the introduction chapter, a great variety of donor-acceptor systems based on porphyrins and its closely related molecules such as corroles, phthalocyanines, core modified porphyrins etc., have been utilized to achieve long-lived charge separated states. In the present chapter, we have utilized *meso* phenyl positions of either free-base or zinc metallated porphyrins have utilized for the construction of D-A systems.

Several models have been synthesized to explain and understand the photoinduced multistep electron transfer (ET) in natural photosynthetic reaction centers (RC) and also to develop solar energy conversion systems.¹⁻⁷ In these studies, the interest has been focused on extending the lifetime of the charge-separated state to facilitate the succeeding multistep ET reactions. The most common approach, for the design of these molecules, follows the pattern of donor-bridge-acceptor in which the charge separation arises from a photoinduced electron transfer between the two ends of the molecule. Due to the availability of easy synthetic protocols, manipulation of electrochemical and photophysical properties and their relevance in natural photosynthesis, porphyrins are the excellent choice for the construction of donor-acceptor systems.⁸⁻¹⁰

Donor-acceptor (D-A) systems based on porphyrins have been reported in literature either by using peripheral (*meso* phenyl or pyrrole- β) or axial position/s of resident metal ion,¹¹⁻¹⁵ Of these D-A systems, we are particularly interested in porphyrin-metallocene dyad systems (Figure 3.1). Porphyrins substituted with ferrocene units at the periphery have attained considerable interest in recent years due to a range of potential applications.¹⁶⁻²⁵ Ferrocene has a low-lying triplet excited state and is known to be an effective triplet quencher.³ The singlet excited state of porphyrin can be reduced by ferrocene and the ferrocenyl center can in turn be reversibly oxidized. The lowest excited singlet state of ferrocene is higher in energy than the lowest excited singlet state of the porphyrin. Gust and Imahori have independently developed initial charge separation (CS) models by combining the central porphyrin unit with carotene and ferrocene (Fc) as donors, and fullerene (C₆₀) as an acceptor. In these studies, the excellent features of C₆₀ were crucial for obtaining the long-lived CS state with high quantum yields.^{22,25} Ferrocene substituted porphyrins have also been synthesized with a variety of spacers between the ferrocene and porphyrin units. D'Souza *et*

al. have constructed D-A systems by using covalently linked zinc porphyrin-ferrocene(s) dyads, self-assembled *via* axial coordination to either pyridine- or imidazole-appended fulleropyrrolidine. Photoexcitation of these systems form the CS of $\text{Fc}^+-\text{ZnP}-\text{C}_{60}^-$ with high quantum efficiency.^{21,23} During the course of our research on porphyrin based D-A systems, we realized that cobaltocene is an alternative choice for construction of porphyrin-metalloocene dyad systems. We have chosen the cobalt mixed sandwich compound $\eta^5-[\text{C}_5\text{H}_4(\text{COOH})]\text{Co}(\eta^4-\text{C}_4\text{Ph}_4)$ as a metalloocene entity due to its high stability and electron donor capability.^{26,27} Recently, Elias and co-workers reported the synthesis and properties of porphyrins substituted at the *meso* positions with sterically hindered $\eta^5-[\text{C}_5\text{H}_4(\text{COOH})]\text{Co}(\eta^4-\text{C}_4\text{Ph}_4)$ cobalt mixed sandwich units.²⁸ Although, there are examples for structurally characterized $\eta^5-[\text{C}_5\text{H}_4(\text{COOH})]\text{Co}(\eta^4-\text{C}_4\text{Ph}_4)$ linked porphyrin system, no systematic photophysical investigations has been done on these systems. Here, in the present study, we have constructed mainly two dyad systems in which ferrocene and cobalt sandwich compound $\eta^5-[\text{C}_5\text{H}_4(\text{COOH})]\text{Co}(\eta^4-\text{C}_4\text{Ph}_4)$ at *meso* phenyl position of either free-base or Zn(II) porphyrin.²⁸ Both the dyad systems have been completely characterized by elemental analysis, MALDI-MS, UV-Visible, ^1H NMR and fluorescence (steady-state and time-resolved) spectroscopies as well as electrochemical methods. In addition, we compared the photophysical properties of porphyrin-ferrocenyl and porphyrin-cobaltocenyl dyads for first time to the best of our knowledge. The molecular structure of both the dyads is shown in Scheme 3.1

Figure 3.1. Molecular structures of H_2TTPFe , ZnTTPFe , H_2TTPCo and ZnTTPCo .

3.2 Experimental section

5,10,15,20-tetra-(4-tolyl)porphyrin (**H₂TTP**), 5-(4-hydroxyphenyl)-10,15,20-tritolylporphyrin (**H₂TTP-OH**), 5,10,15,20-tetra-(4-tolyl)porphyrinato zinc(II) (**ZnTTP**), 5-(4-hydroxyphenyl)-10,15,20-tritolylporphyrinato zinc(II) (**ZnTTP-OH**), ferrocenecarboxylic acid and η^5 -[C₅H₄(COOH)]Co(η^4 -C₄Ph₄) were synthesized according to the reported procedures.^{28,29}

3.2.1 Synthesis of 5-(phenyl-4-[(η^5 -cyclopentadienyl-oate)(η^4 -tetraphenyl cyclobutadiene)cobalt])-10,15,20-tritolylporphyrin (**H₂TTPCo**)

This compound was synthesized by adopting literature reported procedure.³⁰ 5-(4-hydroxyphenyl)-10,15,20-tritolylporphyrin (0.08 g, 0.12 mmol) and η^5 -[C₅H₄(COOH)]Co(η^4 -C₄Ph₄) (0.062 g, 0.12 mmol) were dissolved in 40 ml of dry dichloromethane. To this catalytic amount of DMAP [(4-(dimethylamino)pyridine)] was added under argon, followed by the addition of 1.0 M solution of *N,N'*-dicyclohexylcarbodiimide (1.2 mL, 1.18 mmol) in dichloromethane. The reaction mixture was stirred at room temperature for 4-5 h and the reaction was monitored by TLC. The solvent was removed under vacuo and the residue was purified by using silica gel column chromatography with hexane/dichloromethane (4:6, v/v) to afford **H₂TTPCo** as dark-reddish solid (yield: 72%). Anal. Calcd. for C₈₁H₅₉CoN₄O₂ % (1178.39): C, 82.50; H, 5.04; N, 4.75. Found C, 82.47; H, 5.00; N, 4.71. MALDI-TOF MS: 1180. ¹H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl₃): δ (ppm) 8.91 (m, 3H), 8.87 (s, 5H), 8.10-8.12 (m, 6H), 8.06 (d, 2H, *J* = 5 Hz), 7.56-7.58 (m, 14 H), 7.30-7.33 (m, 12 H), 6.91 (d, 2H, *J* = 5 Hz), 5.53 (m, 2H), 4.95 (m, 2H), 2.72 (s, 9H), -2.77 (brs, 2H). UV-vis (CH₂Cl₂): λ_{\max} : 264, 420, 517, 552, 593, 648 nm.

3.2.2 Synthesis of 5-(phenyl-4-[(η^5 -cyclopentadienyl-oate)(η^4 -tetraphenyl cyclobutadiene)cobalt])-10,15,20-tritolylporphyrinato Zn(II) (**Zn-TTPCo**)

H₂TTPCo (0.03 g, 0.033 mmol) and Zn(OAc)₂·2H₂O (0.365 g, 1.65 mmol) was dissolved in 20 ml of CHCl₃/MeOH (1:1) mixture. The resultant reaction mixture was refluxed until Q bands absorption spectrum was changed. The solvent was removed under vacuo and the solid

obtained was subjected to silica gel column chromatography to afford the corresponding Zn(II) complex in quantitative yield. Anal.Calcd.for $C_{81}H_{57}CoN_4O_2Zn$ % (1242.66): C, 78.29; H, 4.62; N, 4.51. Found C, 78.32; H, 4.65; N, 4.47. MALDI-TOF MS: 1241. 1H NMR (300 MHz, $CDCl_3$): δ (ppm) 9.00 (d, 2H, $J = 3$ Hz), 8.95-8.97 (m, 5H), 8.10-8.13 (m, 6H), 8.05 (d, 2H, $J = 9$ Hz), 7.55-7.58 (m, 14H), 7.29-7.31 (m, 12H), 6.89 (d, 2H, $J = 9$ Hz), 5.52 (m, 2H), 4.94 (m, 2H), 2.72 (s, 9H). UV-vis (CH_2Cl_2): λ_{max} : 258, 420, 549, 590 nm.

3.2.3 Synthesis of 5-(phenyl-4-yl η^5 -Ferrocenyl)-10,15,20-tritolylporphyrin (H_2TTPFe)

This compound was synthesized by adopting similar procedure for the synthesis of H_2TTPCo with yield: 65%. Anal.Calcd.for $C_{58}H_{44}FeN_4O_2$ % (884.84): C, 78.73; H, 5.01; N, 6.33. Found C, 78.75; H, 5.01; N, 6.35. MALDI-TOF MS: 884. 1H NMR (300 MHz, $CDCl_3$): δ (ppm) 8.99 (m, 4H), 8.87 (s, 4H), 8.26-8.28 (m, 2H), 8.10-8.12 (m, 6H), 7.55-7.66 (m, 8H), 5.13 (m, 2H), 4.60 (m, 2H), 4.44 (s, 5H), 2.72 (s, 9H), -2.76 (brs, 2H). UV-vis (CH_2Cl_2): λ_{max} : 419, 517, 551, 593, 648 nm.

3.2.4 Synthesis of 5-(phenyl-4-yl η^5 -Ferrocenyl)-10,15,20-tritolylporphyrinato Zn(II) ($ZnTTPFe$)

This compound was synthesized by adopting similar procedure for the synthesis of $ZnTTPCo$. Anal.Calcd.for $C_{58}H_{42}FeN_4O_2Zn$ % (948.21): C, 73.47; H, 4.46; N, 5.91. Found C, 73.45; H, 4.41; N, 5.95. MALDI-TOF MS: 946. 1H NMR (300 MHz, $CDCl_3$): δ (ppm) 8.99 (dd, 4H, $J = 5$ Hz), 8.96 (s, 4H), 8.26-8.27 (m, 2H), 8.10-8.12 (m, 6H), 7.55-7.59 (m, 8H), 5.13 (m, 2H), 4.60 (m, 2H), 4.43 (s, 5H), 2.72 (s, 9H). UV-vis (CH_2Cl_2): λ_{max} : 421, 549, 585 nm.

Figure 3.2. ¹H NMR spectrum of η^5 -[C₅H₄(COOH)]Co(η^4 -C₄Ph₄) in CDCl₃.

Figure 3.3. ¹H NMR spectrum of Ferrocene-COOH in CDCl₃.

Figure 3.4. ^1H NMR spectrum of $\text{H}_2\text{TPPCoin}$ in CDCl_3 .

Figure 3.5. MALDI-TOF of H_2TPPCo .

Figure 3.6. ¹H NMR spectrum of ZnTPPCo in CDCl₃.

Figure 3.7. MALDI-TOF of ZnTPPCo.

Figure 3.8. 1H NMR spectrum of H_2TPPFe in $CDCl_3$.

Figure 3.9. MALDI-TOF of H_2TPPFe .

Figure 3.10. ¹H NMR spectrum of ZnTPPCo in CDCl₃.

Figure 3.11. MALDI-TOF of ZnTPPCo.

3.3. Results and Discussion

3.3.1. Synthesis and Structural Characterization

Synthetic scheme for preparing both the free-base dyads and their Zn-complexes are shown in Scheme. 3.1. The synthesis of dyads was accomplished by a one-step esterification reaction of 5-(4-hydroxyphenyl)-10,15,20-tritolylporphyrin with the corresponding metallocene-carboxylic acid in the presence of 4-(dimethylamino)pyridine and DCC at room temperature.³⁰ Both the free-bases **H₂TTPCo** and **H₂TTPFe** were subjected to Zn-metallation in the presence of Zn(OAc)₂·4H₂O to afford the corresponding Zn-complexes, **Zn-TTPCo** and **Zn-TTPFe**, respectively. Preliminary characterization of all dyads has been carried out by MALDI-TOF MS and UV-Visible spectroscopic methods. The presence of molecular ion peak in MALDI-MS spectra confirms the exact composition for the formation of corresponding dyads (Figure 3.5, 3.7, 3.9 and 3.11)

Scheme 3.1. Synthetic scheme of porphyrin–metalloocene dyads through ester spacer.

Figure 3.4 and 3.8 illustrates the ¹H NMR spectra of both the free-base dyads. The ¹H NMR spectrum of **H₂TTPCo** exhibit two multiplet signals between 4.95 and 5.53 ppm corresponding to the cyclopentadienyl ring of cobaltocenyl moiety, which is slightly downfield shifted as compared to the cyclopentadienyl ring (cp) of η^5 -[C₅H₄(COOH)]Co(η^4 -

C₄Ph₄) which appeared at 4.83 and 5.23 ppm, respectively. The signals between 6.91 and 8.91 ppm are ascribable for the β -pyrrole and the phenyl protons. In the case of **H₂TTPFe**, the signals for ferrocenyl rings resonate between 4.40-5.10 ppm, which is slightly downfield-shifted as compared to the cyclopentadienyl ring of ferrocenecarboxylic acid which resonates between 4.20-4.80 ppm and the remaining protons are observed between 7.66 and 8.99 ppm. The downfield signals of the cp-ring of metallocene connected to porphyrin are probably due to the electron releasing nature tendency of the metallocene from the porphyrin core. Both **H₂TTPCo** and **H₂TTPFe** show inner -NH signals around -2.77 ppm typical for free-base porphyrins. On zinc metallation, no appreciable changes were observed both on the porphyrin as well as metallocene signals (Figure 3.6 and 3.10) except disappearance of the inner -NH signals.

3.3.2 X-ray structural Characterization

The molecular structure of **Zn-TTPCo** was determined by X-ray crystallography and is shown in Figure 3.12a, and its crystallographic data and structural refinement parameters are given in Table 3.2. The pertinent bond length and bond angle data are given in Table 3.1. As expected the Zn-porphyrin part is nearly planar and the structure illustrates that the molecule has interestingly the cobalt sandwich unit connected to the porphyrin macrocycle through C-O bond (1.353 Å) having a sterically hindered tetraphenylcyclobutadiene unit. The *meso* phenyl group attached at C15 position having cobalt sandwich unit is not coplanar having dihedral angle of 116.3(8)°. Interestingly, the central Zn-ion leads to the formation of a dimeric structure, consisting of two macrocycles, related to each other by an inversion center and held together using the carbonyl O atom of one macrocycle as an axial ligand to the zinc center of another (Figure 3.12b). Thus, the core geometry is similar to that of penta coordinate zinc(II)porphyrins, with the zinc center located 0.22 Å above the mean plane of the molecule and a Zn---O bond length of 2.356 (7)Å. Similar dimers were previously observed for zinc(II) complex of anhydro-meso-rhodochlorin methyl ester that are held together by axial interactions between the zinc(II) center and the cyclohexanone carbonyl O atom of a neighboring macrocycle with Zn---O bond length of 2.204 (3)Å.³²

Figure 3.12. (a) Molecular structure of Zn-TTPCo. (b) View of the dimer formed via axial Zn–O interactions. Meso-tolyl groups on the porphyrin and phenyl groups attached to the cyclobutadiene ring are removed for clarity.

Table 3.1. Selected bond lengths (Å) and bond angles (deg) for ZnTTPCo.

Bond Lengths (Å)		Bond Angle (deg)	
Zn(1)-N(1)	2.042(5)	C(1)-N(1)-C(4)	106.7(4)
n(1)-N(2)	2.053(1)	C(11)-N(3)-C(14)	106.7(2)
C(4)-C(5)	1.402(6)	C(4)-C(5)-C(6)	123.8(9)
C(9)-C(10)	1.401(1)	C(9)-C(10)-C(11)	124.9(8)
C(14)-C(15)	1.397(3)	C(14)-C(15)-C(16)	125.3(6)
C(19)-C(20)	1.412(9)	C(19)-C(20)-C(1)	124.4(3)
C(15)-C(34)	1.505(6)	C(37)-O(1)-C(83)	119.5(5)
C(37)-O(1)	1.407(6)	O(1)-C(83)-O2	123.3(2)

Table 3.2. X-ray crystal structure parameters for **ZnTTPCo**.

parameters	ZnTTPCo
Solvent for crystallization	CHCl ₃ /n-hexane
Formula	C ₁₇₆ H ₁₄₄ Cl ₆ Co ₂ N ₈ O ₄ Zn
Crystal system	triclinic
Space group	<i>P</i> -1 (No. 2)
<i>R</i>	0.0494
w <i>R</i> ₂ (all data)	0.1413
GOF(<i>F</i> ²)	1.020
<i>a</i> [Å]	15.4055(10)
<i>b</i> [Å]	16.4783(10)
<i>c</i> [Å]	18.6577(12)
α [°]	71.699(1)
β [°]	81.681(1)
δ [°]	64.478(1)
<i>V</i> [Å ³]	4057.8(4)
<i>Z</i>	1
<i>T</i> [K]	294(2)
Crystal size [mm ³]	0.12 × 0.08 × 0.05
ρ_{calcd} [g cm ⁻³]	1.185
$2\theta_{\text{min}}, 2\theta_{\text{max}}$ [°]	2.30, 23.33
no. of reflnsmeasd. (unique)	14272
no. of reflnsmeasd. (<i>I</i> > 2σ(<i>I</i>))	10610
no. of params.	805
Δ [e Å ³]	1.970, -1.722
CCDC number	992358

3.3.3 Ground State Properties

Absorption spectra of both free-base dyads and its zinc derivatives measured in dichloromethane solvent. Spectroscopic data which include wavelength of maximum absorbance (λ_{max}), molar extinction coefficients ($\log \epsilon$) of the dyads and their constituent individual components are summarized in Table 3.3. The dyads exhibit characteristic intense Soret band (~ 420 nm), which is an $a_{1u}(\pi)/e_g(\pi^*)$ electronic transition, assigned to the second excited state (*S*₂) and either four (free-base dyads) or two (zinc dyads) Q-bands (500-700 nm) originated from $a_{2u}(\pi)/e_g(\pi^*)$ electronic transition, attributed to the first excited state (*S*₁). From Figure 3.13 and Table 3.3, it indicates that incorporation of metallocene has no significant contribution to the absorption spectra in the spectral region of 400 and 750 nm.

These characteristic bands are similar to many other porphyrin-ferrocene conjugates in which no ground state interactions.³¹ However, a band centered at 270 nm was observed in **H₂TTPCo** and its Zn-complex **Zn-TTPCo**, which probably arise from the π - π^* transition of the substituted phenyl rings on the Cp rings whereas, in ferrocene-linked dyads, no additional bands were observed. Thus, the spectrum of each dyad is more or less similar to the spectrum resulting from a combination (1:1 mole/mole) ratio of either [**H₂TTP**] or [**ZnTTP**] and either [Fer] or [Co] of the corresponding individual precursors.

The cyclic voltammograms of free-base dyads and their Zn-complexes. Table 3.3 summarizes the redox potential data (CH₂Cl₂ and 0.1 M TBAP) of the dyad systems investigated in this study. From the Figure 3.14 and Table 3.3, one can deduce that each new free-base dyad investigated showed two or three oxidation peaks and two reduction peaks. Specifically, the cobaltocene-linked dyad **H₂TTPCo** undergoes three either quasi-reversible

Figure 3.13. UV-vis spectra of dyads in dichloromethane.

Table 3.3. UV-Vis and electrochemical data.

compound	$\lambda_{\text{abs}}/\text{nm}^*$			Redox [†]			
	Soret band (log ϵ , $\text{M}^{-1}\text{cm}^{-1}$)	Q-bands	Ox ₃ (P)	Ox ₂ (P)	Ox ₁ (Cb/Fc)	R ₁ (P)	R ₂ (P)
H₂TTP[†]	419 (5.74)	514 (4.36), 548 (4.06), 590 (3.90), 647 (3.86)	1.30	1.03	-	-1.23	-1.55
H₂TTPCo	420 (5.86)	517 (4.45), 552 (4.21), 593 (4.00), 648 (3.95)	1.35	1.02	0.68 [‡]	-1.34	-1.64
H₂TTPFe	419 (5.86)	517 (4.46), 551 (4.18), 593 (4.04), 648 (3.95)	1.18	0.89	0.86 [‡]	-1.29	-1.56
ZnTTP[†]	420 (5.83)	549 (4.42), 588 (3.78)	-	0.74	-	-1.24	-
ZnTTPCo	420 (5.81)	549 (4.59), 590 (4.23)	-	1.08	0.73 [‡]	-1.46	-1.83
ZnTTPFe	421 (5.85)	549(4.51), 585 (3.95)	-	1.03	0.69 [‡]	-1.48	-1.87

*Solvent: CH₂Cl₂, Error limits: λ_{max} , ± 1 nm, log ϵ , ± 5 . [†]Solvent: CH₂Cl₂, 0.1 M TBAPF₆; Glassy carbon working electrode, Standard calomel is reference electrode (SCE), Platinum is auxiliary electrode. Error limits, $E_{1/2} \pm 0.03$ V, Potential (V) versus SCE, (ΔE_p in mV). [‡]Cb/Fc, cobalt sandwich/ferrocene-centered processes.

or reversible oxidations at 0.86, 1.02 and 1.35 V. The first peak is due to the oxidation of the cobalt sandwich unit. The second and third oxidations observed at +1.02 and 1.35 V belongs to the oxidation of the porphyrin core. Additionally, two porphyrin ring-centered reversible reductions were observed at -1.34 and -1.64 V. Similarly, the ferrocenyl-linked dyad **H₂TTPFe** displayed three either quasi-reversible or reversible oxidations at 0.68, 0.89 and 1.18 V, along with two reversible reductions at -1.29 and -1.56 V respectively. The Zn-complexed dyad, **Zn-TTPCo** showed two quasi-reversible oxidations at 0.73 and 1.08 V. The first oxidation at 0.73 V corresponds to the oxidation of cobaltocene as well as porphyrin macrocycle. Apart from these oxidation peaks, it also showed two reduction waves at -1.46 and -1.83 V of the porphyrin ring. Similarly, the **Zn-TTPFe** displayed two quasi-

Figure 3.14. Cyclic voltammograms of dyads in dichloromethane, with 0.1 M TBAP.

reversible oxidations at 0.69 and 1.03 V, along with two reversible reductions at -1.48 and -1.87 V respectively.

3.3.4 Singlet State Properties

The steady-state fluorescence spectra of all four dyads along with its reference compounds i.e., **H₂TTP** and **ZnTTP** were measured in toluene, dichloromethane and acetonitrile solvents. Figure 3.15 illustrates emission spectra of all four dyads in Dichloromethane solvent. The corresponding wavelength of emission maxima and quantum yields of all four dyads along with its reference compounds are presented in Table 4. As can be seen in Figure 3.15, the spectral shapes and emission maxima is identical in comparison with its reference compounds. Interestingly, the emission intensity of all four dyads quenched when equi-absorbing solutions of dyads were excited at 420 nm (λ_{max} , where porphyrin absorbs predominantly). The possibility of self-aggregation of porphyrins which leads to quenching of fluorescence intensity (as a result of non-radiative path in the excited state) can be ruled out as all experiments were carried out with very dilute solutions (10^{-6} M). The

quenching efficiency was found in the range of 19 to 55% in all investigated solvents. The quenching efficiency is more in ferrocene conjugates than its corresponding cobaltocene conjugates. This is probably due to the more electron releasing nature of ferrocene than its corresponding cobaltocenyl sandwich metallocene.

Various radiative and non-radiative intramolecular processes can be responsible for the excited state decay of all four dyads. Among these, an excitation energy transfer (EET) or photoinduced electron transfer (PET) can be conceived to participate in the quenching of fluorescence emission intensity. In the absence of any appreciable metallocene absorption in the emission wavelength region of porphyrin, one could eliminate energy transfer as a quenching via Förster mechanism. Alternative pathway for emission quenching is the intramolecular PET from the ground state of metallocene to the singlet state of porphyrin. E_{0-0} , energy due to 0-0 electronic transition, of porphyrin moiety of dyads was found to be 1.91 ± 0.05 , 1.91 ± 0.05 , 2.08 ± 0.05 , and 2.09 ± 0.05 eV (estimated from intersecting wavelength of the absorption and emission spectra of porphyrin) for **H₂TTCo**, **H₂TTPFe**, **Zn-TTPCo** and **Zn-TTPFe**, respectively, which is comparable with E_{0-0} value of **H₂TTP** and **Zn-TTP**. The change in free energy due to PET from the ground state of metallocene to excited state of porphyrin can be calculated by using equation (1),

$$\Delta G(^1\text{Por} \leftarrow \text{Met}) = E_{\text{CT}}(\text{Por}^-\text{Met}^+) - E_{0-0}(\text{Por}) \dots\dots\dots (3.1)$$

Por^-Met^+ is the oxidation and reduction potential of dyads in dichloromethane solvent. The calculated free-energy change, ΔG for electron transfer from metallocene entity to the excited state porphyrin is found to be weakly exergonic 0.06, 0.09, 0.29, and 0.1 eV for **H₂TTPFe**, **H₂TTCo**, **Zn-TTPFe**, and **Zn-TTPCo**, respectively. Similar weakly exergonic ΔG values were also observed in other porphyrin-ferrocene conjugates.²³

Fluorescence quantum yields of the dyads and individual constituents have been estimated (Table 4) by comparing the emission curves of reference compounds (*i.e.*, **H₂TTP** or **ZnTTP**, $\phi = 0.13 \pm 0.01$ and 0.036 ± 0.001 , respectively in CH_2Cl_2 solvent) with those of the dyads. It was found that the fluorescence quantum yield (ϕ) of **H₂TTPCo** and **H₂TTPFe**

was 0.09 and 0.065, respectively in CH₂Cl₂ solvent. The fluorescence emission quenching efficiency of dyads were calculated by from eq. (2)

$$Q = \frac{\phi(H_2TTP\text{or}ZnTTP) - \phi(Dyads)}{\phi(H_2TTP\text{or}ZnTTP)} \dots\dots\dots (3.2)$$

Where $\phi(\mathbf{H}_2\mathbf{TTP}$ or \mathbf{ZnTTP}) refer to the fluorescence quantum yields for $\mathbf{H}_2\mathbf{TTP}$ or \mathbf{ZnTTP} and $\phi(\mathbf{Dyads})$ refer to dyads; ($\lambda_{\text{ex}} = 420$ nm). As the static dielectric constant of the solvent is increased, the quenching of fluorescence intensity increased gradually (Table 3.4), indicate the excited state electron transfer mechanism. For example, quenching efficiencies in toluene are less compared to the CH₂Cl₂ and CH₃CN. In general, the PET process is accelerated by polar solvents than the non-polar solvents, so the present results are in consistent with the literature.³³ In all investigated solvents, the efficient quenching of the dyad $\mathbf{H}_2\mathbf{TTPFe}$ relative to that of the $\mathbf{H}_2\mathbf{TTPCo}$ can be directly attributed to the more exothermic value of ΔG_{PET} of $\mathbf{H}_2\mathbf{TTPFe}$. Similar efficient quenching was also observed in their corresponding zinc derivatives.

Further evidence of the intramolecular PET process has been determined by measuring the excited state decay curves. Figure 3.16 illustrates excited state decay curves of four dyads, collected in toluene, CH₂Cl₂, acetonitrile solvents upon excitation at 405 nm and the decay parameters collected in three different solvents are shown in Table 3.4. From the data, it is clear that the fluorescence life-times, τ ($\lambda_{\text{ex}} = 405$ nm and $\lambda_{\text{em}} = 650$ nm) for free-base dyads and ($\lambda_{\text{ex}} = 405$ nm and $\lambda_{\text{em}} = 605$ nm) for zinc dyads are quenched in all solvents when compared to $\mathbf{H}_2\mathbf{TTP/ZnTTP}$. In all investigated solvents, all four dyads decay curves are fitted with a bi-exponential expression except $\mathbf{H}_2\mathbf{TTPCo}$ and major component is having shorter lifetime which is attributed to the deactivation (quenching) of the excited porphyrin by metallocene. The other minor component is assigned to an unquenched decay of porphyrin.

Table 3.4. Fluorescence data and Fluorescence decay parameters.

Dyads	$\lambda_{em}, nm^* (\Phi_F, \% Q)^\dagger$			$\tau, ns (A\%), \lambda_{ex} = 405 nm^\ddagger$		
	$\lambda_{ex} = 420 nm$			Toluene	CH ₂ Cl ₂	CH ₃ CN
H₂TTP	653, 719 (0.11)	653, 719 (0.13)	653, 719 (0.14)	9.6	9.2	9.2
H₂TTPCo	654, 721 (0.073, 33%)	653, 719 (0.09, 31%),	654, 718 (0.09, 36%)	6.4 1.56x10⁸	6.6 1.51x10⁸	6.6 1.51x10⁸
H₂TTPFe	653, 720 (0.056, 49%)	653, 720 (0.065, 50%)	653, 720 (0.063, 55%)	3.4 (66) 5.8 (34) 2.94x10⁸	3.6 (67) 6.1 (33) 2.77x10⁸	3.6 (67) 6.1 (33) 2.77x10⁸
ZnTTP	599, 642 (0.037)	603, 649 0.036	606, 659 0.042	2.07(95) 1.11(5)	1.76(95) 1.17(5)	1.72(89) 2.86(11)
Zn-TTPCo	605, 656 (0.030, 19%)	598, 648 (0.024, 33%)	606, 658 (0.026, 38%)	0.9 (63) 1.6 (37) 1.11x10⁹	1.1 (77) 2.1 (23) 9.09x10⁸	1.1 (88) 2.4 (12) 9.01x10⁸
Zn-TTPFe	606, 656 (0.027, 27%)	598, 649 (0.023, 36%)	598, 648 (0.021, 50%)	1.0 (90) 3.4 (10) 9.99x10⁸	1.0 (83) 2.7 (17) 9.99x10⁸	1.1 (83) 2.7 (17) 9.09x10⁸

Values in parenthesis are relative amplitude of corresponding decay component. *Error limits: λ_{ex} , $\pm 2 nm$, $\Phi \pm 10\%$. $\dagger Q$ is defined in Eq. 2 (see text). \ddagger All lifetimes are in nanoseconds (ns), Error limits of $\tau \sim 10\%$. Bold value denotes rate constant in s^{-1} .

Further, rate constant (k_{ET}) for the charge transfer state $Por^{\cdot-}Met^{+}$ has been calculated using eq (3) and summarized in Table 3.4.

$$k_{ET} = (1/\tau_f) - k_{\dots} \dots \dots \dots \quad (3.3)$$

Figure 3.15. Fluorescence spectra of free-base dyads and zinc dyads in investigated solvents, at $\lambda_{\text{ex}} \sim 440$ nm.

Where k is the reciprocal of the lifetime of the $\text{H}_2\text{TTP}/\text{ZnTTP}$, τ_f is the lifetime of H_2TTPCo or $\text{H}_2\text{TTPFe}/\text{Zn-TTPCo}$ or Zn-TTPFe . The solvent-dependent k_{ET} values are in the range of 1.51×10^8 to $1.11 \times 10^9 \text{ s}^{-1}$. The observed general increase of the k_{ET} values with increasing polarity of the solvent is consistent with the participation of a charge transfer state

Figure 3.16. Fluorescence decay for dyads ($\lambda_{\text{ex}} = 405 \text{ nm}$, $\lambda_{\text{em}} = 650 \text{ nm}$) in investigated solvents.

in the excited state deactivation of the porphyrin component of these D-A systems. Overall, the photoinduced reactions are influenced by the nature of the metallocene that are connected to porphyrin macrocycle. Both in steady-state and excited state lifetime, the quenching was more for ferrocene derivatives than their corresponding cobaltocene derivatives. This might be due to the more electron releasing nature of ferrocene than the cobaltocenylmetallocene and this is reflected in electrochemical studies (Table 3.3). This type of comparison of photophysical process of porphyrin-metallocene systems are first time to the best of our knowledge.

3.4 Conclusion

In conclusion, we have designed, synthesized, and photophysical studies of porphyrin-metallocene donor-acceptor systems. All dyads are characterized by various spectroscopic and electrochemical methods. The ground state properties indicates that there exists minimum interactions between porphyrin macrocycle and metallocene. X-ray single crystal analysis of **ZnTTPCo** showed that it exists in dimeric form. Steady-state and time-resolved fluorescence experiments reveal that intramolecular PET is taking place from the excited porphyrin to the metallocene. The electron transfer rates are found in the 1.51×10^8 to $1.11 \times 10^9 \text{ s}^{-1}$ and are solvent dependent. We observed long-lived charge separated state in ferrocene derivatives than its corresponding cobaltocene derivatives

3.5 References

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Chapter-4

Synthesis, characterization and photophysical properties of ferrocenyl and mixed sandwich cobaltocenyl ester linked meso- triaryl corrole dyads

4.1 Introduction

In the previous chapter, we have designed and studied porphyrin based D-A systems in which metallocenes (ferrocene and cobaltocene) at *meso* phenyl position with ester link. The detailed photophysical properties of these dyads were investigated. In order to further understand about the long-lived charge separated states, we have extended similar design concept to other members of tetrapyrrolic family such as corroles in the present chapter. We have used 10-(4-Hydroxyphenyl)-5,15-bis-(pentafluorophenyl) corrole as main scaffold with metallocenes linked at *meso* phenyl position with ester bridge and studied their computational studies, electrochemical, photophysical properties and excited state dynamics.

Corroles are tribasic macrocycle closely related to porphyrins, and are widely studied due to its unique photo and electrochemical properties. They are promising candidates for panchromatic dyes due to their intense absorption in the visible range, high fluorescent quantum yields and can perform as donor as well as acceptor depending on the nature of the substituent to construct efficient donor– acceptor type conjugated (D–A) systems. Reports on photoactive arrays based on corroles are very few in number compared to analogous porphyrin systems.^{1,2} Donor–acceptor (D-A) systems based on corroles have been reported either by using peripheral (*meso* phenyl or β -pyrrole) positions or axial position/s of the resident metal ion of corrole macrocycle.³ Of these D-A systems, we are particularly interested in peripherally substituted corrole–metallocene dyad systems. Ferrocene is a widely accepted metallocene with strong electron donating ability and rich electrochemistry.^{4,5} Recently, our group have designed corrole based D-A systems in which ferrocene connected at its β -pyrrole position *via* vinylene spacer and studied in detail the electron transfer properties.⁶ Substitution at *meso* phenyl positions of corroles have not been well studied with metallocenes. Recently Paolosse and co-workers have reported ferrocene substituted at all of the *meso* phenyl positions of triphenylcorrole.⁷ Gryko et al. have reported a triad system in which a ferrocene directly connected at its *meso* phenyl position of corrole and porphyrin.⁸ Ground state properties suggests that the lack of electronic interactions between ferrocene and porphyrinoids. Although these compounds are structurally characterized and studied the electrochemical properties, no systematic photophysical investigations have been carried out on these systems. In previous chapter, cobaltocene-

porphyrin and ferrocene-porphyrin systems have been discussed and observed electron transfer from the metallocenes to the porphyrin core.⁹ Herein, we have synthesized corrole based D–A dyad systems with ferrocene and cobaltocene substituents at the *meso* phenyl position of the corrole macrocycle. To the best of our knowledge, this is the first report on corrole-cobaltocene D-A systems. We have chosen cobaltocene due to its high stability and electron donor capability. The synthesized corrole-metallocenes D-A systems were characterized by various spectroscopic techniques. Photophysical and electrochemical properties revealed that the metallocenes serves as good electron donors to the corrole moiety. However transient absorption studies suggest that the quenching of emission intensity in these dyad systems could be due to heavy atom effect.

Figure 4.1. Molecular structures of **Ph-corrole**, **Dyad-1** and **Dyad-2**.

4.2 Experimental section

Dipyrromethane (DPM), 10-(4-Hydroxyphenyl)-5,15-bis-(pentafluorophenyl)corrole (Ph-Corr), ferrocene carboxylic acid and η^5 -[C₅H₄(COOH)]Co(η^4 -C₄Ph₄) were synthesized according to the reported procedures.^{11,12}

4.2.1 Synthesis of Corrole-Ferrocene (Dyad 1)

Dyad 1 was synthesized according to the previously reported literature procedures [42]. 10-(4-hydroxyphenyl)-5,15-bis-(pentafluorophenyl)corrole (0.04 g, 0.05 mmol) and ferrocenecarboxylic acid (0.013 g, 0.05 mmol) were dissolved in 12 mL of dry

dichloromethane. To this catalytic amount of DMAP was added under the inert atmosphere, followed by the addition of 1.0 M solution of DCC (0.8 mL, 0.54 mmol) in dichloromethane. The reaction mixture was stirred at room temperature for 4–5 h and the reaction was monitored by TLC. The solvent was removed under vacuum and the residue was purified by using silica gel column chromatography with hexane/dichloromethane (6:4 v/v) gave desired product **Dyad 1** (Yield: 50%). ^1H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl_3): δ 9.12 (d, $J = 4.2$ Hz, 2H), 8.74 (dt, $J = 14.5, 7.3$ Hz, 4H), 8.58 (d, $J = 4.1$ Hz, 2H), 8.23 (d, $J = 8.3$ Hz, 2H), 7.59 (t, $J = 10.6$ Hz, 2H), 5.14 – 5.08 (m, 2H), 4.61 – 4.56 (m, 2H), 4.44 – 4.38 (m, 5H). MALDI-TOF MS: 935.05.

4.2.2 Synthesis of Corrole-Cobaltocene (Dyad 2)

The compound was synthesized by adopting similar procedure for the synthesis of dyad **1** with yield of 40%. ^1H NMR (500 MHz, CDCl_3): δ 9.11 (d, $J = 4.1$ Hz, 2H), 8.74 (d, $J = 4.3$ Hz, 4H), 8.58 (s, 2H), 8.03 (d, $J = 8.1$ Hz, 2H), 7.57 (d, $J = 6.9$ Hz, 8H), 7.30 (dd, $J = 15.7, 8.2$ Hz, 12H), 6.93 (d, $J = 8.1$ Hz, 2H), 5.51 (s, 2H), 4.95 (d, $J = 16.4$ Hz, 2H). MALDI-TOF MS: 1229.14.

Figure 4.2. ^1H NMR spectroscopy of **Dyad 1**.

Figure 4.3. MALDI-TOF spectrometry of Dyad 1.

Figure 4.4. ^1H NMR spectroscopy of Dyad 2.

Figure 4.5. MALDI-TOF spectrometry of **Dyad 2**.

4.3. Result and discussion

4.3.1. Synthesis and structure characterization

The synthetic procedure for the dyads is outlined in Scheme 4.1. The dyads were synthesized by a one-step esterification reaction of 10-(4-Hydroxyphenyl)-5,15-bis-(pentafluorophenyl) corrole with the corresponding metallocenecarboxylic acid in the presence of 4-(dimethylamino) pyridine and DCC at room temperature. Finally the dyads were obtained by column purification followed by recrystallization from hexane/DCM solvent mixture and characterized by ^1H NMR, MALDI-TOF and UV-visible spectroscopic methods. The presence of molecular ion peak in the MS spectra of both the compounds confirms the formation of corrole-metallocene dyad systems (Figure 4.3 and 4.5). The dyads further confirmed from the ^1H NMR analysis. Figures 4.2 and 4.4 illustrates the ^1H NMR spectra of **Dyad 1** and **Dyad 2**. In **Dyad 1** the cyclopentadiene protons shifted downfield compared to the protons in ferrocene carboxylic acid. Similarly for **Dyad 2** the cyclopentadiene protons and phenyl protons have shifted downfield compared to the

corresponding cobaltocene carboxylic acid.⁹ Both the dyads show corrole pyrrolic protons around 8-9 ppm.

Scheme 4.1. Synthetic scheme of corrole-metallocene dyads (**Dyad-1** and **Dyad-2**).

4.3.2. UV-visible absorption studies

The optical absorption spectra of the dyads and its parent compound **Ph-Corr** were performed in dichloromethane solution at room temperature and are displayed in Figure 4.6. The wavelength of absorption maxima (λ_{max}) and logarithmic of molar extinction coefficients (ϵ) are listed in Table 4.1. In general, corroles have an intense Soret band at 416 nm, arise due to π - π^* electronic transition from ground state to the second excited state (S_2) and three less intense Q-bands in 500-700 nm, originated from π - π^* electronic transitions, attributed to the first excited state (S_1). A broad band at 300 nm is observed in **Dyad 2** system which arise from the π - π^* transition of the phenyl group present on the cyclobutadiene ring of cobaltocene sandwich unit. Similar bands are not observed in the case of **Dyad 1**. A slight broadening and splitting of Soret band can be observed in both the dyads compared to the

pristine Ph-corr, indicating a weak ground state interaction between the corrole unit and metallocenes part in these D-A systems.

Figure 4.6. Absorption spectra of **Ph-corr**, **Dyad 1** and **Dyad 2** in dichloromethane solvent.

Table 4.1. UV–vis and electrochemical data.

Compounds	Absorption, λ_{\max} , nm ($\log(\epsilon)$, $M^{-1} \text{cm}^{-1}$) ^a		Redox Potential (V) vs. SCE ^b	
	Soret band	Q- bands	Oxidation	Reduction
Ph-corr	411 (5.51)	564 (4.69), 612 (4.46), 637 (4.23)	0.68, 0.93, 1.35	-1.08, -1.70
Dyad 1	410 (5.51)	563 (4.70), 612 (4.47), 638 (4.24)	0.64, 0.77, 0.92, 1.33	-1.07, -1.68
Dyad 2	410 (5.50)	563 (4.69), 612 (4.48), 638 (4.27)	0.68, 0.92, 1.11	-1.10, -1.68

^aSolvent CH_2Cl_2 , Error limits: λ_{\max} , ± 1 nm, $\log \epsilon$, $\pm 10\%$. ^b CH_2Cl_2 , 0.1 M TBAP; Glassy carbon working electrode, Standar calomel electrode is reference electrode, Pt electrode is auxillary electrode. Error limits, $E_{1/2} \pm 0.03$ V.

4.3.3 Electrochemical studies

The electrochemical properties of the newly synthesized dyads were investigated by cyclic voltammetry and differential pulse voltammetric techniques. Figure 4.7 shows the DPV of **Ph-corr**, **Dyad 1** and **Dyad 2**, while the corresponding redox potentials are presented in Table 4.1. CVs of the compounds are shown in Figure 4.8. Under the experimental conditions employed, each corrole unit exhibited two to three oxidations and two reductions. The first reduction peak of both dyads is a purely corrole reduction as we did not observe any reduction of the metallocenes under our experimental conditions. The first oxidation of **Dyad 1** *i.e.* at 0.77 V belongs to the ferrocene unit in **Dyad 1**. On the other hand, the first oxidation peak at 0.92 V belongs to both oxidation of both the corrole macrocycle and the cobaltocene sandwich unit. However, only the first oxidation of the metallocene and the first reduction of the corrole are considered to evaluate the probable free-energy change which could be associated with photoinduced electron transfer in the dyads and is listed in Table 4.1. The experimental HOMO–LUMO gap (potential difference between the first oxidation and the first reduction) was found to be in agreement with theoretical value and suggest no ground state electronic interactions in these dyads.

Figure 4.7. Differential pulse voltammograms for **Ph-Corr**, **Dyad 1** and **Dyad 2** in dichloromethane solvent.

Figure 4.8. Cyclic voltammograms of the indicated compounds in dichloromethane with 0.1M TBAP.

4.3.4 Computational Studies

To gain an insight into the structural, electronic and optical properties of the dyads, DFT and TD-DFT calculations with a functional basis set of the DFT/631G (d, p) level were performed. Figure 4.9 shows the ground state optimized structures of both the dyads, which comprises donor corresponding metallocene and acceptor corrole macrocycle separating the ester linkage that keeps both dyads in one plane. The frontier molecular HOMO and LUMO levels orbital diagrams (Figure 4.10) and the molecular electrostatic potential (MEP) maps for the compounds are given in Figure. 4.9. The optimized structural parameters and the orbital energies are summarized in Table 4.2. In both the dyads, the electron density distribution of HOMO and LUMO is occupied only on corrole macrocycle. The estimated edge to edge distance, R_{e-e} from the corrole ring to the nearest carbon of the metallocene for **Dyad 1** was found to be 2.42 Å, while the center to centre, R_{c-c} between them was estimated to be 11.22 Å. In case of **Dyad 2** the values are found to be 2.40 Å and 11.34 Å. The energies of HOMO and LUMO for the dyads 1 and 2 were found to be 5.07 eV and 5.11 eV and 2.58 eV and 2.55eV respectively.

Figure 4.9. (a) Electrostatic potential maps (esp) for **Dyad 1** and **Dyad 2**. (b) Frontier molecular orbital energy levels and energy gap.

Table 4.2. B3LYP/6-31G(d,p)-optimized structural parameters and related orbital energies of the investigated dyads.

Compounds	E, Kcal/mol ⁻¹	R _{e-e}	R _{c-c}	HOMO	LUMO	HL
Dyad 1	2.80 × 10 ⁶	2.42	11.67	5.07	2.58	2.49
Dyad 2	3.43 × 10 ⁶	2.40	11.72	5.11	2.55	2.56

Figure 4.10. HOMO-1, HOMO-2, HOMO-3, LUMO+1, LUMO+2 and LUMO+3 for (a) **dyad 1** and (b) **dyad 2**, calculated at the B3LYP/6-31G(d,p) level in dichloromethane.

4.3.5 Steady-state Emission

The steady-state emission spectra of both the dyads along with their parent compound Ph-corr were measured in toluene, *O*-dichlorobenzene, CH₂Cl₂ and CH₃CN solvents. Figure 4.12 illustrates emission spectra of both the dyads in all four investigated solvents. The corresponding wavelength of emission maxima (λ_{max}) and quantum yields (ϕ) are presented in Table 3. As can be seen in Figure 4.11, the spectral shapes and emission maxima is identical in comparison with its parent compound. However, the quantum yields are quenched, when equi-absorbing solutions of dyads excited at 410 nm (λ_{max} , where corrole absorbs predominantly). The quenching efficiency was found in the range of 5–33% in all investigated solvents. Table 4.3 suggests that the quenching is more in ferrocene dyad, when compared to cobaltocene dyad and it may be due to more electron releasing nature of ferrocene.

The quenching of fluorescence emission intensity can primarily be due to either intramolecular excitation energy transfer (EET) or photoinduced electron transfer (PET). Lack of absorption of metallocene in the emission wavelength region of corrole could rule out the possibility of energy transfer *via* Forster mechanism. An alternative pathway for emission quenching is the intramolecular PET from the ground state of the metallocene donor to the singlet state of the corrole acceptor. The E_{0-0} (0–0 spectroscopic transition energy) values of the corrole part of the dyads, 1.91 ± 0.05 eV, as estimated from overlap of their absorption and emission spectra were found to be in the same range as the E_{0-0} values of their parent compound Ph-corr. The change in free energy for PET from the metallocene to the corrole can be calculated using the following equation (1).

$$\Delta G(^1\text{Cor} \leftarrow \text{Met}) = E_{\text{CT}}(\text{Cor}^-\text{Met}^+) - E_{0-0}(\text{Cor}) \dots \dots \dots (4.1)$$

Where Cor^-Met^+ is the oxidation and reduction potential of dyads in dichloromethane. The calculated free-energy change ΔG for electron transfer from metallocene to the excited state of the corrole was found to be -0.06 for **Dyad 1** and weakly exergonic -0.01 eV for **Dyad 2**,

when excited at 416 nm. Similar weakly exergonic ΔG values were also observed in porphyrin-cobaltocene conjugates, and emission quenching was observed in polar solvents.⁹

Figure 4.11. Fluorescence spectra of equiabsorbing solutions of **Ph-Corr**, **Dyad 1** and **Dyad 2** in (a) Toluene (b) ODCB (c) Dichloromethane and (d) Acetonitrile (OD, $\lambda_{\text{ex}} = 0.1$), $\lambda_{\text{ex}} = 410$ nm.

Fluorescence quantum yields of the dyads and their parent compound have been estimated (Table 4.3) by comparing the emission curves of reference compound (*i.e.* 5,10,15-tris(pentafluorophenyl)corrole, $\phi = 0.14 \pm 0.01$ in CH_2Cl_2 solvent) with that of dyads.¹⁰ The fluorescence quantum yields of **Dyad 1** and **Dyad 2** were found to be 0.10 and 0.12, respectively, in dichloromethane solvent. The quenching efficiency values (Q) can be estimated from equation (2).

$$Q = \frac{\phi(\text{Ph-Corr}) - \phi[\text{Dyad1}] \text{ or } [\text{Dyad2}]}{\phi(\text{Ph-Corr})} \dots\dots\dots (4.2)$$

Table 4.3. Fluorescence data

$\lambda_{\text{exc}} = 410 \text{ nm}, \lambda_{\text{em}}, (\phi, Q\%)^{\text{a}}$				
Compound	Toluene	ODCB	CH_2Cl_2	CH_3CN
Pristine	657 (0.16)	657 (0.19)	657 (0.15)	633 (0.33)
Dyad 1	658 (0.15, 6)	656 (0.16, 6)	657 (0.10, 33)	632(0.26, 18)
Dyad 2	660 (0.16, ~1)	656 (0.18, 5)	657 (0.12, 20)	633 (0.25, 21)

^aError limits: $\lambda_{\text{ex}}, \pm 2 \text{ nm}, \phi \pm 10\%$. ^b Q is defined in equation 1 (see text).

Figure 4.12. Fluorescence decay curve for **Ph-Corr**, **Dyad 1** and **Dyad 2** in investigated solvents ($\lambda_{\text{exc}} = 405 \text{ nm}, \lambda_{\text{em}} = 650 \text{ nm}$).

Where ϕ (**Ph-Corr**) and ϕ (**Dyad 1/Dyad 2**) refer to the fluorescence quantum yields of Ph-Corr and the dyads respectively; ($\lambda_{\text{ex}} = 410 \text{ nm}$). When the static dielectric constant of the solvents increases, the extent of quenching increases, indicating the probable electron

transfer pathway to be operative to depopulate the excited state of corrole. The quenching efficiencies are found to be smaller in non-polar solvents, toluene and *O*-dichlorobenzene. In general, the photoinduced electron transfer process is more favorable in polar solvents than in non-polar solvents, and the present results are consistent with the values in literature.¹³

Figure 4.12 illustrates the decay curves of both dyads and their parent compound measured in acetonitrile solvent at the excitation wavelength 405 nm. The lifetimes of both dyads were measured in all four investigated solvents and the corresponding data are given in Table 4.4. The fluorescent lifetimes of the dyads ($\lambda_{\text{ex}} = 405$ nm and $\lambda_{\text{em}} = 650$ nm) were found to be quenched when compared to the monomer phenyl corrole ($\lambda_{\text{ex}} = 405$ nm and $\lambda_{\text{em}} = 650$ nm) in all the investigated solvents, and the quenching is stronger in the polar solvents acetonitrile and dichloromethane. It is clear from the lifetime values shown in Table 4.4 that quenching is weaker in nonpolar solvents toluene and ODCB.

Table 4.4. Fluorescence decay parameters[†] and electron transfer rate constants (k_{ET} , S^{-1}).[‡]

Compound	$(\tau, \text{ns (A\%)}, k_{\text{ET}}, \text{s}^{-1})$			
	Toluene	ODCB	CH_2Cl_2	CH_3CN
Ph-Corr	4.16	4.13	3.98	3.88
Dyad 1	3.42(99)	3.26(95)	3.20(97)	2.66(97)
	3.35(1)	10.4(5)	2.33(2)	10.7(3)
	2.9×10^8	3.1×10^8	3.1×10^8	3.8×10^8
Dyad 2	3.76(98)	3.74(93)	3.61(100)	2.96 (94)
	10.7(2)	10.2(7)	2.8×10^8	6.13 (6)
	2.7×10^8	2.7×10^8		3.4×10^8

[†] All lifetimes are in nanoseconds (ns). [‡] Error limits of τ and $k_{\text{ET}} \sim 10\%$. Values in parenthesis are relative amplitude of corresponding decay component

4.3.6 Transient absorption studies

In order to understand the PET dynamic between metallocene and the corrole macrocycle, if any, and the relaxation dynamics of the prepared Dyads along with their parent compound Ph-Corr were studied by femtosecond transient absorption (TA) spectroscopic technique upon Soret band excitation at 400 nm in ACN solvent. A comparative analysis of transient data of **Dyad 1** and **Dyad 2** was done with the parent Ph-

Corr molecule. Figure 4.13 shows the profile picture of TA absorption of Ph- Corr and **Dyad 1** in ACN which includes a ΔOD heat map along with the TA absorption spectra at different delay times and time traces at different wavelengths. No remarkable change in the pattern and time evolution of TA was observed among Ph-Corr, **Dyad 1** and **Dyad 2** (profile picture of **Dyad 2** in Fig. 4.14). In all cases, upon excitation at 400 nm a prompt rise of negative signals to the region of ground state absorption were observed along with strong positive signals at 450 nm region and a relatively weak positive signal at 590 nm. These negative signals are well known and are assigned to be ground state photobleaching (GSB) and stimulated emission (SE) from $S_2 \rightarrow S_0$ if any, and observed positive signals are the photoinduced excited state absorption (ESA) which can be the sum of $S_2 \rightarrow S_n$, $Q_y \rightarrow S_n$, $Q_x \rightarrow S_n$ and $T_1 \rightarrow T_n$ transitions. The ground state photobleaching recovery dynamics and excited state absorption dynamics are exactly similar. Spectrally similar states are observed for all the cases.

Figure 4.13. ΔOD heat maps as a function of probe wavelength (vertical) and probe delay (horizontal) for Ph-Corr (a) and **Dyad 1**(d) in ACN; excitation at 400 nm. As indicated in the color map, the zero level is colored in yellow, red indicates positive signals (*i.e.* excited state absorption, ESA), and green/blue denote negative signals (*i.e.* decrease in absorption due to stimulated emission and/or ground state photobleaching). Transient spectra at selected delays are shown for Ph-Corr (b) and **Dyad 1** (e) Time traces at selected probe wavelengths for Ph-Corr (c) and **Dyad 1** (f).

Transient absorption data for all the three compounds was analyzed globally by a simple four component model. Figure 4.15a portrays the compartmental-based target model

used for analysis of observed TA data upon 400 nm excitation by using the four components that were necessary to adequately fit the data. S_2 , Q_x , Q_y and T_1 are the probable species associated difference spectra (SADS) related with Ph-Corr, **Dyad 1** and **Dyad 2**. The transition from S_2 state to ground state (S_0), internal conversion (IC) from $S_2 \rightarrow Q_y$, transition from $Q_y \rightarrow S_0$, intersystem crossing (ISC) from $Q_x \rightarrow T_1$, transition from $Q_x \rightarrow S_0$ along with $Q_x \rightarrow T_1$ are considered to be the major processes following excitation. No additional transition could be associated with **Dyad 1** or **Dyad 2**. The TA data were collected up to a 2.5 ns time window since the exact lifetime of T_1 state cannot be estimated precisely from this data set. Hence, in global and target analysis lifetime of T_1 was kept as constrained to 1–2 μ s.

Based on this model, the data of all compounds were fitted convincingly well and the spectra of the components as well as the lifetimes of the associated states were thus determined and listed in the model. The estimated species associated difference spectra and population time profiles are shown in Figs 4.15b and 4.15c, respectively, for Ph-corr and **Dyad 1** (and for **Dyad 2** in Figure 4.14). The first SADS₁ can be identified as the S_2 state, with a GSB at ~425 nm and a weak SE peak at 440 nm corresponding to S_2 emission. It is clearly different than that of other states, and the lifetime (τ_1) of this state was found to be 18 ± 50 fs for all compounds. The SADS₂ and SADS₃ represent Q_y and hot Q_x state with an excited state absorption (ESA) peak at ~450 nm and GSB corresponding to the ground state absorption peaks pertaining to Q_y and Q_x . The lifetime (τ_2) of the Q_y state is calculated to be 182 ± 2 ps. SADS₃ represents the thermally relaxed Q_x state and it undergoes a tiny blue shift of ESA with respect to SADS₂. Finally the Q_x state decays to the ground state by radiative pathways as well as to the lowest triplet state T_1 *via* ISC, a long-lived component. The lifetimes of the Q_x state are found to be 4, 3 and 3.5 ns for **Ph-Corr**, **Dyad 1** and **Dyad 2** respectively, which are very close to the values observed by the TCSPC experiment. SADS₄ can be recognized as T_1 state with an ESA peak at ~450 nm, and it becomes narrower than SADS₃ associated with singlet states with almost no positive signal above 500 nm. Interestingly, a noticeable change in intersystem crossing rates was found to increasing upon going from Ph-Corr to **Dyad 2**, and the corresponding rate constants are shown in Figure 4.15. The 70% Q_x population was found to participate in ISC populating the lowest triplet state in **Ph-Corr**, where as 90% and 80% Q_x population was transferred to the lowest triplet

state in **Dyad 1** and **Dyad 2**, respectively. This observation could predict that attachment of ferrocene and cobaltocene to the corrole macrocycle could lead to an enhancement of the intersystem crossing rate, resulting in a slight decrease in singlet state (Q_x) lifetime. No transient spectral or dynamic signature of ferrocene/cobaltocene cation and corrole anion was observed which could certainly establish photoinduced reductive electron transfer from the ferrocene/cobaltocene moiety to the corrole macrocycle. Hence, the possibility of the PET process leading to fluorescence quenching is ruled out.

Figure 4.14. ΔOD heat maps as a function of probe wavelength (vertical) and probe delay (horizontal) for **Dyad 2** (a) in ACN; excitation at 400 nm. As indicated in the color map, the zero level is colored in yellow, red indicates positive signals (i.e., excited state absorption, ESA), and green/blue denote negative signals (i.e., decrease in absorption due to stimulated emission and/or ground-state photobleaching). Transient spectra at selected delays (b) and time traces at selected probe wavelengths (c).

It can be also noted here that the quenching pathway in the corrole-ferrocene D–A system,⁶ where ferrocene moiety was attached by using vinylic spacer at β -pyrrole position

of corrole, showed photoinduced electron transfer (PET) from ferrocene to corrole moiety. It was further noted that the ΔG value for that system⁶ was found to be one order higher (-0.6 eV) than the present dyad systems. Although the present dyad systems have slightly favorable free energy for PET, they may not be kinetically sufficient to favor the PET process. Hence observed fluorescence quenching in the present dyad systems predominantly could be due to enhancement of intersystem crossing rate in the presence of relatively heavy atoms in the vicinity of the corrole macrocycle.

Figure 4.15. (a) Compartmental model (kinetic Scheme) used for target analysis of the 400 nm excitation data. The estimated rate constants (in 1/fs, 1/ps, 1/ns and 1/ms) are indicated in the figure; percentage of population transfer to the subsequent states are shown in parenthesis, the global lifetimes of the respective states are shown for all the studied compounds. P stand for **Ph-Corr**, D1 stands for **Dyad 1**, D2 stands for **Dyad 2**. (b) The population profiles and estimated SADS for Ph-Corr. (c) The population profiles and estimated SADS for **Dyad 1**.

4.4 Conclusion

In conclusion, we have designed, synthesized and conducted photophysical studies of corrole-metallocene donor-acceptor systems in which a donor metallocene connected at its *meso*-phenyl position of acceptor corrole by using ester linkage. Both the dyads are characterized by various spectroscopic techniques including transient absorption spectroscopy. The ground-state properties suggests that there exists ground state interactions between metallocene and corrole macrocycle. DFT studies suggest that both HOMO and LUMO resides on corrole macrocycle. Quenched emission is observed in polar solvents when excited at corrole absorption in both the dyads. The transient absorption studies reveal that the quenching of emission is predominantly due to the heavy atom effect in both the dyads.

4.5 References

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Chapter-5

*Axially substituted phosphorous(V)
corrole with polycyclic aromatic
hydrocarbons: Synthesis, X-ray
structure, and photoinduced energy and
electron transfer studies*

5.1 Introduction

In the previous chapters Chapter 3&4, we have studied peripheral positions of either porphyrin or corrole for construction of D-A systems and we have demonstrated the modulation of electrochemical and photophysical properties. In the present chapter, we have utilized axial positions of a P(V) corrole in the construction of D-A systems. This approach is facile, modular, by conducting hydroxyl condensation at axial positions of a metalloid corrole to avoid tedious synthetic protocols. The ‘axial bonding’ concept is relatively unexplored, when compared to porphyrin axial chemistry.

As already discussed in the previous chapter, corroles show excellent photophysical and electrochemical properties. These properties open up the potential for using corroles in many other applications, including diverse areas such as photochemical sensors,¹ artificial photosynthesis² and biomedical applications³ during the last two decades. There is a rich literature on corrole-based D-A assemblies as models for artificial photosynthetic systems.⁴ Efficient D-A systems were constructed by attaching electron acceptors and donors either axially or equatorially to the corrole macrocycle. Our group⁵⁻¹⁰ and many others^{11,12} have investigated energy and electron transfer phenomena in systems containing corroles covalently linked with chromophores such as pyrene, fullerenes, anthraquinone, porphyrins, perylenebisimides etc. Most of these D-A systems possessed substituents at the periphery of the corrole macrocycle. However, a few D-A systems in which the substituents are linked axially *via* the resident metal/metalloid atom of corrole macrocycle.⁸ The natural photosynthetic process has inspired the axial bonding concept where electron transfer is mediated through axially linked aminoacids.^{13,14} It should be noted that such an arrangement in artificial complexes have some added advantages related to the spatial separation of the substituents as they are placed on the opposite faces of the corrole ring and the aggregate formation would be hindered, a widespread problem with synthetic model compounds. In recent years, several corrole complexes with main group element (Al(III), Sn(IV), Ge(IV), Ga(III), Al(III) and P(V))¹⁵ have been reported and showed that these complexes exhibit good photophysical properties. In this respect, P(V) are unique as they can form stable complexes with corroles exhibiting high fluorescent intensity and quantum yields and its two axial coordination sites can be used to fine tune the photophysical and electrochemical properties.¹⁶⁻¹⁷ This has been explored in the present study by axially linking 5,10,15-

tris(pentafluorophenyl)corroleP(V), **P(tpfc)(OH)₂** with polyaromatic hydrocarbons (PAH), *i.e.*, naphthalene or pyrene to form a new series of donor-acceptor triads (Figure 5.1). The naphthyl-corrole triad was structurally characterized by single crystal X-ray diffraction. In the newly synthesized triads, naphthalene and pyrene have been employed to probe the energy/electron donating capability. Careful examination of the photophysical and electrochemical studies revealed that naphthalene serves as energy donor and pyrene as both energy and electron donor in the newly designed corrole PAH donor-acceptor systems.

Figure 5.1. Molecular structures of **P(tpfc)(OH)₂**, **Triad1** and **Triad2**.

5.2 Experimental Section

The synthesis of dipyrromethane (DPM), 5,10,15-tris(pentafluorophenyl) corrole (tpfc) and phosphorous complex of tpfc (**P(tpfc)(OH)₂**) have been reported elsewhere.¹⁶⁻²⁰

5.2.1 Synthesis of Bis(2-naphthoxy)phosphorus(V)- tris 5,10,15-(pentafluorophenyl) corrole. (Triad 1)

P(tpfc)(OH)₂ (0.05 g, 0.0582 mmol) and β -naphthol (0.017 g, 0.116 mmol) were dissolved in 25 ml of dry toluene and refluxed at 110 °C for 12 h under nitrogen atmosphere. The solvent was removed under vacuum and the resulting mixture was purified by column chromatography (100-200 silica gel, hexane/ dichloromethane) to get the titled product in 50% yield. ¹H NMR (500 MHz, CDCl₃): δ (ppm) δ 9.35 (dt,

2H, $J = 7.0, 3.5$ Hz), 8.90 (dt, 4H, $J = 8.0, 4.3$ Hz), 8.79 – 8.76 (m, 2H), 7.05 (dd, 2H, $J = 7.5, 4.9$ Hz), 6.96 – 6.93 (m, 4H), 6.60 – 6.56 (m, 2H), 6.17 (d, 2H, $J = 8.7$ Hz), 2.29 (dd, 2H, $J = 4.9, 2.2$ Hz), 2.09 (dt, 2H, $J = 8.9, 2.2$ Hz). HRMS, $m/z = 1133.11$ [M + Na]⁺.

5.2.2 Synthesis of Bis(1-pyrenoxy)phosphorus(V)- tris 5,10,15-(pentafluorophenyl) corrole. (Triad 2)

P(tpfc)(OH)₂ (0.05 g, 0.0582 mmol) and pyrene-1-ol (0.025 g, 0.116 mmol) were dissolved in 25 ml of dry toluene and refluxed at 110 °C for 12 h and the solvent was removed under vacuum. Work up and purification was done in a similar manner to get the desired product in 30% yield. ¹H NMR (500 MHz, CDCl₃): δ (ppm) δ 9.03 (dd, 4H, $J = 4.5, 3.0$ Hz), 8.94 – 8.91 (m, 2H), 8.78 (t, 2H, $J = 4.0$ Hz), 7.79 – 7.76 (m, 2H), 7.71 – 7.67 (m, 4H), 7.51 (d, 2H, $J = 9.0$ Hz), 7.29 (d, 2H, $J = 8.8$ Hz), 6.88 (d, 2H, $J = 9.2$ Hz), 6.53 (d, 2H, $J = 8.0$ Hz), 2.80 (d, 2H, $J = 9.2$ Hz), 2.01 (dd, 2H, $J = 8.4, 3.1$ Hz). HRMS, $m/z = 1281.14$ [M + Na]⁺.

Figure 5.2. ¹H NMR spectroscopy of **Triad 1** in CDCl₃.

Figure 5.3. HRMS-mass of Triad 1.

Figure 5.4. ^1H NMR spectroscopy of Triad 2 in CDCl_3 .

Figure 5.5. HRMS-mass of Triad 2.

Figure 5.6. ^{31}P NMR spectroscopy of $\text{P}(\text{tpfc})(\text{OH})_2$, Triad1 and Triad2 in CDCl_3 .

5.3 Results and discussion

5.3.1 Synthesis and Characterization

5,10,15-tris(pentafluorophenyl)corrole (H_3tpfc) and its phosphorous complex, $P(tpfc)(OH)_2$ were synthesized according to previously reported literature.²⁰ The insertion of phosphorous into the corrole cavity has been carried out by refluxing H_3tpfc with $POCl_3$ in pyridine as per the earlier report.^{16,17} The formation of the phosphorous corrole can be confirmed by the change of color green to purple. The triads were synthesized according to the method outlined in Scheme 5.1. **Triads 1** and **2** were obtained by the condensation of $P(tpfc)(OH)_2$ with β -naphthol and pyren-1-ol, respectively in toluene under reflux for 24 h. The resulting mixture was purified by 100-200 mesh silica gel column chromatography and subsequent recrystallization from chloroform/hexane yielded the desired products in good yields.

Scheme 5.1. Synthetic scheme of two axially substituted corrole triads (**Triad 1** and **Triad 2**).

The newly synthesized triads were characterized by 1H , ^{31}P NMR, and mass spectral analysis. 1H NMR spectral data of the triads are displayed in Figure 5.2 and

5.4. The peak around 8-9 ppm belongs to the β -pyrrole protons of the corrole part of the triad. In contrast, the PAH protons appear in the range 6-7 ppm. Shielding effects are apparent for the protons on the PAH units bound axially to the corrole moiety. The resonances due to the PAH protons *a* and *b* are shifted upfield in the range 2-3 ppm in the triads due to the ring current effect of the corrole macrocycle. The corrole ring current effect is more in **Triad 2** than in **Triad 1**. Similar type of upfield previously observed for the porphyrin-pyrene axially linked triad systems.²² All these peak positions confirms the axial bonding of PAH to the corrole macrocycle. One of the significant structural characterizations of the phosphorous complexes is the coordination number of phosphorous in these triad systems. Phosphorous can form five and six coordination and which can be confirmed from the ³¹P NMR spectroscopy.²³ **Triads 1** and **2** were found to be six-coordinated with the peak at ~186 ppm and ~183 ppm, respectively (Figure 5.6). The formation of triads further confirmed from HRMS spectral analysis, *m/z*, 1133.11 and *m/z*, 1288.14 for **Triad 1** and **Triad 2** respectively, which corresponds to (M + Na)⁺ molecular ion peak (Figure 5.3 and 5.5). Above all, we were successful in getting the single crystal for **Triad 1** which strongly confirms the formation of the axially linked six coordinated P(V)corrole complex.

5.3.2 X-ray crystal structure

Quality crystals for single crystal analysis for **Triad 1** were obtained by slow evaporation of chloroform/hexane solvent mixture over a period of five days. The molecular structure of the **Triad 1** is shown in Figure 5.7. The compound was crystallized in the monoclinic space group *C2/c*. The pertinent data collection parameters and a listing of significant bond distances and angles are depicted in Tables 5.1 and 5.2, respectively. The phosphorous in **Triad 1** is coordinated to two oxygen atoms and four nitrogen atoms to form a hexacoordinated complex in which the central phosphorous atom is placed on the plane of the corrole macrocycle comprising four pyrrole rings and three meso carbons of corrole with minor distortions. The coordination geometry can be described as distorted octahedral with four equatorial nitrogen atoms in the plane and two axial oxygen atoms. The axial P-O distance is found to be 1.69 Å and the equatorial P-N distances range from 1.80-1.84 Å.

Figure 5.7. Molecular Structure of **Triad 1**. H atoms have been omitted for clarity.

Table 5.1. Crystal data collection parameters for **Triad 1**.

Parameter	Triad 1
Mol formula	C ₅₇ H ₂₂ F ₁₅ N ₄ O ₂ P
Formula weight	1110.75
crystal system	Monoclinic
space group	C2/c
cryst size	0.44x 0.21x 0.19
Temp/K	293 K
<i>a</i> /(Å)	22.2000(15)
<i>b</i> /(Å)	15.2908(10)
<i>c</i> /(Å)	27.5057(19)
α (°)	90
β (°)	95.4730(1)
γ (°)	90
<i>V</i> /Å ³	9294.40(11)
<i>Z</i>	8
<i>D</i> _{calcd} , g cm ⁻³	1.588
μ /(Mo,K α)mm ⁻¹	0.172
<i>F</i> (000)	4464
<i>R</i> 1 [<i>I</i> > 2 σ (<i>I</i>)]	0.0546
<i>wR</i> 2 [<i>I</i> > 2 σ (<i>I</i>)]	0.1455
<i>R</i> 1 (all data)	0.0680
<i>wR</i> 2 (all data)	0.1350
Gof	1.06
CCDC no.	1579496

Table 5.2. Selected bond lengths (Å) and bond angles (°) of **Triad 1**.

Parameter	Bond Length(Å)
P1–O1	1.673 (18)
P1–O2	1.690 (17)
P1–N1	1.845 (2)
P1–N2	1.804 (2)
P1–N3	1.810 (2)
P1–N4	1.827 (19)
Parameter	Bond Angle (°)
O1– P1–O2	173.37 (9)
O1– P1–N1	91.54 (9)
O1– P1–N2	87.88 (10)
O1– P1–N3	87.90 (9)
O1– P1–N4	93.63 (9)
O2– P1–N1	87.78 (9)
O2– P1–N2	85.54 (9)
O2– P1–N3	92.09 (9)
O2– P1–N4	93.00 (8)
N1– P1–N2	90.95 (9)
N2– P1–N3	83.00 (9)
N3– P1–N4	90.94 (9)
N4– P1–N1	95.12 (9)

Figure 5.8. View of **Triad 1** showing the intermolecular hydrogen bonding interactions involving C55–H55 of the naphthyl moiety and F9 of the pentafluorophenyl group forming a 1D array.

These trends in the distances are found to be same as that observed in phosphorous corrole complexes featuring the axial linkage.²¹ The *meso* substituents are tilted with respect to the corrole mean plane to minimize the steric repulsion between aromatic rings and they are twisted by 73.121, 61.021 and 88.471, respectively.

The corrole ring is distorted and adopts a “ruffled” deformation confirmed by the smaller core size (1.845(2) Å) compared to the Collins and Hoard suggested core size of 2.01 Å.²⁴ Further scrutiny of the packing diagram of **Triad 1** showed an intermolecular hydrogen bonding interaction between the naphthyl hydrogen H55 of the triad with the corrole fluorine F9 of an adjacent triad to form a 1D array with a separation of 2.525 Å [H(55)–F(9)] and an angle of 138.711 [C(28)–H(28) O(8)] (Fig. 5.8).

5.3.3 UV-visible absorption studies

The electronic absorption spectra of the triads along with its monomeric constituents *i.e.*, **P(tpfc(OH)₂)**, naphthalene (Nap) and pyrene (Pyr) were measured in dichloromethane and are displayed in Figure 5.9. The corresponding wavelength of absorption maxima and molar extinction coefficients (ϵ) are listed in Table 5.3.

Figure 5.9. Absorption spectra of triads and monomeric units in CH_2Cl_2 solvent.

The absorption peaks between 250 to 350 nm region arises due to π - π^* of Nap and Pyr monomeric units of triads. In contrast, corrole has an intense Soret band at 410 nm due to π - π^* electronic transition from ground state to the second excited state (S_2) and three less intense Q bands, originated from π - π^* electronic transitions attributed to the first excited state (S_1). A comparison of the UV-visible spectra of triads with the spectra of the corresponding precursor units suggest that the λ_{\max} and ϵ values of **Triad 1** is found in the same range as those of the reference compounds. Thus, the spectrum of the **Triad 1** is more or less similar to the spectrum resulting from a combination (1:2 mole/mole ratio) of **P(tpfc)(OH)₂** and Nap of the individual precursors. On the other hand, both Soret and Q bands are slightly broadened and absorption maxima red-shifted by 4 nm in case of **Triad 2** due to π - π interactions of axial pyrene units with corrole macrocycle.

Table 5.3. UV-visible and electrochemical data.

Compound	Absorption, λ_{\max} , nm ^a (log ϵ , M ⁻¹ cm ⁻¹)	Potential V vs. SCE ^b		E_{CT} (Cor ⁺ PA H)	E_{CT} (Cor ⁻ PAH ⁺)
		Reduction	Oxidation		
Nap	275 (5.30)	-	1.50 ^c	-	-
Pyr	274 (5.50) 336 (5.50)	-	1.34 ^d	-	-
P(tpfc)(OH)₂	411 (6.20) 521 (5.30) 561 (5.50) 581 (5.70)	-1.10 -1.79	1.06, 1.33, 1.55	-	-
Triad 1	280(4.90) 412(5.70) 521 (5.20) 560(5.50) 580 (5.60)	-1.15 -1.79	1.04 1.31 1.57	3.04	2.72
Triad 2	279 (5.20) 353(5.10) 412(5.50) 524(5.00) 564(5.30) 584(5.40)	-1.16 -1.80	0.96 1.24 1.56	2.96	2.72

^aSolvent CH₂Cl₂, Error limits: λ_{\max} , \pm 1 nm, log ϵ , \pm 10%. ^bCH₂Cl₂, 0.1 M TBAP; Glassy carbon working electrode, Standard calomel electrode is reference electrode, Pt electrode is auxiliary electrode. Error limits, $E_{1/2} \pm 0.03$ V, ^cRef.29, ^dRef.10.

5.3.4 Electrochemical Properties

Figure 5.10. Differential pulse voltammetry of $P(tpfc)(OH)_2$, Triad 1 and Triad 2 in 0.1 M TBAP solution in CH_2Cl_2 .

Figure 5.11. Cyclic voltammogram of Triad 1 and Triad 2 in 0.1 M TBAP solution in CH_2Cl_2 .

The electrochemical behaviour of the triads was investigated using cyclic and differential pulse voltammetric techniques. Figures 5.10 and 5.11 illustrate the differential pulse and cyclic voltammograms of both triads and Table 5.3 summaries the redox potential data (CH_2Cl_2 and 0.1 M TBAP) of the D–A systems investigated in this study along with the control compounds. Table 5.3 indicates that **P(tpfc)(OH)₂** showed three oxidation and two reduction peaks under the experimental conditions employed for the study. In contrast, in the case of pristine PAH molecule, we observed a quasi-reversible oxidation process. Similarly, both triads exhibited three oxidation and two reduction peaks. However, only the first oxidation of PAH and the first reduction of corrole were examined to evaluate the free-energy change associated with photoinduced electron transfer (PET) in the triad. The experimental HOMO–LUMO gap (potential difference between the first oxidation and the first reduction) was found to be in agreement with the theoretical value.

5.3.5 Computational studies

The computational calculations were carried out at the B3LYP/ 6-31G(d,p) level for understanding the geometry and electronic structure of the triads. The frontier molecular orbitals (HOMOs and LUMOs) and the molecular electrostatic potential (MEP) maps for both the triads are given in Figure 5.12. The optimized structural parameters and the orbital energies are summarized in Table 5.4. The estimated edge-to-edge distance R_{e-e} from the corrole ring to the nearest carbon of the naphthalene for **Triad 1** was 2.80 Å, while the centre-to-centre distance R_{c-c} between them was estimated to be 5.65 Å, and the distances are in good agreement with the values obtained from the crystal structure (R_{e-e} , 2.78 Å and R_{c-c} , 5.75 Å). In the case of **Triad 2**, these values are found to be 2.83 Å and 6.58 Å, respectively. The energies of the HOMO and LUMO for **Triads 1** and **2** were 5.17 eV and 5.18 eV, and 2.44 eV and 2.71 eV, respectively. For **Triad 1**, both the HOMO and LUMO located on the corrole moiety whereas for **Triad 2**, a part of the HOMO is located on pyrene and the LUMO is completely on the corrole macrocycle. Further, TD-DFT studies on these molecules were carried at the B3LYP/6-31G(d,p) level to secure information on the excited-state transitions and the results are in reasonable agreement with the experimental values. Singlet state properties of wavelength of maximum absorbance, oscillation strength (f), excited state

energy (E) in eV, and percentage contribution of the molecular orbital for the triads by means of absorption spectra computed from the frontier molecular orbitals using the *GaussSum-2.2.5* software are given in Table 5.5 and the theoretical absorption spectra are shown in Fig. 5.3.

Table 5.4. B3LYP/6-31G (d,p)-optimized structural parameters and related orbital energies of the investigated triads.

Compounds	E , Kcal/mol ⁻¹	R_{e-e} , Å	R_{c-c} , Å	HOMO, eV	LUMO, eV	HL, eV
Triad 1	3.04×10^6	2.80	5.65	-5.17	-2.44	2.73
Triad 2	2.75×10^6	2.83	6.58	-5.18	-2.71	2.47

Figure 5.12. Electrostatic potential map and frontier molecular orbitals energy levels and energy gap of Triad 1 and Triad 2.

Figure 5.13. Theoretical absorption spectra of **Triad 1** (a), and **Triad 2** (b) in DCM solvent.

Table 5.5. Comparison of experimental optical properties with singlet excited state properties of dyads by B3LYP in DCM solvent.

Compound	^a λ_{\max}	^b λ_{\max}	^c f	^d E	% of molecular orbital composition
Triad 1	580	535	0.1202	2.31	H-1- \rightarrow L+1 (22%), HOMO- \rightarrow LUMO (76%)
Triad 2	584	624	0.0145	1.98	HOMO- \rightarrow LUMO (98%)

^aRecorded absorbance in nm, ^bTheoretical absorbance in nm, ^cOscillation strength, and ^dExcitedstateenergy in eV.

5.3.6 Exited state properties

As can be seen from Figure 5.9 and Table 5.3, both triads can be exclusively excited at either the PAH or the corrole absorption maximum. Figure 5.14a shows the emission spectra of both triads when excited in dichloromethane solvent at either 275 nm or 336 nm, that is, the λ_{\max} where PAH absorbs predominantly. The resultant emission spectra are quenched in both triads, when compared to their monomeric units. In contrast, when excited at 410 nm, *i.e.*, the λ_{\max} where the corrole macrocycle absorbs predominantly, the resulting

Figure 5.14. a) Emission spectra of equiabsorbing solutions of **Triad 1**, Nap, **Triad 2** and Pyr (OD $\lambda_{\text{ex}} = 0.1$) in CH_2Cl_2 solvent. b) Emission spectra of equiabsorbing solutions of **Triad 1**, **Triad 2** and P(ptfc)(OH)₂ (OD $\lambda_{\text{ex}} = 0.1$) in CH_2Cl_2 solvent.

Table 5.6. Florescence data ^a

Compound	λ_{ex} , nm	λ_{em} (nm) (Φ , Q%) ^b			
		Toluene	DCM	PhCN	DMSO
Naphthalene	275	337 (0.23)	338 (0.16)	-- ^d	338 (0.51)
Pyrene	336	385 (0.52) ^c	375 (0.49) ^c	374 (0.45)	375 (0.50)
P(ptfc)(OH) ₂	410	588 (0.47)	588 (0.53)	586 (0.32)	591 (0.36)
Triad 1	275	347, 588, (0.03, 86)	344, 586 (0.02, 88)	-- ^d	347, 582 (0.13, 75)
	410	586 (0.36)	588 (0.43)	582 (0.34)	582 (0.50)
Triad 2	336	384 (0.07, 87)	384(0.02, 95)	388 (0.07, 84)	391(0.02, 95)
	410	588 (0.03, 93)	587 (0.02, 96)	585 (0.05, 91)	587 (0.02, 93)

^aSpectra were measured at 293 ± 3 K. Error limits: $\lambda_{\text{em}}, \pm 1$ nm; $\Phi, \pm 10\%$. ^bQ is defined in eqn (1).

^cRef. 21. ^dSolvent has absorption at this wavelength.

Figure 5.15. Emission spectra of **P(ptfc)(OH)₂**, **Triad 1** and **Triad 2** at $\lambda_{\text{ex}} = 410$ nm in (a) Toluene (b) DMSO (c) PhCN.

emission spectra in dichloromethane presented in (Figure 5.14b). We carried out emission studies of both triads in toluene, PhCN and DMSO solvents (Figure 5.15 and 5.16) and the corresponding emission maxima and quantum yield data are presented in Table 5.6. The spectral shapes and wavelengths of maximum emission for individual chromophores of both triads remain close to those for the corresponding monomeric entities. The E_{0-0} (0–0 spectroscopic transition energy) values of naphthalene (4.05 ± 0.05 eV), pyrene (3.56 ± 0.05 eV) and the corrole (2.11 ± 0.05 eV for **Triad 1** and 2.15 ± 0.05 eV for **Triad 2**) moieties of the triads, as estimated from an overlap of their absorption and emission spectra, were found to be in the same range as the E_{0-0} values of naphthalene, pyrene, and **P(tpfc)(OH)₂**, respectively. From Figure 5.14a and 5.14b and Table 5.6, it is clear that fluorescence quantum yields of naphthalene and pyrene in both the triads and corrole in **Triad 2**.

Figure 5.16. Fluorescence spectra of naphthalene and **Triad 1** ($\lambda_{\text{ex}} = 275 \text{ nm}$) and pyrene and **Triad 2** ($\lambda_{\text{ex}} = 336 \text{ nm}$) in Toluene and DMSO.

moiety became remarkably smaller than the corresponding monomeric units. The quenching efficiency Q ,

$$Q = \frac{\phi(\text{ref}) - \phi(\text{triads})}{\phi(\text{ref})} \dots\dots\dots (5.1)$$

$$k_{\text{obs}} = \frac{Q/(1-Q)}{\tau(\text{ref})} \dots\dots\dots (5.2)$$

and the rate of fluorescence quenching, k_{obs} , values evaluated using the fluorescence data are given in Table 5.7. In eqn (1) and (2), $\Phi_{\text{f}}(\text{ref})$ and $\Phi_{\text{f}}(\text{triads})$ refer to the quantum yield of an appropriate reference compound and a given triad, respectively. $\tau(\text{ref})$ is the singlet-state

lifetime of either Nap (7, 14, 20 and 53 ns in toluene, CH₂Cl₂, PhCN and DMSO) or pyrene, respectively. It was found that Q is in the range of 75 to 89% for **Triad 1** and 87 to 95% for **Triad 2** in the investigated solvents. These values suggest that the photo-excited states of the PAH and corrole moiety were quenched through energy and/or electron transfer.

There exists a strong overlap between the emissions of PAH and absorption of corrole in both the triads and this suggests that quenching of the emission of PAH in these D–A systems might be due to a photoinduced energy transfer (PEnt) from the singlet state of PAH to the corrole macrocycle. Indeed, excitation of an approximately 10⁻⁷ M solution of **Triad 1** at 275 nm resulted in the appearance of a well-defined corrole emission band at 588 nm in all four investigated solvents. In addition, when the fluorescence was monitored at the corrole emission maximum ($\lambda_{\text{max}} = 588$ nm), the excitation spectrum taken for **Triad 1** showed bands characteristic of naphthalene absorption (Figure 5.17).

Table 5.7. Energy transfer data of **Triad 1**^a

	Solvent	%Q	%T	k_{obs} (10 ⁹ s ⁻¹)	$k_{\text{EN}}^{(\text{obs})}$ (10 ⁹ s ⁻¹) ^e	J^d (cm ⁶ mmol ⁻¹) ^c	k_{Forster} (10 ¹³ s ⁻¹) ^d
Triad 1	Toluene (n = 1.496, $\epsilon = 2.24$) ^b	89	80	0.58	0.29	0.26×10^{-13}	0.15
	DCM (n = 1.452, $\epsilon = 8.93$) ^b	85	80	0.81	0.57	2.52×10^{-13}	3.32
	DMSO (n = 1.477, $\epsilon = 46.7$) ^b	75	71	0.06	0.05	0.02×10^{-13}	0.49

^aError limits: %Q, $k_{\text{obs}} \pm 8\%$, %T, $k_{\text{EN}}^{(\text{obs})}$: $\pm 15\%$ ^b η and ϵ refer to refractive index and dielectric constant of the solvents, respectively. ^cSpectral overlap term calculated by using PhotochemCAD software²⁷. ^d $\kappa^2 = 0.66$ in all the cases and $R_{\text{c-c}} = 5.65$ Å (**Triad 1**). ^e $k_{\text{EN}}^{(\text{obs})}$ calculated by using equation. $\frac{T_{\text{obs}}(1-T_{\text{obs}})}{\tau(\text{PAH})} T_{\text{obs}}$, energy transfer efficiency, was calculate from the overlap of the excitation and absorption spectra. 1.496; 2.240.

Moreover, when excited at 410 nm, *i.e.*, the corrole absorption maxima, the obtained emission spectra are identical to its monomeric unit **P(tpfc)(OH)₂**. It should be mentioned here that a solution containing a 1 : 1 (mole/mole) intermolecular mixture of Nap and corrole did not show quenching of the fluorescence due to Nap ($\lambda_{\text{max}} = 275$ nm), nor did it suggest

energy transfer in the excitation spectrum. Collectively, these observations provide evidence for intramolecular PEnT in **Triad 1** from the singlet state of naphthalene to corrole. On the other hand, in **Triad 2**, when excited at 336 nm, *i.e.*, the λ_{\max} corresponding to the pyrene absorption, the emission spectra were quenched when compared to its monomeric unit Pyr with no observation of corrole emission at 588 nm, in spite of the pyrene emission overlap with absorption of corrole. Similarly, when excited at 410 nm where corrole absorbs predominantly, the resulting emission spectra are quenched when compared to its monomeric unit **P(tpfc)(OH)₂**. Moreover, no characteristic absorption of pyrene was observed when the fluorescence was monitored at 588 nm (corrole emission maxima) in **Triad 2** (Figure 5.17). These observations suggested that the quenching pathway in **Triad 2** is mainly photoinduced electron transfer (PET), which will be discussed in the later part of the chapter.

Figure 5.17. Overlay of the excitation and absorption spectra of **Triad 1** and **Triad 2** in CH_2Cl_2 ($\lambda_{\text{em}} = 588 \text{ nm}$).

Energy transfer reactions in bichromophoric D–A systems can proceed mainly by two types of mechanisms, the Förster mechanism (or dipole–dipole interaction)²⁵ or the Dexter mechanism (or electron exchange mechanism).²⁶ The Förster mechanism requires, among other things, the rate of energy transfer to be proportional to spectra overlap, J , of the donor emission and the acceptor absorption. The spectral overlap integral, $J_{\text{Förster}}$, can be evaluated according to eqn (5.3).

$$J_{\text{Forster}} = \frac{\int F(\nu)\varepsilon(\nu)\varepsilon^{-4} d\nu}{\int F(\nu)d\nu} \dots\dots\dots (5.3)$$

Where $F_D(\lambda)$ is the fluorescence intensity of the donor with total intensity normalized to unity. $\varepsilon_A(\lambda)$ refers to the molar extinction coefficient of the acceptor expressed in units of $M^{-1}cm^{-1}$ and λ in nm. In the present study, $J_{\text{Förster}}$ values for **Triad 1** and **Triad 2** in four different solvents were calculated using software, PhotochemCAD,²⁷ and the obtained values are tabulated in Table 5.7. Using these $J_{\text{Förster}}$ values, the Förster energy transfer rate, $k_{\text{Förster}}$, was evaluated according to eqn (5.4)

$$k_{\text{Foster}} = \frac{8.8 \times 10^{23} \kappa^2 \phi_D J_{\text{Foster}}}{n^4 \tau_D R^6} \dots\dots\dots (5.4)$$

where n is the refractive index of the specified solvent, Φ_D and τ_D are the emission quantum yield and lifetime of the isolated donor in the investigated solvents, R is the donor–acceptor center-to-center distance (for **Triad 1**, it is 5.65 Å and for **Triad 2**, it is 6.58 Å) and k^2 , the orientation factor, takes into account the relative orientation of the transition dipole moments of the donor and the acceptor, and for randomly oriented dipoles, a value of $k^2 = 2/3$ is generally used. Using these $J_{\text{Förster}}$ values, the rates of Förster energy transfer, $k_{\text{Förster}}$, evaluated according to eqn (5.4) were found to be in the range of $0.15 \times 10^{13} s^{-1}$ (toluene) $0.49 \times 10^{13} s^{-1}$ (DMSO) for **Triad 1**. The free-energy changes (ΔG_{EN}) accompanying energy transfer, either by dipole–dipole or electron exchange mechanism in all solvents, were calculated by eqn (5.5)²⁸ and are tabulated in Table 5.7.

$$\Delta G_{\text{EN}} = -E_{0,0}(\text{PAH}^*) + E_{0,0}(\text{Corrole}) \dots\dots\dots (5.5)$$

The driving force for the photoinduced energy transfer, ΔG_{EN} , from $^1\text{PAH}^*$ to corrole, for both triads in all investigated solvents, was found to be exothermic, and this is more pronounced in the case of **Triad 1** as compared to **Triad 2** (see Table 5.7). Though ΔG_{EN} is also exothermic in **Triad 2**, no corrole emission was observed when it was excited at 336 nm, and also corrole emission was quenched when it was excited at 410 nm, therefore there is a possibility of photoinduced electron transfer (PET) in addition to the PEnT process. The change in freeenergy for an electron transfer (ΔG_{PET}) from the singlet excited state of PAH to

the ground state of corrole was calculated by employing the redox potential and E_{0-0} data by using following equation.

$$\Delta G_{PET} = E_{1/2}(\text{PAH}/\text{PAH}^+) - E_{1/2}(\text{Cor}/\text{Cor}^-) - E_{0-0} \dots\dots\dots (5.6)$$

$E_{1/2}(\text{PAH}/\text{PAH}^+)$ and $E_{1/2}(\text{Cor}/\text{Cor}^-)$ refer to the oxidation potential of PAH and reduction potential of corrole, respectively (*vide supra*). The driving force for charge separation (ΔG_{PET}) for **Triad 1** is -1.33 eV and for **Triad 2** it is -1.26 eV. Therefore, based on the above investigations, energy transfer is the major pathway in **Triad 1** and electron transfer is the major pathway in **Triad 2** (Table 5.8).

Table 5.8. Free energy change (eV) for singlet energy transfer (ΔG_{EN}) **Triad 1** and **Triad 2** in various solvents.

Compound	$(\Delta G_{EN} (\text{PAH}^*-\text{Corrole}))$			
	Toluene	DCM	PhCN	DMSO
Triad 1	-1.96	-1.94	-1.93	-1.92
Triad 2	-1.44	-1.41	-1.40	-1.38

Figure 5.18. Spectrum of (a) one-electron oxidized and (b) one-electron reduced species of **P(tpfc)(OH)₂** (red lines) in comparison with the neutral compound obtained by performing spectroelectrochemical measurements in benzonitrile containing 0.2 M (TBA)ClO₄.

Figure 5.18 shows the spectrum of the one-electron oxidized and one-electron reduced species of **P(tpfc)(OH)₂** (red lines) in comparison with the neutral compound (black lines) in benzonitrile. New peaks corresponding to **P(tpfc)(OH)₂⁺** appeared at 490 and 645 nm while peaks corresponding to **P(tpfc)(OH)₂⁻** were located at 502, 545 and 590 nm. To a large extent, these peaks were found to be reversible. The appearance of new peaks at these locations will provide direct proof of electron transfer in the triads (*vide supra*).

5.3.7 Excited state processes

Figure 5.19. Fluorescence decay curves of **P(ptfc)(OH)₂**, **Triads 1** and **2** in DCM.

First, excited state lifetimes of the investigated compounds were recorded using time correlated single photon counting (TCSPC) with nanoLED excited sources. In the case of phosphorous corrole and the triads, a single exponential decay was observed when corrole was excited at 410 nm and the emission was monitored at 588 nm (See Figure 5.19 for decay curves). However, when either naphthalene excited at 275 nm in **Triad 1** or pyrene excited at

336 nm in **Triad 2**, and monitored at their respective emission wavelengths (338 nm for naphthalene and 390 nm for pyrene), a biexponential decay was satisfactory. Table 5.9 lists the lifetimes of the investigated compounds in different solvents. Several interesting observations were made. The lifetime of $^1\text{PC}^*$ ($\text{PC} = \mathbf{P}(\text{tpfc})(\text{OH})_2$) was around 3.5 ns rendering it to be useful sensitizer. The $^1\text{naphthalene}^*$ lifetime was quenched in **Triad 1** likely due to the earlier discussed occurrence of singlet-singlet energy transfer, however, when corrole was excited in **Triad 1**, no significant change in the $\mathbf{P}(\text{tpfc})(\text{OH})_2$ was observed, suggesting that the $^1\text{PC}^*$ ($\text{PC} = \mathbf{P}(\text{tpfc})(\text{OH})_2$) is not likely involved in additional photochemical events. Interestingly, when pyrene was excited in **Triad 2**, substantial quenching of $^1\text{pyrene}^*$ in **Triad 2** was observed. This was also the case when PC was excited in **Triad 2**, a decrease of about 15-20% of $^1\text{PC}^*$ lifetime was observed indicating occurrence of photochemical events originated from these excited states in **Triad 2**.

Table 5.9. Singlet excited state life time of the phosphorous corrole derivatives in different solvents

Compound	λ_{ex}	λ_{em}	Toluene ^a (τ/ns)	DCM ^a (τ/ns)	PhCN ^a (τ/ns)	DMSO ^a (τ/ns)
Naphthalene	275	338	14.11	7.20	--	50.80
Pyrene	336	390	5.52(8) 19.70 (92)	5.72 (7) 25.01 (93)	6.79 (19) 27.6 (81)	3.78 (1) 120.70 (99)
$\mathbf{P}(\text{tpfc})(\text{OH})_2$	410	588	3.56	3.63	3.78	3.52
Triad 1	410	588	3.47	3.66	3.74	3.82
	275	345	3.68 (32) 9.05 (67)	3.34 (70) 10.84 (30)	--	3.79 (61) 18.70 (39)
Triad 2	410	588	3.34	3.41	3.08	3.47
	336	385	1.77 (21) 11.13 (78)	2.55 (42) 13.76 (57)	2.59 (43) 10.3(57)	1.59 (37) 10.80 (62)

^aError limit of τ 10%. Values in parenthesis are relative amplitudes of the corresponding decay component.

Femtosecond transient spectra recorded for the PC and the triads are shown in Figure 5.20. Immediately after excitation, the instantaneously formed $^1\text{PC}^*$ revealed positive peaks at 455, 508, 618, 684 and 1430 nm due to transitions originating from the singlet excited state. Negative peaks at 565, 588 and 650 nm are also observed

(Figure 5.20a). By comparison with the absorption and fluorescence spectrum of PC, the 565 and 588 nm peaks are ascribed to ground state bleaching, while part of 588 and 650 nm peaks are assigned to stimulated emission of the excited probe. As shown in Figure 5.20b, the decay of the 1430 nm peak (black) lasted over 3 ns, consistent with the longer lifetime of the $^1\text{PC}^*$ (see Table 5.9). The spectral features observed for **Triad 1** at the excitation wavelength of 410 nm, exciting primarily PC, are almost identical to that of the pristine PC (Figure 5.20b). The decay of the 1430 nm peak (red line) tracked that of pristine PC, indicating absence of either energy or electron transfer involving the naphthalene entities from the $^1\text{PC}^*$ state. In contrast, the transient spectra recorded for **Triad 2** revealed faster relaxation of $^1\text{PC}^*$ originated events (singlet-singlet transition, ground state bleaching and stimulated emission) indicating its involvement with additional photochemical events involving appended pyrene entities.

Figure 5.20. Femtosecond transient spectra at the indicated delay times (410 nm of 100 fs pulses) of (a) P(tpfc)(OH)₂, (b) **Triad 1** and (c) **Triad 2** in Ar-saturated benzonitrile, d) Decay profile.

Figure 5.21. Femtosecond transient spectra recorded at a delay time of 2.74 ns of (i) **PC** and (b) **Triad 2** in PhCN.

The decay of the 1430 nm was also relatively fast (Figure 5.20d blue line). As shown in Figure 5.21, the transient spectrum recorded at a delay time of 2.74 ns for **Triad 2** revealed positive absorbance in the 580-590 nm range (appearing as a shoulder peak to the 590 nm negative peak) compared to the spectrum recorded at the same delay time for PC. This spectral feature is attributable to PC^- species (see Figure 5.20b). These results point out to the occurrence of photoinduced electron transfer from pyrene to $^1\text{PC}^*$ to yield pyrene $^+$ - PC^- charge separated state, however, with low quantum efficiency as revealed by the earlier discussed fluorescence lifetimes.

5.4 Conclusions

In summary, phosphorous(V) corrole has been used to build donor-acceptor conjugates to mimic the early events of natural photosynthesis. The one-step synthesis of triads involved reacting either beta naphthol or pyrene-1-ol with phosphorous(V) corrole bearing axial -OH groups. The X-ray structure of the **Triad 1** revealed axial disposition of the two naphthyl entities without causing noticeable steric hindrances. Electron deficient nature of phosphorous(V) in the triads was clear from the frontier LUMO generated on the optimized structures and also by electrochemical methods. Steady-state fluorescence studies revealed singlet-singlet

energy transfer from singlet-excited naphthalene to corrole in the case of **Triad 1**, however, no energy transfer event was observed when corrole was selectively excited. Interestingly, in the case of **Triad 2** such singlet-singlet energy transfer process from excited pyrene to corrole was weak, however, evidence of charge separation leading to the formation of pyrene⁺-PC⁻ charge separated state was witnessed when corrole of selectively excited. The present study brings out the significance of axial bound entities on phosphorous (V) corrole in promoting photo-induced energy and electron transfer events.

5.5 References

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Chapter-6

***Unprecedented Charge-Transfer
Complex of Fused Diporphyrin as Near-
Infrared Absorption Induced High
Aspect Ratio Nanorods***

6.1 Introduction

To understand the formation and excited state dynamics of long lived charge transfer species in donor acceptor system, in the previous three chapters, we have successfully studied covalently linked (either peripheral or axial positions) donor acceptor systems in which either porphyrins or corroles as the scaffolding unit. However, in natural photosynthesis matrix aids in various supramolecular interactions between donor-acceptor systems *via* π - π stacking, Vander waal interaction, and hydrogen bonding to form charge transfer complex. In the present chapter we introduced fused Zinc porphyrin (**FZnDP**) as electron donor, perylene diimide (PDI) as an electron acceptor to form near-IR charge transfer complex (CT) by supramolecular π - π interaction.

Porphyrins and metalloporphyrins have received significant attention in the field of organic semiconductors,¹ chemosensors,² photodynamic therapy,³ nonlinear optical materials⁴ and dye-sensitized solar cells (DSSCs).⁵ Further extensions of π -conjugated porphyrin systems allowed an improvement in efficiency in organic electronics and biological applications.⁶ Recently, fused porphyrins had a great influence on organic electronics because of their remarkable optical and electronic properties. However, there are very few fused porphyrin systems mentioned in the literature owing to the preference of *meso* and β -pyrrole position.⁷ An oxidative ring closure method was developed and utilized for preparing the porphyrins fused with anthracene, pyrene, azulene and other porphyrins.⁸ Osuka and co-workers extensively studied the various fused porphyrin systems constructed by using *meso-meso*, *meso- β* and β - β positions and highlighted that fused systems exhibited excellent optical and electronic properties when compared to the extended π -conjugated porphyrin systems.⁹ To the best of our knowledge, several fused porphyrins were synthesized and systematically characterized, but none of the studies considered donor-acceptor interactions and surface morphology for potential improvements in plastic electronics.¹⁰⁻¹¹ Such diversity of investigations is very important for emergence in the organic field-effect transistors (OFETs) and ferroelectric applications. In this context, the development of novel fused porphyrins is highly important to achieve these targets. Therefore, we designed and synthesized novel fused and non-fused anthracenyl diporphyrin derivatives whose fused

structure allowed the formation of a charge-transfer (CT) complex with an acceptor, which led to nanorod morphology upon a vapor diffusion approach.

Figure 6.1. (a) Chemical structures of diporphyrin-anthracene (DP) and zinc diporphyrin-anthracene (ZnDP). (b) Structure of fused zinc diporphyrin-anthracene (**FZnDP**) and corresponding pictorial representation. (c) Schematic representation of mixture of **FZnDP** and PDI leads CT complex in CHCl₃, which results nanospheres and coalesced to form nanorods by diffusion of CH₃OH vapours.

Non-fused and fused anthracenyl diporphyrin-based systems such as diporphyrin-anthracene (DP), zinc diporphyrin-anthracene (ZnDP) and fused zinc diporphyrin-anthracene (**FZnDP**) were designed for studying the donor–acceptor interactions. DP consists of anthracene C-C bonded with diporphyrins at the *meso*-position. However, fast spontaneous decomposition of DP hampers the progress in the preparation of extended π -conjugated porphyrin systems. Thus, metallodiporphyrin-anthracene ZnDP has been designed by inserting zinc (Zn) metal into the cavity of porphyrins, to resolve this issue. DP and ZnDP exhibit similar structural features and optoelectronic properties. Both of these are non-planar because of the free rotation at the porphyrin C-C bonded anthracene (Figure 6.1a). On the other hand, **FZnDP** comprising of two Zn-porphyrins fused by an anthracene group at the *meso*- and β -positions, which resembles a perylene-diporphyrin derivative, is planar as a result of the restricted free rotation (Figure 6.1b). **FZnDP** is also attractive because of its solubility in most organic solvents. In addition to that, **FZnDP** allows considerable shifting of the visible absorption band to the near-IR region by decreasing the HOMO–LUMO gap.

Hence, this molecule acts as a good electron donor. Subsequently, we selected perylene diimide (PDI) as an electron acceptor with structural similarities to perylene in **FZnDP**. Thus CT complex formation is likely possible through face-to-face interactions by mixing **FZnDP** and PDI in solution.¹² Optical, NMR spectroscopic and microscopic investigations revealed that the CT complex formed between **FZnDP** and PDI leads to high-aspect-ratio nanorods upon diffusion of methanol (CH₃OH) vapors into a chloroform (CHCl₃) solution of FZnDP/PDI (1:1 molar ratio, Figure 6.1c).

6.2 Experimental section

Synthesis of 5-mesityl dipyromethane (**1**), 1,5-di bromo anthracene (**2**) were synthesized as per procedures reported in the literature^{13,14}

6.2.1 Synthesis of 1,9-Bis (pentafluorobenzoyl)-5-mesityl-dipyromethane (**1a**)

The solution of 5-mesityl dipyromethane (**1**) (2 g, 7.57 mmol) in toluene (80 mL), ethylmagnesiumbromide (C₂H₅MgBr, 30 mL, 37.87 mmol) was added under an inert atmosphere at 0 °C. The resulting brown solution was stirred for 30 min at 25 °C and then 2,3,4,5,6-pentafluorobenzoyl chloride (4.48 ml, 22.72 mmol) in toluene (30 mL) was added drop-wise for 45 min. The resulting solution darkened and the mixture was stirred overnight. The reaction was quenched by adding saturated aq. NH₄Cl (75 mL). The organic phase was separated, dried over Na₂SO₄. The solvent was removed under reduced pressure to afford brown oil. The crude product was purified by column chromatography (silica gel 100 – 200 mesh, ethyl acetate: hexane [10:90] to give white solid (**1a**). (2.47 g, 50% yield). ¹H NMR (500 MHz, CDCl₃): δ 9.18 (s, 2H), 6.96 (s, 2H), 6.69 (s, 2H), 6.29 – 6.25 (m, 2H), 5.99 (s, 1H), 2.33 (s, 3H), 2.11 (s, 6H). HRMS (ESI) *m/z* = (C₃₂H₁₈F₁₀N₂O₂) (M+Na)⁺ 675.11 (100 %). (calcd. 652.1).

6.2.2 Synthesis of Anthracene-1,5-dicarbaldehyde (**2a**)

By modifying a literature procedure,¹⁵ *n*-butyl lithium (2.18 mL, 3.27 mmol) was added to the solution of 1,5-dibromoanthracene (500 mg, 1.49 mmol) in dry ether (20 mL) after cooled to -10 °C. The reaction mixture was stirred at 0 °C for 30 min before it was warmed to ambient temperature. After 1 h, the solution was cooled to -78 °C and DMF (461

μL , 5.95 mmol) was added drop wise. The reaction was stirred for 1.5 h, warmed to ambient temperature and diluted with water (5 mL). Then the crude product was purified by column chromatography (silica gel 100 – 200 mesh, ethyl acetate: hexane (1:3 v/v) to give **2a** as a yellow crystalline compound (220 mg, 63% yield). $^1\text{H-NMR}$ (300 MHz, CDCl_3): δ 10.40 (s, 2H), 10.03 (s, 2H), 8.42 (d, $J = 8.5$ Hz, 2H), 8.08 (d, $J = 6.7$ Hz, 2H), 7.72 (dd, $J = 8.3, 6.9$ Hz, 2H). MS (ESI) $m/z = \text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{10}\text{O}_2$: (M+H) $^+$ 235.1 (100%). (calcd. 234.1).

6.2.3 Synthesis of Anthracene 1,5 Di-dipyrromethane (**2b**)

2b prepared by using reported synthetic procedure from **2a**.¹⁶ Dialdehyde **2a** (0.700 g, 2.98 mmol) treated with excess pyrrole (12 mL, 0.179 mol) in the presence of TFA (46.0 μL , 0.59 mmol). After wash with 0.1 M aq NaOH, separated the organic layer and removed excess pyrrole under reduced pressure. The resultant crude product was purified by column chromatography (silica gel 100 – 200 mesh, ethyl acetate: hexane (15:85, v/v) gave pale yellow oil and further recrystallized from hot hexane yields pale yellow solid (**2b**) (0.69 g, 50% yield). $^1\text{H NMR}$ (500 MHz, CDCl_3): δ 8.61 (s, 2H), 7.97 (brs, 4H, NH), 7.86 (d, $J = 8.5$ Hz, 2H), 7.35 (dd, $J = 8.4, 7.0$ Hz, 2H), 7.13 (d, $J = 6.9$ Hz, 2H), 6.69 (dd, $J = 4.1, 2.6$ Hz, 4H, Pyr-H), 6.40 (s, 2H, *meso*-H), 6.17 (dd, $J = 5.8, 2.8$ Hz, 4H, Pyrrole-H's), 6.00 (s, 4H, Pyrrole-H's). HRMS: $m/z \text{C}_{32}\text{H}_{25}\text{N}_4$: (M+H) $^+$ 465.20 (100%). (calcd. 465.2).

6.2.4 Synthesis of Anthracene Diporphyrin (DP)

By modifying a literature procedure,¹⁷ a solution of diacyldipyrromethane (**1a**) (0.510 g, 0.8 mmol) in dry THF/methanol (33 mL, 10:1) was treated with NaBH_4 (1.21 g, 3.2 mmol) at 25 °C for 2 h. The reaction mixture was poured into a mixture of saturated aq. NH_4Cl (80 mL) and CH_2Cl_2 (80 mL). The organic phase was separated and concentrated to dryness. The resulting unstable dipyrromethane-dicarbonyl (**1b**) was dissolved in CH_2Cl_2 (200 mL) and anthracene 1,5 Di-dipyrromethane (**2b**) (0.150 g, 0.32 mmol) was added under argon at room temperature. After a homogenous solution was obtained, *p*-TsOH (0.024 g, 0.14 mmol) was added and the reaction mixture was stirred at room temperature for 90 min. DDQ (0.145 g, 0.64 mmol) was added and stirring was continued for 2 h. The resulting crude product was purified by column chromatography on silica gel ($\text{CH}_2\text{Cl}_2/\text{hexane} = 1:3$). Recrystallization ($\text{CHCl}_3/\text{CH}_3\text{OH}$) gave a purplish black solid **Anthracene Diporphyrin (DP)**; yield: 54 mg

(10 %); $^1\text{H NMR}$ (400 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 8.86 (d, $J = 4.6$ Hz, 4H, $\beta\text{-H}$), 8.81 (d, $J = 4.7$ Hz, 4H, $\beta\text{-H}$), 8.75 (s, 8H, $\beta\text{-H}$), 8.18 (dd, $J = 4.8, 2.9$ Hz, 2H), 7.88 (s, 2H), 7.55 – 7.53 (m, 4H), 7.35 (s, 4H, Ar-H), 2.68 (s, 6H, $p\text{-CH}_3$), 1.90 (s, 12H, $o\text{-CH}_3$), -2.51 (brs, NH, 4H). m/z (MALDI-TOF-MS) = 1694.49, ($\text{C}_{96}\text{H}_{46}\text{F}_{20}\text{N}_8$); $[\text{M}]^+$, (calcd. 1695.4).

6.2.5 Synthesis of Zn_2 Anthracene Diporphyrin (ZnDP)

ZnDP was achieved by modification of a literature procedure.¹⁸ To a solution of **DP** (0.070 g, 0.041 mmol) in DCM/MeOH (3:1) 15 mL was added $\text{Zn}(\text{OAc})_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (0.135 g, 0.618 mmol). The mixture was stirred at room temperature for 4 h. The extent of the reaction was monitored by TLC. At completion, the mixture was work up with water to remove unreacted zinc acetate and loaded onto a silica column chromatography (DCM/hexane). The red-purple product was collected and the solvents removed. The product was precipitated from DCM/MeOH to give reddish brown solid. $^1\text{H NMR}$ (500 MHz, CDCl_3): δ 8.94 (d, $J = 4.6$ Hz, 4H), 8.88 (d, $J = 4.5$ Hz, 4H), 8.85 – 8.82 (m, 8H), 8.18 (dd, $J = 5.2, 2.4$ Hz, 2H), 7.82 (s, 2H), 7.53 – 7.50 (m, 4H), 7.35 (s, 4H), 3.28 (s, 6H), 1.92 (s, 6H), 1.88 (s, 6H). m/z (MALDI-TOF-MS) = 1822.05, ($\text{C}_{96}\text{H}_{46}\text{F}_{20}\text{N}_8\text{Zn}_2$); $[\text{M}]^+$, (calcd. 1822.2).

6.2.6 Synthesis of Fused Zn_2 Anthracene Diporphyrin (FZnDP)

FZnDP was prepared by adaptation of a previously reported oxidative ring fusion procedure.^[S5] **ZnDP** (0.020 g, 0.016 mmol), scandium triflate (0.038 g, 0.078 mmol) and DDQ (0.018 g, 0.078 mmol) were dried under vacuum overnight. To this, 5 mL of dry DCM was added under nitrogen and the reaction mixture was stirred at room temperature for two hours. The extent of the reaction was monitored by TLC and once at completion the reaction mixture was passed through a silica plug (DCM/Hexane). The solvents were removed and the product recrystallized from DCM and n-pentane to give the title compound (4a) as a green-brown solid. $^1\text{H NMR}$ (400 MHz, CDCl_3): δ 9.75 (d, $J = 8.3$ Hz, 2H), 9.61 (s, 2H), 9.48 (d, $J = 4.4$ Hz, 2H), 8.96 (d, $J = 4.3$ Hz, 2H), 8.71 (d, $J = 4.3$ Hz, 4H), 8.68 (d, $J = 4.4$ Hz, 4H), 8.58 (d, $J = 7.0$ Hz, 2H), 8.47 (t, 2H), 7.31 (s, 4H), 2.66 (d, $J = 12.7$ Hz, 6H), 1.91 (d, $J = 17.7$ Hz, 12H). m/z (MALDI-TOF-MS) 1818.20, ($\text{C}_{96}\text{H}_{46}\text{F}_{20}\text{N}_8\text{Ni}_2$); $[\text{M}]^+$, (calcd. 1818.2).

Figure 6.2. ^1H NMR of 1,9-Bis(pentafluorobenzoyl)-5-mesityl-dipyrrromethane (1a).

Figure 6.3. HRMS-MASS of 1,9-Bis(pentafluorobenzoyl)-5-mesityl-dipyrrromethane (1a).

Figure 6.4. ¹H NMR of Anthracene-1,5-dicarbaldehyde **2a**.

Figure 6.5. ¹H NMR of Anthracene 1,5 Di-dipyrromethane **2b**.

Figure 6.6. HRMS-MASS of Anthracene 1,5 Di-dipyrromethane **2b**.

Figure 6.7. ^1H NMR of Anthracenyl diporphyrin DP.

Figure 6.8. MALDI-MASS of Anthracenyl diporphyrin DP.

Figure 6.9. ¹H NMR of Anthracenyl Zinc diporphyrin ZnDP.

Figure 6.10. MALDI-MASS of Anthracenyl Zinc diporphyrin ZnDP.

Figure 6.11. ^1H NMR of Fused anthracenyl Zinc diporphyrin FZnDP.

Figure 6.12. MALDI-TOF mass spectrum of Fused anthracenyl Zinc diporphyrin **FZnDP**.

Figure 6.13. NOESY NMR spectrum of Fused anthracenyl Zinc diporphyrin **FZnDP**.

Scheme 6.1. Synthetic scheme of DP, ZnDP and FZnDP.

6.3 Result and discussions

6.3.1 Synthesis and structure characterization

Schematic synthesis of precursors (1a), (1b), (2a), (2b) and three porphyrin derivatives have been shown in scheme 6.1. **DP**, **ZnDP** and **FZnDP** are synthesized by using Lindsey's acid catalyzed reaction and oxidative ring closure method. **DP** was prepared by condensation of dipyrromethane dicarbinol (1b) and 1,5-anthracene di-dipyrromethane (2b). Treatment of **DP** with p-TsOH/DDQ followed by metallation with $\text{Zn}(\text{OAc})_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$, provided **ZnDP**. Subsequently, synthetically challenged near IR absorbing **FZnDP** was synthesized by treating **ZnDP** with scandium triflate/DDQ under oxidative intramolecular fusion reaction conditions.

^1H NMR and HRMS-Mass spectral characterization of individual precursors of porphyrins are shown in Figure 6.2 - 6.6. The newly synthesized porphyrins were characterized by ^1H NMR, NOSEY-NMR, and Maldi-mass spectral analysis. ^1H NMR spectra of the **DP**, **ZnDP** and **FZnDP** are displayed in Figure 6.7, 6.9 and 6.11. The porphyrin peaks around 8.5-9 ppm corresponding to the β -pyrrolic protons, further peaks at 7.35, 1.9 to 2.2 ppm are attributed to mesitylene protons of both **DP** and **ZnDP**. **DP** shows inner NH signals around -2.51 ppm, there is no appreciable changes on zinc metallation except disappearance of inner proton signals. In contrast, the anthracene protons appear in the range 7.5-8.2 ppm. By oxidative fusion, **FZnDP** gets more deshielding effect H_a, H_c (α, β -anthracenyl) and H_b (β -pyrrolic) protons appeared at 9.5-10.0 ppm range, H_h (β' -anthracenyl) proton appeared at 8.96 ppm, (Figure 6.18) compared to unfused porphyrin (**ZnDP**) which is due to the ring current effect of the planar fused macrocycle. Remaining all protons appeared almost same region as **DP**, **ZnDP**. NOSEY spectrum of **FZnDP** revealed through-space interactions between H_a, H_b (9.67 ppm, 9.75 ppm) and H_c, H_d (9.47 ppm, 8.97 ppm) protons, shown in Figures 6.13. These three porphyrin derivatives are systematically characterized by MALDI-TOF MS and UV-visible spectroscopic methods. The presence of molecular ion peaks $[\text{M}]^+$, 1694.49.11 $[\text{M}]^+$, 1822.14 and $[\text{M}]^+$, 1818.14 for **DP**, **ZnDP** and **FZnDP** respectively, in MALDI-TOF-MS spectra (Figure 6.8, 6.10 and 6.12). All these characterizations confirms the formation of corresponding porphyrins.¹³⁻¹⁹

6.3.2 UV-visible absorption studies

UV/Vis-NIR optical absorption studies of **DP**, **ZnDP** and **FZnDP** were performed in chloroform at a concentration of 2×10^{-5} M (Figure 2 a). Non-fused porphyrins **DP** and **ZnDP** exhibited absorption spectra typical for simple porphyrin monomers with an intense Soret band at 419 nm and either four or two less intense Q-bands. The absorption spectra suggest that the electronic features of **DP** and **ZnDP** changed considerably before and after insertion of Zn metal into the diporphyrin systems.

However, expansion of the π -system by fusion with an anthracene unit perturbed the electronic structure. As a result, the absorption spectrum of **FZnDP** was red-shifted, displaying a λ_{\max} at 859 nm (Figure 6.14). Similar absorption changes have also been observed in other fused porphyrin systems.²⁰ In addition, perylene in **FZnDP** played a significant role in the electronic features of diporphyrins and displayed absorption bands at 769 and 859 nm in the NIR region.

Figure 6.14. UV-vis-NIR optical absorption spectra of **DP**, **ZnDP** and **FZnDP** of **PDI** in CHCl_3 at 2×10^{-5} M at 25 °C.

6.3.3 Charge transfer complex and characterization

Furthermore, optical absorption spectra of **DP**, **ZnDP** and **FZnDP** with **PDI** in a 1:1 molar ratio in CHCl_3 revealed that **FZnDP/PDI** exclusively showed the new absorption band. Figure 6.15a represents the UV/Vis-NIR absorption spectra of mixtures of **DP**, **ZnDP** or **FZnDP** with **PDI** in a 1:1 molar ratio. **DP/PDI** exhibited similar Soret and Q-bands to both **DP** and **PDI**, indicating that the two molecules did not interact with each other in the mixture. **ZnDP/PDI** showed a similar behavior to the mixture of **DP/PDI**. **FZnDP/PDI** revealed a new absorption band at 940 nm, together with other absorption values of Soret and Q-bands of **FZnDP** and **PDI**. This new NIR band suggested that the CT complex formed through face-to-face interactions of perylene in **FZnDP** and **PDI** in a 1:1 molar ratio of the composition. These results also indicated that structural dissimilarities and non-planarity of **DP** and **ZnDP** restricted the interactions with **PDI**, while the perylene in **FZnDP** was structurally analogous to **PDI** and results in the CT complex formation.

Figure 6.15. UV-vis-NIR optical absorption spectra of a) **DP**, **ZnDP** and **FZnDP** before and after mixing of **PDI** in CHCl_3 at 2×10^{-5} M at 25 °C. at 1:1 molar ratio. b) Absorption spectra of stoichiometric ratio (0-1 equivalents) of **PDI** to the **FZnDP** (1 equivalent, 2×10^{-5} M) added successively and recorded at 25 °C.

Subsequently, a stoichiometric molar ratio of **FZnDP** and **PDI** was examined to confirm the definite concentration required for the CT complex between **FZnDP** and **PDI**. Thus, **PDI** added constantly from 0 to 1.0 equivalents to a CHCl_3 solution of **FZnDP** (1 equivalent of 2×10^{-5} M concentration, Figure 6.15b). Interestingly, a new absorption band appeared at 940

nm upon addition of 0.1 m **PDI** and further enhancement in the intensity observed in the sequential addition of **PDI**. After attaining 1 or >1 M concentration of **PDI**, the intensity of the new band reached saturation, which indicated that a 1:1 molar ratio is the precise combination to form the CT complex (Figure 6.15b). Furthermore, similar experiments were repeated with mixtures of **ZnDP** and **PDI**, revealed neither a shift in the absorption maxima, nor the appearance of any new bands, which again proved that the two molecules did not interact (Figure 6.16). UV/Vis-NIR optical absorption spectroscopic investigations suggested that **FZnDP/PDI** are an exceptional CT complex property compared to the other derivatives.

Figure 6.16. UV-vis-NIR absorption spectra of stoichiometric ratio of **ZnDP** with **PDI** (0-1 equivalents, 2×10^{-5} M) in CHCl_3 at 25 °C. To a 1 equivalent of **ZnDP**, **PDI** added successively from 0 - 1 molar in 1 cm cuvette and recorded each spectrum.

^1H NMR studies of **ZnDP** or **FZnDP** individually or in mixtures with **PDI** were performed in CDCl_3 to confirm the CT complex between **FZnDP/PDI**. The ^1H NMR peaks of **ZnDP/PDI** (1:1 molar ratio) revealed that the chemical shift values of the mixture were similar to those of **ZnDP** and **PDI** alone, without any substantial changes, indicating that the two molecules did not interact with each other (Figure 6.17). In contrast, **FZnDP/PDI**

showed significant changes in chemical shift values in comparison to the individual components. Figure 6.18 a represents the ^1H NMR spectra of **FZnDP**, **PDI** and **FZnDP/PDI** (1:1 molar ratio) in the aromatic chemical shift region (7–10 ppm). In the case of **FZnDP**, a triplet (H_h , 8.47 ppm) and two doublets (H_a , 9.75 and H_c , 9.48 ppm) were observed for the perylene moiety fused with the diporphyrin, while the other aromatic region peaks represent the peripheral protons of the porphyrins and the mesityl groups, whereas the perylene moiety of PDI exhibited two doublets (H_x , 8.69 ppm; H_y , 8.62 ppm). **FZnDP/PDI** showed a significant upfield chemical shift in comparison with the spectra of **FZnDP** and **PDI** alone. New upfield shifts belonging to the fused perylene group of **FZnDP** showed a triplet at 7.95 ppm and two doublets at 9.15 and 9.35 ppm, along with an upfield chemical shift of the signals of PDI, revealed an interaction between the perylene in the diporphyrin and PDI, which resulted in a CT complex. This postulation was also supported by the optical

Figure 6.17. ^1H NMR spectra of **ZnDP**, **PDI**, **ZnDP/PDI** (1:1 molar ratio) in chloroform- CDCl_3 at 25 °C. (* represents solvent peak).

Figure 6.18. ¹H NMR spectra of **FZnDP**, **PDI** and **FZnDP/PDI** (1:1 molar ratio) recorded in CDCl₃ at 25 °C (* represents solvent peak).

absorption studies performed on **FZnDP/PDI** in CHCl₃. Subsequently, NOESY experiments on **FZnDP** and **FZnDP/PDI** (1:1 molar ratio) were carried out in CDCl₃ to further understand the CT complex between the perylene in **FZnDP** and **PDI**. The NOESY spectrum of **FZnDP/PDI** showed through space interactions between H_a, H_y and H_c, H_x (Figures 6.19a and 6.19b). These results suggested that the perylene in **FZnDP** and **PDI** interact through π–π stacking, leading to the CT complex formation (Figure 6.19). Thus, **FZnDP** has the exceptional ability to form a CT complex with **PDI**, while **ZnDP** did not show any substantial changes in optical and spectroscopic properties in mixtures with **PDI**, which demonstrates the importance and planarity of perylene in diporphyrin systems.

Having confirmed the charge transfer complex of **FZnDP** and **PDI**, powder X-ray diffraction (PXRD) analyses were performed **ZnDP** or **FZnDP** individually, or in mixtures with **PDI** (Figures 6.20a). **ZnDP** and **PDI** showed diffraction peaks that were very sharp and

Figure 6.19. a) NOESY of aromatic region of **FZnDP/PDI** (1:1 molar ratio). b) Structural illustration of through-space interactions attained in **FZnDP** v/s **FZnDP/PDI** from NOESY and denoted in blue colour and vanished indicated in red colour after face-to-face stack with **PDI**.

crystalline in nature, while **ZnDP/PDI** peaks were similar to those of **ZnDP** and **PDI** alone, indicating that the two molecules did not interact, further supporting the absorption and ^1H NMR analyses (Figure 6.20b). In contrast, **FZnDP** exhibited broad peaks that were amorphous in nature. The mixture of **FZnDP/PDI** displayed rather dissimilar crystalline peaks of **PDI** and considerable shifts in the d-spacing values at 8.5 Å, 6.09 Å, and 3.8 Å

Figure 6.20. Powder X-ray diffraction analysis performed at 25 °C. (a) **ZnDP**, **PDI**, **ZnDP/PDI** (1:1 molar ratio). (b) **FZnDP**, **PDI**, **FZnDP/PDI** (1:1 molar ratio).

indicating that the perylene in **FZnDP** and **PDI** form a CT complex via π - π stacking interactions (Figure 6.20b). Therefore, **FZnDP** only formed a CT complex with **PDI** because of the perylene moiety, which favors strong π - π stacking interactions.

6.3.4 Self assemblies and Morphology studies

We prepared the aggregates of the CT complex by vapor diffusion. CHCl_3 solutions of the individual components and a mixture of **FZnDP/PDI** were prepared by keeping the vial in 1 mL of methanol for 2 days; these aliquots were then transferred onto the substrate *via* a drop-casting method. TEM and AFM were used to analyze the surface morphology of these aggregates. TEM images revealed that **FZnDP** formed spherical aggregates with an average diameter of 150–200 nm (Figure 6.21a), whereas **PDI** displayed fused spherical

aggregates with an average diameter of 200–250 nm (Figure 6.21b). Interestingly, **FZnDP/PDI** (1:1 molar ratio) showed nanospheres, coalesced nanospheres and elongated nanorods (Figures 6.21c and 6.21d). At higher concentration (5×10^{-5} M), the CT complex of **FZnDP/PDI** exhibited nanorod morphology (Figure 6.22).

Figure 6.21. TEM images of an air-dried suspension of **FZnDP**, **PDI** and **FZnDP/PDI** (1:1 molar ratio) prepared by MeOH vapour diffusion into a CHCl_3 solution of **FZnDP**, **PDI** and **FZnDP/PDI** (2×10^{-5}) at 25 °C. (a) **FZnDP**. (b) **PDI**. (c) **FZnDP/PDI** (1:1 molar ratio). (d) Magnified image of **FZnDP/PDI** (1:1 molar ratio).

Figure 6.22. TEM image of an air-dried suspension of FZnDP/PDI (1:1 M, 5×10^{-5} M) prepared from $\text{CHCl}_3/\text{MeOH}$ and drop-casted on carbon coated grid at 25°C .

Figure 6.23. AFM image of an air-dried suspension of FZnDP, PDI and FZnDP/PDI (1:1M, 2×10^{-5} M) prepared from $\text{CHCl}_3/\text{MeOH}$ and drop-casted on freshly cleaved mica at 25°C .

Subsequently, AFM images of **FZnDP**, **PDI** and **FZnDP/PDI** (1:1 molar ratio) were recorded on freshly cleaved mica surfaces and the resultant morphology was similar to that of the TEM images of nanostructures (Figure 6.23a–c). The corresponding section analyses confirmed that the dimensions of the nanospheres and nanorods were in the range of 200–300 nm (Figure 6.23d–f). A detailed morphological analysis suggested that the CT complex of **FZnDP/PDI** (1:1 molar ratio) initiated a nucleation growth mechanism, which formed spheres by π - π stacking interactions of the CT complex, leading to hierarchical nanostructures. Moreover, this progression from nanospheres to nanorods was exclusive for **FZnDP/PDI**. Furthermore, thin films of **FZnDP**, **ZnDP**, **FZnDP/PDI** and **ZnDP/PDI** were prepared by drop-casting the suspensions in CH₃OH on glass surface to check the aggregates in bulk system (Figure 6.24). UV/Vis-NIR absorption spectra revealed that **FZnDP/PDI** films exhibited broad peaks in the NIR region between 1000–1200 nm with a 50 nm bathochromic shift compared to the monomeric state of CT complex which suggested the formation of J-aggregates (Figure 6.24a).^{10d} **FZnDP** also exhibited J-aggregates that were, however, weak in aggregation when compared to the CT complex of **FZnDP/PDI**. In contrast, **ZnDP** and **ZnDP/PDI** films revealed negligible changes in spectral bands, similar to those in solution (Figure 6.24). Thus, **FZnDP/PDI** exclusively forms a CT complex in solution and subsequently aggregates by vapor diffusion approach, leading to hierarchical nanostructures.

Figure 6.24. UV-vis-NIR optical absorption studies of individual and mixture of **FZnDP** and **ZnDP** with **PDI** at film state. a) **FZnDP/PDI**. b) **ZnDP/PDI**. Films were prepared by drop-casting the suspension on glass plates, dried and recorded at 25 °C.

6.4 Conclusion

In conclusion, we have synthesized NIR absorbing **FZnDP** that forms a CT complex with **PDI** via face-to-face π - π stacking. Leading to elongated nanorods via coalesced nanospheres by methanol vapor diffusion. Fused and non-fused diporphyrins strongly differentiate their optical properties and reveal significant donor-acceptor interactions of CT complexes. **FZnDP** opens a pathway from nanospheres to CT rods that could become highly important in the near future for optical, biological and ferroelectric applications, as well as in microwave devices.

6.5 References

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Chapter-7

Conclusions and future perspectives

This thesis entitled “**Donor-acceptor systems based on porphyrins and corroles**” deals with design, synthesis, theoretical aspects, spectroscopy, electrochemical, photophysical characterisation and excited state dynamics of porphyrin and corrole macrocycles that have been covalently bonded either at axial or peripheral position/s and supramolecular π - π interaction with electron acceptor units. The major attention has been laid on the design of molecular structures in order to study the long lived charge transfer state and formation of near-IR charge transfer complex of porphyrin and corrole based donor acceptor systems to mimic the natural photosynthetic reaction centre.

Porphyrins and corroles belongs to tetrapyrrolic family, their metallo/metalloid derivatives possess tunable electrochemical and photophysical applications in various research areas such as molecular electronics, molecular catalysis, photodynamic therapy *etc.*¹⁻⁵ Porphyrins structurally has close relation with chlorophyll pigment and corroles are one carbon atom less and are present in Vitamin B12. A great variety of D-A systems based on porphyrins and corroles have been reported in the literature.⁶⁻¹⁰ Among them porphyrins and corroles with metallocenes based D-A systems have not reported for generation of long lived charge separated species by using its peripheral (either *meso* or β -pyrrole) positions. In contrast, construction of D-A systems by using axial position/s of resident metal/metalloid ion of corroles are relatively less known in literature due to the stability and synthetic protocols of corrole macrocycle compared to the porphyrins. Extension of π -conjugation in porphyrins by fusing macrocycle with hydrocarbons such as anthracene, pyrene *etc.*, will shift the absorption towards red region and these fused porphyrins with good acceptor such as perlynediimide to form charge transfer complex. In this thesis, the theme of energy/electron transfer between donor-acceptors and formation of charge-transfer complex in the systems designed to investigate the phenomenon are examined.

This dissertation is divided into 7 chapters and Chapter-1 discussed about the brief introduction of natural photosynthesis and importance of artificial photosynthesis, theories involved in energy and electron transfer, particularly in D-A systems. Literature survey on artificial donor-acceptor systems development and formation of their long lived charge transfer state of various ‘peripherally’- and ‘axially’ substituted porphyrins, and corroles have been discussed. Chapter-2 consist list of chemicals used and their purification methods and also summarize spectroscopic, electrochemical, magnetic resonance and photophysical

techniques involved to study and characterize the materials during the research work. Chapter-3 inspects the synthesis, separation and characterization of a series of four new D–A system based porphyrin metallocene dyads, which are connected by ester link at *meso*-phenyl position of porphyrin. Chapter-4 we focused on extension of our earlier work in similar design of donor acceptor concept in the class of corroles, synthesis, separation, characterization, photophysical electrochemical and excited dynamics of two free-base corrole-metallocene based D–A system. In Chapter-5 we are interested on minimizing the aggregation of corroles by utilization of axial position/s of P(V) corrole. Here, we introduced naphthalene and pyrene donors at axial positions of a phosphorous (V) corrole for the construction of aggregation minimized D-A systems. Finally in chapter-6 we designed and characterized fused porphyrin based near IR absorbing charge transfer complex, in the concept of supramolecular donor acceptor systems *via* π – π interaction with perylenediimide as acceptor.

7.1 Donor acceptor based Porphyrin-metallocenes

In this chapter, we designed and synthesized porphyrin-metallocene dyads consisting of a metallocene [either ferrocene or mixed sandwich η^5 -[C₅H₄(COOH)]Co(η^4 -C₄Ph₄)] connected *via* an ester linkage at *meso* phenyl position of either free-base [H₂TTPFe or H₂TTPCo] or zinc porphyrin [Zn-TTPFe or Zn-TTPCo] (Figure 7.1). All these four dyad systems were characterized by various spectroscopic and electrochemical methods, and Zn-TTPCo structure analysed by single crystal X-ray diffraction method. The porphyrin macrocycle acts as acceptor, metallocenes acts as donor.

Figure 7.1. Molecular structures of porphyrin-metallocenes.

The key results in this study can be summarised as follows:

- X-ray crystal structure of **Zn-TTPCo** suggests that the complex exists in dimeric form.
- The absorption spectra of all four dyads measured in dichloromethane solvent and indicated the absence of electronic interactions between porphyrin macrocycle and metallocene.
- Electrochemical properties suggest that redox values of dyads are not much different from monomeric units.
- Fluorescence emission of the all four dyads shown the porphyrin was quenched (19-55%) as compared to their monomeric units.
- The quenching was more pronounced in ferrocene derivatives rather than cobaltocenyl derivatives.
- The emission quenching can be attributed to the excited state intramolecular photoinduced electron transfer from metallocene to singlet excited state of porphyrin.
- Electron transfer rates (k_{ET}) were established in the range 1.51×10^8 to $1.11 \times 10^9 \text{ s}^{-1}$.

7.2 Donor acceptor based Corrole-metalloenes

Figure 7.2. Molecular structures of Corrole-metalloenes as **Dyad 1** and **Dyad 2**.

In order to further understand about the long lived charge separated states, herein, we extended similar design concept to other member of tetrapyrrolic family such as corroles. In this chapter, we designed and synthesised corrole-metalloene dyads consisting of metallocene [either ferrocene (**Dyad 1**) or mixed sandwich η^5 -[C₅H₄(COOH)]Co(η^4 -C₄Ph₄)

(**Dyad 2**)] connected *via* an ester linkage at *meso* phenyl position (Figure 7.2). Both the dyads were characterized by ^1H NMR, MALDI-TOF, UV-visible, fluorescence spectroscopies (steady-state, picosecond time-resolved), femtosecond transient absorption spectroscopy (*fs*-TA) and electrochemical methods.

The key results in this study can be summarised as follows:

- The absorption spectra of these dyads showed slight broadening and splitting of Soret band that indicates a weak ground state interaction between the corrole macrocycle and metallocene part of these D-A systems.
- The electrochemical properties suggest that redox properties are not altered. The ground-state properties suggest that there exist ground state interactions between metallocene and corrole macrocycle.
- DFT studies suggest that both HOMO and LUMO resides on corrole macrocycle.
- Fluorescence emission of the corrole was quenched in polar solvents as compared to its parent compound 10-(4-hydroxyphenyl)-5,15-bis-(pentafluorophenyl) corrole (**Ph-Corr**).
- The quenching was more pronounced in ferrocene derivatives rather than cobaltocenyl derivatives may be due to more electron releasing nature of ferrocene.
- Transient absorption studies confirm the absence of photoinduced electron transfer from metallocene to corrole for these dyad systems and the quenching of singlet state of corrole is found to enhance intersystem crossing due to heavy atom effect.

7.3 Axially linked corrole Based D–A systems

In the previous chapter, we have utilized *meso* phenyl positions of corrole macrocycle in the construction of D-A systems. One of the methods, that one can minimize the aggregation of corroles are utilization of axial position/s. The concept of ‘Axial bonding’ is not much explored in corrole chemistry. Here, we utilized axial positions of a Phosphorous(V) corrole in the construction of D-A systems. This approach is facile, modular, by conducting hydroxyl condensation at axial positions of a metalloid corrole to avoid tedious synthetic protocols. This has been encouraged in the study of axially linking 5,10,15- tris(pentafluorophenyl)corroleP(V), **P(tpfc)(OH)₂** with polyaromatic hydrocarbons

(PAH) either naphthalene (**Triad 1**) or pyrene (**Triad 2**) as shown in Figure 7.3. Both the triads were characterized by various spectroscopic techniques, electrochemical and computational studies of both the triads, excited state events, monitored by both time-resolved emission and transient absorption studies, revealed several interesting results.

Figure 7.3. Molecular structures of axially linked Corroles triads.

The key results in this study can be summarised as follows:

- The X-ray structure packing of **Triad 1** showed an intermolecular hydrogen bonding interaction between the naphthyl hydrogen H55 of the triad with the corrole fluorine F9 of an adjacent triad to form a 1D array.
- The absorption spectrum of the **Triad 1** is more or less similar to the spectrum resulting from a combination (1:2 mole/mole ratio) of **P(tpfc)(OH)₂** and **Napthalene** of the individual precursors.
- In case of **Triad 2** absorption spectrum Soret and Q bands are slightly broadened and absorption maxima red-shifted by 4 nm due to π - π interactions of axial pyrene units with corrole macrocycle.
- The electrochemical studies suggest HOMO-LUMO gap (potential difference between the first oxidation and the first reduction) was found to be in agreement with the theoretical value.

- DFT studies suggest that both the HOMO and LUMO located on the corrole moiety in **Triad 1**, whereas for **Triad 2**, a part of the HOMO is located on pyrene and the LUMO is completely on the corrole macrocycle.
- Steady-state fluorescence studies revealed singlet-singlet energy transfer from singlet-excited naphthalene to corrole in the case of **Triad 1**, however, no energy transfer event was observed when corrole was selectively excited.
- Whereas in the case of **Triad 2**, the energy transfer process from singlet excited pyrene to corrole was weak, but evidence of photoinduced charge separation in **Triad 2** leading to the formation of pyrene⁺-PC⁻ was witnessed from femtosecond transient absorption studies, when either pyrene or corrole was selectively excited.
- The importance of axial bound donor entities on phosphorous(V) corrole in promoting photoinduced energy and electron transfer events is borne out from the present study.

7.4 Fused porphyrin based near IR-charge transfer complex

In the previous three chapters, we have used covalent bond in construction of D-A systems. In natural photosynthesis matrix aids in various supramolecular interactions between donor-acceptor systems *via* π - π stacking, Van der waal interaction, and hydrogen bonding to form charge transfer complex. Structural similarities between donor and acceptor are rather important to achieve this phenomenon. Herein, we are designed, synthesized and characterized near IR-charge transfer complex by electron donors such as non-fused diporphyrin-anthracene (**DP**), zinc diporphyrin-anthracene (**ZnDP**) and fused zinc diporphyrin-anthracene (**FZnDP**) in which **FZnDP** absorbs in NIR region, and perylenediimide(**PDI**) as an electron acceptor to form near-IR charge transfer complex (CT) by supramolecular π - π interaction, which led to nanorod morphology upon a vapour diffusion approach (Figure 7.4).

Figure 7.4. (a) Chemical structures of diporphyrin-anthracene (**DP**) and zinc diporphyrin-anthracene (**ZnDP**). (b) Structure of fused zinc diporphyrin-anthracene (**FZnDP**) and corresponding pictorial representation. (c) Schematic representation of mixture of **FZnDP** and **PDI** leads CT complex in CHCl_3 , which results nanospheres and coalesced to form nanorods by diffusion of CH_3OH vapours.

The key results in this study can be summarised as follows:

- Synthetically challenged π -extended, planar and good soluble **FZnDP** was synthesized by treating oxidative intramolecular fusion reaction of **ZnDP**.
- **FZnDP** comprising of two Zn-porphyrins fused by an anthracene group at the *meso*- and β -positions, which resembles a perylene-diporphyrin derivative.
- **FZnDP** allows considerable shifting of the visible absorption band to the near-IR region (854 nm) by decreasing the HOMO–LUMO gap.
- **FZnDP** with **PDI** in a 1:1 molar ratio in CHCl_3 formed that **FZnDP/PDI** as Charge transfer complex, exclusively showed the new absorption band at 940 nm in absorption spectrum, unlike non-fused **ZnDP** and **DP**.
- 1:1 molar ratio of **FZnDP/PDI** showed a significant upfield chemical shift in comparison with the spectra of **FZnDP** and **PDI** alone in ^1H NMR spectrum. New upfield shifts belonging to the fused perylene group of **FZnDP** and, along with an upfield chemical shift of the signals of **PDI**, revealed an interaction between the perylene core in **FZnDP** and **PDI**, which resulted in a CT complex

- Nosey spectroscopy and powder X-ray diffraction analysis demonstrated that the CT complex formation occurs by π - π stacking between perylene in **FZnDP** and **PDI** upon mixing together at 1:1 molar concentration in CHCl_3 ,
- Transmission electron microscopic and atomic force microscopic images revealed that CT complex initially forms nanospheres leading to nanorods by diffusion of CH_3OH vapours into the CHCl_3 solution of **FZnDP/PDI** (1:1 M).

7.5 Future perspectives

The designing of new donor acceptor based systems for harvesting the solar energy, which is the most abundant and eco-friendly renewable energy resource for both the present and future generation. Regardless of these valuable studies, a profound analysis of the results and discussions in previous chapters described in this thesis implies that the strategy of designing D-A systems could be extended still more for getting a deeper understanding of energy and electron transfers as competing quenching pathways. For instance, the design of D-A systems has changed to D- π -A approach where one can expect long-lived charge separated state.

The molecular structures of the newly designed multi chromophoric D- π -A systems are illustrated in Figure 7.5.

Figure 7.5. Molecular structures of D- π -A type porphyrin and corrole systems.

By adopting photoactive chromophores such as porphyrins and corroles, two series of D- π -A systems are designed for functional multicomponent structures for light harvesting system, in which donors phenothiazine, carotene and carbazole are connected at *meso* phenyl position, porphyrin or corrole macrocycle as π -spacer and acceptors as bodipys, perelenediimide and fullerene, at opposite *meso* position of the donor attached to π - spacer. This type of strategy addresses, how we can design and study the effective functional multicomponent structures for achieving charge separation.

The above mentioned design of porphyrin and corrole D- π -A systems having strong electron donor groups and also bulky donors such as carotene groups reduce the aggregation of porphyrin or corrole¹¹⁻¹³. Moreover, strong electron acceptors like fullerene and prelenediimide and good energy acceptor such as Bodipy are used to understand the flow of electron or energy transfer¹⁴⁻¹⁵ and formation of charge separated state. The design of D- π -A based systems are well encouraged to make the molecule useful in artificial photosynthetic reaction centre for a variety of spectroscopic and photochemical investigations.

7.6 References

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